

Deliverable 5.1
Pilots plan, operation and evaluation -
first sprint

WP5 Perform and Evaluate digital
Deliberative Democracy Pilots

T5.1 Pilots and evaluation plan – first
sprint

T5.2 Pilots operation and evaluation –
first sprint

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<p>Abstract: The present deliverable D5.1 documents the outcomes of the "First Sprint" (M7-M15), contributing to the fulfilment of the WP5 objectives: i) to construct models for evaluating acceptance, trust, and usability, ii) to develop concrete evaluation plans for each pilot site, and iii) to pilot results in real-life scenarios. The aim of the deliverable is to (a) present the detailed context and operational planning for the four pilot sites (Germany, Greece, International, Italy), defining their transition to AI-enabled processes, and (b) to establish the evaluation methodology and report the results of the initial internal testing of the project's socio-technical infrastructure. This includes the validation of process guidelines (WP2), institutional frameworks (WP3), the AI toolkit (WP4) and the citizen Acceptance and Trust Model (WP5). These findings set the operational and methodological baseline for the subsequent citizen-facing sprints.</p>	
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Executive Summary

The present deliverable **D5.1: Pilots plan, operation and evaluation – first sprint** constitutes the first reporting iteration of Work Package 5 (WP5). It documents the outcomes of the "First Sprint" (M7-M15) and contributes directly to the fulfilment of the primary objectives of WP5:

- **O5.1:** To construct a model for evaluating acceptance and trust, specifically for AI deliberations, and devise a method to evaluate usability.
- **O5.2:** To develop a concrete evaluation plan for each pilot site.
- **O5.3:** To pilot results in real-life scenarios (focusing in this sprint on internal validation and infrastructure readiness).

The aim of the deliverable is to (a) present the detailed context and operational planning for the four pilot sites, defining their transition to AI-enabled processes, and (b) to establish the evaluation methodology and report the results of the initial internal testing of the project's socio-technical infrastructure.

Section 2 addresses the first objective by detailing the planning and execution of the four pilot cases: the **German pilot** (City of Bamberg), the **Greek pilot** (opengov.gr), the **International pilot** (Long Covid), and the **Italian pilot** (National Climate Change Adaptation Plan). For each pilot, the document employs a uniform documentation structure based on the **WP2 Design Matrix**, mapping the current "AS-IS" deliberation processes against the envisioned "TO-BE" states. This section reports on the specific activities of the first sprint, which prioritised internal simulations, the curation of historical datasets, and role-play exercises by consortium members to validate the feasibility of the proposed workflows before engaging citizens.

Sections 3, 4, and 5 address the evaluation objectives. Section 3 presents the agile evaluation strategy, which divides the project into three sprints, and details the methodology used to assess the four key project components: the **process guidelines (WP2)**, the **institutional framework (WP3)**, the **AI toolkit (WP4)**, and the **acceptance/usability models (WP5)**. Sections 4 and 5 detail the results and lessons learned. The evaluation at this sprint was restricted to **consortium members**.

The current deliverable sets the critical foundations for the **second sprint**. The operational plans and technical feedback recorded here will guide the configuration of tools for pilot administrators and the execution of small-scale pilots with citizens, which will be reported in the subsequent deliverable D5.2.

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Contents

1.	Introduction	11
1.1.	Purpose of this document	11
1.2.	Structure of the document.....	11
2.	Pilots planning and operation	13
2.1.	Greek pilot: National-level deliberations on draft legislation (opengov.gr).....	14
2.1.1.	Background and objectives	14
2.1.2.	AS-IS state.....	15
2.1.3.	TO-BE state.....	17
2.1.4.	Pilot planning, activities and lessons learned	18
2.2.	German pilot.....	20
2.2.1.	Background and objectives	20
2.2.2.	AS-IS state.....	20
2.2.3.	TO-BE state.....	22
2.2.4.	Pilot planning, activities and lessons learned	23
2.3.	International pilot.....	23
2.3.1.	Background and objectives	23
2.3.2.	AS-IS state.....	24
2.3.3.	TO-BE state.....	26
2.3.4.	Pilot planning, activities and lessons learned	26
2.4.	Italian pilot.....	28
2.4.1.	Background and objectives	28
2.4.2.	AS-IS state.....	28
2.4.3.	TO-BE state.....	30
2.4.4.	Pilot planning, activities and lessons learned	31
3.	Evaluation plan – methodology	33
3.1.	Overall Evaluation strategy and dimensions	33
3.2.	Evaluation methodology of AI-enabled Deliberation processes (WP2)	35
3.3.	Evaluation methodology of the comprehensive framework (WP3)	36
3.4.	Evaluation methodology of AI toolkit (WP4)	37
3.5.	Evaluation of acceptance, trust and usability (WP5)	39
4.	Evaluation results	43
4.1.	Evaluation results for AI-enabled Deliberation processes (WP2)	43
4.1.1.	Quantitative evaluation	43
4.1.2.	Qualitative evaluation	45
4.2.	Evaluation results for comprehensive framework (WP3)	47

4.2.1.	WP3 evaluated outcome: Conditions and requirements for institutionalising AI-enabled deliberation	47
4.2.2.	Quantitative evaluation	50
4.2.3.	Qualitative evaluation	52
4.3.	Evaluation results: AI toolkit (WP4)	57
4.3.1.	WP4 evaluated outcomes: AI tools	58
4.3.2.	Data used for the evaluation	60
4.3.3.	Pilot activities for WP4 evaluation	62
4.3.4.	Evaluation results per tool	63
4.3.4.1.	Evaluation results of Summarisation	63
4.3.4.2.	Evaluation results of Moderation	68
4.3.4.3.	Evaluation results of Argument extraction (LLM-based & oAMF)	71
4.3.4.4.	Evaluation results of Translation	75
4.3.4.5.	Evaluation results of ECHO	76
4.3.4.6.	Evaluation results of Topic Modeling	77
4.4.	Results: acceptance, trust and usability (WP5).....	78
5.	Discussion and feedback for next sprints	92
5.1.	Lessons learned per pilot	92
5.2.	Lessons learned per WP2–WP5 components	93
5.2.1.	Lessons learned for AI-enabled Deliberation processes (WP2)	93
5.2.2.	Lessons learned for comprehensive framework (WP3)	95
5.2.3.	Lessons learned for AI tools (WP4).....	95
5.2.4.	Lessons learned for (WP5).....	98
6.	Conclusion	99
	References	100
	Appendix A – AS-IS pilot Questionnaires	113
	Appendix B – WP2 process matrix of pilots	132
	Appendix C – WP2 evaluation questionnaire	147
	Appendix D – WP3 evaluation questionnaire and result.....	150
	Appendix E – WP2 non-aggregate analysis	155
	Appendix F – WP5 literature review eDemocracy	156
	Appendix G – WP5 literature review AI and acceptance	157

Acronyms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI4D	AI4Deliberation project
CAPs	Citizen Amendment Proposals
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
EEA	European Economic Area
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IBIS	Input/Output Buffer Information Specification
LLM	Large-language model
ML	Machine learning
NCCAP	National Climate Change Adaptation Plan
oAMF	Open Argument Mining Framework
SEAB	Scientific Ethics Advisory Board
SEM	Structural Equation Modelling
WP	Work Package
xAIF	eXtended Argument Interchange Format

Partners List Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Description
UNIS	UNI SYSTEMS SYSTMATA PLIROFORIKIS MONOPROSOPI ANONYMI EMPORIKI ETAIRIA - UNI SYSTEMS INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY SYSTEMS COMMERCIAL S.M.S.A.
TUD	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT - TU Delft
CERTH	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS - CENTRE FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY HELLAS CERTH
UBAM	OTTO-FRIEDRICH-UNIVERSITAET BAMBERG - UNI BA
KT	KONNEKT ABLE TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED - Konnekt-able Technologies
UNIVDUN	UNIVERSITY OF DUNDEE - UNIVDUN
IK	INŠTITUT ZA KRIMINOLOGIJO PRI PRAVNI FAKULTETI V LJUBLJANI - INSTITUTE OF CRIMINOLOGY AT THE FACULTY OF LAW LJUBLJANA
BRANE	Dembrane B.V. - Dembrane
TG	THOUGHTGRAPH LTD - TG
GFOSS	ETAIREIA ELEYTHEROY LOGISMIKOY ANOIKTOY KODIKA - GFOSS
AAIT	ACTIONAID INTERNATIONAL ITALIA ETS - ACTIONAID INTERNATIONAL ITALIA ETS
CBAM	Stadt Bamberg – City of Bamberg
UZH	UNIVERSITY OF ZÜRICH

Table of Figures

Figure 1 AS-IS Greek pilot	17
Figure 2 TO-BE Greek pilot.....	18
Figure 3: AS-IS Deliberation Process (German Pilot). Overview of the current deliberation process in the City of Bamberg, illustrating an open but weakly structured participation lifecycle with manual aggregation and limited feedback mechanisms.	21
Figure 4: TO-BE Deliberation Process with AI Support (German Pilot). Envisioned deliberation lifecycle for the German pilot, showing a staged process with targeted participation, structured deliberation, and AI-supported analysis and feedback to enhance inclusiveness, transparency, and administrative efficiency.	22
Figure 5: AS-IS Deliberation Process (International Pilot)	25
Figure 6: TO-BE Deliberation Process with AI Support (International Pilot) – The dimensions in which the potential for AI enhancement is being explored are highlighted in green.	26
Figure 7: An Overview of the Current Iteration of the Long Covid Deliberation Graph.....	27
Figure 8: AS-IS state in AAIT deliberative process. The diagram summarises the main critical aspect of the current deliberative processes, broken down by phase.....	30
Figure 9: TO-BE state in AAIT deliberative process. The diagram summarises the AI-enabled features that should be implemented according to the three stages of deliberation.	30
Figure 10: Descriptive respondents.....	43
Figure 11: Questions-respondents’ matrix averages.....	44
Figure 12: Respondents-organisation overall average.....	44
Figure 13: Box-plot outlier per question	45

PENDING EC APPROVAL

Table of Tables

Table 1. Summary of the suggestions-critical points.....	45
Table 2. Conditions and requirements related to fostering democratic values (meaningful deliberation)	48
Table 3. Conditions and requirements related to guaranteeing the effectiveness of mass deliberation (meaningful deliberation)	49
Table 4. Conditions and requirements related to practising adaptive governance (sustainable integration).....	49
Table 5. Conditions and requirements related to cultivating long-term support (sustainable integration).....	50
Table 6. Conditions and requirements related to situating AI-enabled mass deliberation in existing organizational practices	50
Table 7. Constructs and their facets definitions	82
Table 8. Items per construct (In parentheses, the target construct or facet of the item is presented)	86

PENDING EC APPROVAL

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of this document

Work Package (WP) 5 “Perform and Evaluate digital Deliberative Democracy Pilots” aims to:

- i) O5.1 To construct a model for evaluating acceptance and trust, specifically for AI deliberations, and devise a method to evaluate usability,
- ii) O5.2 To develop a concrete evaluation plan for each pilot site and
- iii) O5.3 To pilot all our results in four real-life scenarios.

Specifically, WP5 focuses on evaluating the project's outputs through three iterative sprints, ensuring that the developed processes, AI tools and frameworks meet the needs of stakeholders and enhance democratic processes.

This deliverable, D5.1: Pilots plan, operation and evaluation - first sprint, reports on the results of the first two tasks of WP5: T5.1 “Pilots and evaluation plan – first sprint” and T5.2 “Pilots operation and evaluation – first sprint”. T5.1 involved detailing the context and planning for each pilot based on the initial outputs from WP2, WP3, and WP4, while T5.2 focused on the actual execution and internal evaluation of these pilots.

The primary purpose of D5.1 is to document the "AS-IS" and "TO-BE" states of the four pilot cases, present the methodology used for the first round of evaluation, and report the operational results and lessons learned from this initial sprint. This first sprint focused primarily on internal testing and controlled simulations to assess technical feasibility and output quality before broader deployment. The insights gathered in D5.1 will inform the updates to the pilot plans and evaluation strategies for the second sprint, as well as the developments of the other technical Work Packages (WP2, WP3, WP4).

1.2. Structure of the document

Addressing the dual objectives of planning and evaluation, the deliverable is structured into five main sections as follows:

- **Section 2** presents the comprehensive documentation and planning for the four pilots: the German pilot, the Greek pilot, the International pilot and the Italian pilot. For each pilot, this section details the background, the current "AS-IS" deliberation processes, the envisioned "TO-BE" states integrating AI support, and the specific planning and activities undertaken during the first sprint.
- **Section 3** outlines the evaluation methodology applied during this sprint. It describes the strategies used to assess the project's core outcomes, including: i) the AI-enabled deliberation process (WP2), the comprehensive framework for institutionalisation (WP3), the AI tool (WP4) and the acceptance and usability models (WP5).
- **Section 4** reports the detailed evaluation results for all project's core outcomes (WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5) based on the methodology described in Section 3.
- **Section 5** discusses the feedback and implications for future iterations. It synthesises the improvement actions required for each pilot and specifies the necessary updates for the technological and methodological components in WP2 through WP5 for the next sprint.

- Finally, **Section 6** concludes the document, summarising the key takeaways from the first sprint.

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2. Pilots planning and operation

This section documents the planning, execution, and contextual background of the four AI4Deliberation pilots. For each pilot, this section details the specific objectives and stakeholders involved, alongside a comparative analysis of the current "AS-IS" deliberation processes and the envisioned "TO-BE" states. This analysis highlights the transition from manual, often fragmented processes to AI-assisted processes designed to improve scalability, inclusiveness, and administrative efficiency. Finally, the section reports on the specific planning activities, internal testing, and lessons learned during this initial sprint, setting the stage for the subsequent sprints.

The activities reported in this deliverable encompass the first sprint of the pilots, structured into two distinct but interconnected tasks: **Pilot Planning (T5.1)** and **Pilot Operation and Evaluation (T5.2)**.

Pilot Planning (T5.1) This phase focused on defining the operational context and strategic vision for each pilot site. To rigorously map the deliberative landscape, a two-step methodological approach was employed:

- **AS-IS Analysis (June):** Structured interviews were conducted with pilot teams using a dedicated questionnaire to capture the baseline situation, identifying existing workflows, bottlenecks, and stakeholder needs. The **questionnaires for each pilot are available in Appendix A.**
- **Process Design (September–October):** Collaborative workshops were held utilising the **WP2 Design Matrix**. In these sessions, partners mapped their current AS-IS processes and co-designed the envisioned "TO-BE" states, integrating AI-enabled functionalities into their specific governance structures. The complete **matrix per pilot is available in Appendix B.**

Pilot Operation and Evaluation (T5.2), following the planning phase, the operation task focused on the practical execution of the first sprint. This phase was characterised by internal testing and the generation of evidence to validate project components before public deployment. Key activities included:

- **Data Selection and Generation:** Pilots generated controlled datasets through role-play simulations (German and Italian pilots) or curated historical and external datasets (Greek and International pilots) to serve as the ground truth for testing.
- **Evaluation of WP2 Process Guidelines, WP3 Framework and WP4 Tools.** More details on the evaluations are provided in Sections 3 (evaluation methodology) and Section 4 (evaluation results).

The next sections detail the operational context for the four pilot sites by contrasting their current "AS-IS" deliberation processes with the envisioned "TO-BE" states. For each pilot, the following subsections outline the background and objectives, followed by a mapping of the transition from manual or legacy workflows to the proposed AI-enabled deliberation lifecycles. This structure ensures a clear definition of the operational requirements and strategic goals guiding the pilot execution.

2.1. Greek pilot: National-level deliberations on draft legislation (opengov.gr)

2.1.1. Background and objectives

The Greek pilot is implemented within the context of Greece's national legislative process and focuses on enhancing digital public deliberation on draft legislation through the *opengov.gr* platform. This platform represents Greece's official electronic public consultation system, operated under the oversight of the Ministry of Digital Government and the General Secretariat for Legal and Parliamentary Affairs in the Presidency of the Government. The pilot builds on 16 years of opengov.gr operational experience and responds to well-documented challenges related to comment moderation workload, synthesis of citizen feedback, and the generation of consultation reports required by the legislative process.

The platform's track record is substantial: over 1,238 deliberations have been conducted, accumulating more than 417,521 citizen comments across 28 public bodies. This extensive corpus of deliberation data provides both a critical resource for AI tool development and testing and a compelling case for AI-enhanced deliberation support. The platform operates on a WordPress-based open-source architecture, with the template design and source code publicly available.

The legal mandate for public consultation derives from Law 4622/2019, which establishes a structured five-stage legislative drafting process. Article 63 of this law mandates that the General Secretariat for Legal and Parliamentary Affairs, in cooperation with the sponsoring Ministry, shall publish the draft law and Regulatory Impact Analysis on *opengov.gr* for public consultation, typically lasting two weeks. The consultation period may be shortened to one week or extended by an additional week only in exceptional, well-justified circumstances.

The **objectives** of the Greek pilot can be articulated across several dimensions:

- First, the pilot aims to reduce the administrative burden associated with comment moderation and synthesis, thereby enabling Ministry staff to focus on substantive policy analysis.
- Second, it seeks to improve the quality and timeliness of consultation reports that accompany draft legislation when submitted to Parliament.
- Third, the pilot aspires to enhance transparency and citizen engagement by providing better-organised feedback even while deliberations are ongoing.
- Finally, the pilot pursues compliance with existing legal frameworks while exploring innovative AI applications that can be scaled across the Greek public administration.

Key **stakeholders** involved in the pilot include:

- Ministry administrators: responsible for launching and managing consultations
- Platform moderators: who review and approve citizen comments
- Citizens and commenters who participate in public deliberations
- Policy makers (MPs included): who utilise consultation outcomes in legislative debates and voting
- Civil society: organisations that actively participate in legislative consultations

- Research community: interested in deliberative democracy and AI applications

The pilot is coordinated by GFOSS (Greek Free/Open Source Software Society), with involvement from consortium partners UNIS, CERTH, KT, IK, and UNIVDUN. GFOSS contributes platform expertise, Greek deliberation data preparation for LLM testing, requirements specification, integration validation, and quality assurance.

In terms of expected **impact**, the pilot anticipates both quantitative and qualitative outcomes. Quantitative outcomes include reduced moderation time, accelerated report generation, increased comment processing capacity, and potentially higher participation rates. Qualitative impacts encompass better-organised citizen feedback, more insightful summary reports, improved trust in the quality of deliberation as perceived by stakeholders, enhanced citizen engagement, and ultimately more evidence-based policy making.

2.1.2. AS-IS state

Overall

In its current form, public consultation on opengov.gr operates within a structured legal framework but relies heavily on manual processes throughout the deliberation lifecycle. The consultation process is initiated top-down by the sponsoring Ministry, which defines the draft legislation and supporting materials to be published. Participation is open to all citizens through self-selection to participate, requiring only a valid email address for comment submission.

The deliberation structure follows the draft law's article-by-article organisation. Citizens may comment on individual articles or provide general observations. However, they cannot comment on the regulatory impact analysis. Comments are submitted through a simple text interface and are moderated before publication. The moderation process, conducted by Ministry staff, verifies compliance with the terms of participation—primarily checking for inappropriate content, spam, or off-topic submissions—before making comments publicly visible.

Output generation represents the most resource-intensive phase of the current process. Following the conclusion of the consultation period, the Ministry's Coordination Service is required by Law 4622/2019 to prepare a comprehensive report that groups and synthesises participant comments and proposals, provides a reasoned recommendation on whether to incorporate them into the final legislative text, publishes this report on the platform where the consultation took place, and communicates the report to all participants via their registered email addresses.

The AS-IS state presents several documented challenges. Manual comment moderation creates processing bottlenecks, particularly for high-volume consultations. The synthesis of large numbers of comments into coherent thematic clusters requires substantial human effort and time. Comprehensive report generation is labour-intensive and often delayed relative to the legislative timeline. There is limited capacity for argument analysis beyond surface-level categorisation. Quality control remains resource-intensive, and there are no mechanisms for providing real-time feedback to participants during the consultation period.

Based on the WP2 matrix

The current AS-IS deliberation process on opengov.gr can be characterised across its three main phases: pre-deliberation, deliberation, and post-deliberation.

In the *pre-deliberation phase*, the process begins when the Legislative Drafting Committee completes its work on the draft law and Regulatory Impact Analysis. The General Secretariat for Legal and Parliamentary Affairs, in coordination with the sponsoring Ministry, publishes these documents on opengov.gr. An introductory text by the Minister accompanies the publication, explaining the law's objectives and inviting public participation. The consultation period is announced, typically lasting two weeks. Information provision is limited to the published documents themselves, with minimal additional contextual framing or accessibility support.

During the *deliberation phase*, participation is open and self-selected. Citizens may comment on any article or section of the draft law. Comments are submitted individually and moderated manually before publication. There is no structured phasing of the discussion—all comments on all provisions are accepted throughout the consultation period. The discussion unfolds as a linear accumulation of comments without systematic differentiation between types of contributions (e.g., factual observations, policy arguments, technical suggestions, or expressions of support or opposition). Participants receive no immediate feedback on the deliberative status of issues they have raised.

In the *post-deliberation phase*, following the closure of the consultation period, Ministry staff manually review all submitted comments. The Coordination Service of each competent Ministry prepares a consultation report that groups comments thematically and provides reasoned recommendations on their incorporation into the final text. This report is published on the Hellenic Parliament platform and on opengov.gr albeit not systematically. The draft law, accompanied by the consultation report, is then submitted to Parliament for discussion and voting.

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Figure 1 AS-IS Greek pilot

2.1.3. TO-BE state

Based on the WP2 matrix

In the envisioned TO-BE state, the deliberation process is enhanced through the integration of AI-supported functionalities while maintaining full compliance with the existing legal framework under Law 4622/2019. The transformation affects each phase of the deliberation lifecycle.

In the *pre-deliberation phase*, the publication of consultation materials continues as mandated by law. However, AI-supported tools may assist in preparing supplementary explanatory materials that make complex legislative provisions more accessible to non-specialist participants. This, for example, could include simplified summaries of key provisions, visual representations of regulatory changes, or multimodal guides/personas that help citizens navigate the structure of the draft law.

The *deliberation phase* benefits most substantially from AI enhancement. Comment clustering enables real-time organisation of submissions by theme, allowing both administrators and participants to see emerging patterns in the discussion. Sentiment analysis supports moderation by flagging potentially problematic content for human review, reducing the manual screening burden. As comments accumulate, AI-generated summaries provide stakeholders with evolving overviews of the main themes and positions expressed—not as authoritative outputs, but as supporting material that complements human judgment.

Figure 2 TO-BE Greek pilot

In the *post-deliberation phase*, AI-supported summarisation and argument extraction substantially accelerate report generation. The tools provide structured drafts that Ministry staff can review, refine, and finalise rather than building reports from scratch. This reduces the time between consultation closure and report publication while maintaining human oversight over all outputs. Enhanced feedback mechanisms reconnect outcomes to participants, potentially including more detailed explanations of how specific types of input influenced the final legislative text.

Throughout the TO-BE process, AI tools function as supporting material rather than authoritative outputs. Human oversight remains essential at all decision points, consistent with both the legal requirements of Law 4622/2019 and the ethical framework established by the AI4Deliberation project.

2.1.4. Pilot planning, activities and lessons learned

The Greek pilot (as all the project pilots) operates across three sprints spanning project months 7 to 33, with progressively expanding scope and stakeholder involvement.

For Sprint 1: evaluation was conducted internally by GFOSS technical staff and consortium members. The pilot provided annotated Greek-language consultation data for testing WP4 tools, including 42 annotated comments for moderation pipeline evaluation and consultation datasets for summarisation and argument extraction assessment (more info on the provided

data is available in Section 3). The evaluation focused on output quality, Greek language compliance, and practical usability in the consultation context.

Substantial preparatory work has been completed to ensure compliance with GDPR and Greek Law 4624/2019. A Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) has been prepared addressing GDPR requirements. For Sprint 1, which focused on historical data from past consultations, personal identifiers were removed to create effectively anonymised datasets. The lawful basis for processing original consultation data derives from Article 6(1)(c) (legal obligation) and Article 6(1)(e) (public interest task) of the GDPR, as stated in the opengov.gr privacy policy.

Several challenges have been identified through the first sprint activities:

- **Greek language compliance:** Evaluation revealed that not all AI tools perform reliably with Greek-language content. Claude 4 Sonnet was assessed as the most consistently useful tool for Greek consultations, while LLaMA 3.3 70B showed language instability (mixed Greek-English content, corrupted terms) that undermines credibility for official-facing synthesis. Topic extraction outputs were delivered in English rather than Greek, failing to meet basic specifications. Mitigation involves prioritising tools with demonstrated Greek language reliability and enforcing strict language settings throughout processing pipelines.
- **Moderation pipeline accuracy:** Testing of three moderation configurations on 42 annotated pilot comments revealed error rates of 31% (LLM-only), 36% (LlamaGuard → LLM), and 26% (Detoxify → LlamaGuard → LLM). The multi-stage pipeline achieved better accuracy, particularly for hate speech detection, but all configurations showed weaknesses in detecting spam, advertisements, and off-topic content. A specific 'Greek profanity blind spot' was identified where some Greek slurs and personal attacks went undetected. Mitigation requires expanded prompt coverage for spam/off-topic categories and enhanced Greek-language moderation rules.
- **Topic extraction reliability:** Evaluated outputs produced generic governance topics (migration, housing, polarisation) that did not align with actual consultation content (e.g., education staffing, animal welfare, offshore taxation). The system appeared to apply static taxonomies rather than extracting themes from text, rendering outputs unusable and potentially misleading. This functionality requires substantial redesign before deployment.
- **Government stakeholder coordination:** Successful deployment requires ongoing coordination with Ministry administrators and the Office of Better Regulation. Changes to consultation workflows must align with established procedures and legal requirements under Law 4622/2019.

Plans for Sprint 2: Building on Sprint 1 findings, the second sprint will focus on refined tool deployment with emphasis on language compliance, limited public testing with one to two selected deliberations involving citizens, closer integration with Ministry workflows and documentation for administrators, enhanced moderation pipelines addressing identified gaps in spam/off-topic detection and Greek profanity coverage, and structured feedback collection mechanisms to inform further refinement. The transition from internal testing to limited public deployment will require careful coordination with government stakeholders and clear communication to participating citizens about the research dimension of their consultation involvement.

2.2. German pilot

2.2.1. Background and objectives

The German pilot is situated in the context of municipal participation processes in the City of Bamberg and focuses on strengthening digital and hybrid deliberation in urban governance. The pilot builds on existing participation formats—both online (via Consul) and in-person—and responds to well-documented challenges related to inclusiveness, scalability, transparency, and administrative workload. Organisationally, the pilot is coordinated by the Smart City Office, which assumes responsibility for overall project management and strategic alignment, while the Office for Citizen Participation acts as the central consultation agency, drawing on its experience in moderating, structuring, and evaluating participatory processes. Citizens constitute the primary target group, both as contributors to deliberation and as beneficiaries of more transparent and responsive participation formats.

The overarching **objective** is not merely to digitise participation, but to restructure deliberation as a coherent, transparent, and inclusive process that more effectively connects citizen input with administrative workflows and political decision-making. From the vision articulated for the pilot, several guiding objectives emerge.

- First, the pilot aims to broaden participation and reduce structural inequalities, moving beyond self-selection toward more diverse and representative engagement.
- Second, it seeks to increase procedural clarity across the deliberation lifecycle, enabling participants to better understand how discussions evolve from agenda setting through deliberation to outcomes.
- Third, the pilot aspires to enhance transparency and feedback, ensuring that citizens can trace how their contributions are processed, interpreted, and used by the administration and political bodies.
- Finally, the pilot pursues institutional reliability and legal certainty, allowing the city administration to explore AI-supported innovation while maintaining accountability, compliance, and trust.

In terms of expected **impact**, the pilot is intended to strengthen the legitimacy and effectiveness of municipal participation by improving both the quality of deliberative exchanges and the visibility of their outcomes. For citizens, this is expected to translate into greater trust, clearer feedback, and a stronger sense of meaningful involvement. For the administration, the anticipated impact lies in reduced manual workload, improved process oversight, and more systematic integration of citizen input into policy preparation. Taken together, these effects are expected to contribute to more resilient, inclusive, and future-oriented urban governance structures.

2.2.2. AS-IS state

Overall

In its current form, citizen participation in Bamberg is open and accessible but largely unstructured. Recruitment relies almost exclusively on self-selection, both online and in-person, which limits diversity and reach. Agenda setting is solely arranged top-down, with topics defined by the city administration or political actors and presented to citizens with minimal contextual framing. Participation rules are implicit rather than actively

communicated, and deliberation unfolds in a single, undifferentiated discussion space without clearly defined phases.

Output generation and review are handled manually by municipal staff, who summarise contributions and prepare decision templates for the city council. While this process is conducted with care, it remains opaque from the perspective of participants, who receive little immediate feedback. Overall, the AS-IS state enables participation but remains fragmented, labour-intensive, and weakly connected across stages, placing high demands on administrative interpretation and limiting participants' sense of impact.

Based on the WP2 matrix

In the current AS-IS state, the deliberation process in the City of Bamberg is open and accessible but largely unstructured across its lifecycle. Participation is based on open self-selection, with limited mechanisms for targeted outreach or diversification of participants. Agenda setting follows a top-down logic, with topics defined by the city administration or political actors and presented to citizens with a short descriptive background text.

Rules of engagement are minimally specified and accepted through a simple confirmation step, without active onboarding or guidance on deliberative behaviour. Deliberation itself takes place in a single open discussion space, structured as comments and replies, without explicit phases for problem definition, reflection, or solution development. Contributions of varying types—opinions, reactions, arguments, and emotional responses—coexist without systematic differentiation.

Figure 3: AS-IS Deliberation Process (German Pilot). Overview of the current deliberation process in the City of Bamberg, illustrating an open but weakly structured participation lifecycle with manual aggregation and limited feedback mechanisms.

Following the discussion phase, municipal staff manually review the contributions and prepare a summary report that serves as input for political decision-making. Review and quality assessment are also conducted manually. Feedback to participants is limited and typically delayed, and the broader public is informed through standard municipal communication channels. Overall, the process functions but remains fragmented, labour-

intensive, and weakly transparent, relying heavily on administrative interpretation rather than shared procedural clarity.

2.2.3. TO-BE state

In the envisioned TO-BE state, the deliberation process is restructured as a clearly staged and continuous lifecycle, spanning pre-deliberation, deliberation, and post-deliberation phases. Participation remains open but is complemented by targeted outreach mechanisms to broaden inclusion and reduce structural inequalities. Agenda setting is transformed into a more collaborative process, supported by preparatory offline or hybrid formats involving citizens and city representatives.

Participants are guided into the process through structured onboarding, including clear explanations of discussion rules and accessible learning materials. Information provision is expanded through multiple formats, including concise texts and AI-supported assistance, ensuring that participants enter the deliberation phase with a shared knowledge base.

Figure 4: TO-BE Deliberation Process with AI Support (German Pilot). Envisioned deliberation lifecycle for the German pilot, showing a staged process with targeted participation, structured deliberation, and AI-supported analysis and feedback to enhance inclusiveness, transparency, and administrative efficiency.

Deliberation itself unfolds in distinct phases, beginning with problem definition, followed by open discussion, reflection, and collaborative solution-building. AI-supported functions assist by simplifying language, supporting moderation, and helping participants navigate complex argumentative landscapes. These supports are designed to enhance inclusion and deliberative quality, not to replace human judgment.

In the post-deliberation phase, outputs are generated more systematically and transparently. Automated summaries and visual overviews support administrative review and political use, while feedback loops reconnect outcomes to participants and the wider public. As a result, the TO-BE process strengthens transparency, reduces administrative workload, and fosters a

clearer connection between citizen input and decision-making, aligning deliberation with the principles of accountability, inclusiveness, and legal certainty.

2.2.4. Pilot planning, activities and lessons learned

The first sprint of the German pilot focused on internal testing under controlled conditions, using a small, simulated deliberation with municipal staff, which was then evaluated by the responsible project manager. In addition, contact has already been made with the service provider behind our Consul instance (DemokratieToday), as they have been commissioned by a nearby German city to create a Consul substructure for the German context for the simple implementation of various AI architectures. They have promised to support us with the necessary interface definition. In addition, various workshops were held in which we evaluated our current situation or defined a vision in an interview setting. In another workshop, we then applied this defined vision of AI-supported deliberation to the process defined in WP 2. In addition, all project progress was communicated internally to the necessary stakeholders and promoted externally via our website and blog posts. Building on these experiences, the next sprint will expand participation to approximately 20 citizens, recruited through 'Zielgruppenanwälte', citizens representing diverse civil groups (e.g., people with disabilities, students, women, migrants). Due to technical constraints, ECHO will likely be used again as a standalone environment, with the same tools retested alongside additional candidates.

In the final sprint, ECHO and Consul might be used in parallel. The audio transcription and analysis tool ECHO may serve as a more playful, low-threshold engagement space—for example, in informal settings such as brewery discussions, for advertising purposes—while Consul remains the formal participation platform. These activities may also support agenda setting for the final evaluation round, contingent on political support.

Several lessons have emerged. Most importantly, greater attention must be paid to the full deliberation lifecycle, as this significantly influences pilot design and timing. Preparation must begin earlier, particularly when citizen involvement is planned. At the same time, defining a strict, linear process remains challenging in asynchronous deliberation settings, requiring flexibility without sacrificing coherence. These insights will directly inform the design of subsequent pilot phases.

2.3. International pilot

2.3.1. Background and objectives

The AI4Deliberation International Pilot, implemented by Thoughtgraph (TG), addresses the global deliberation challenge presented by the emergence, global spread, and continuing impact of the SARS-CoV-2 virus and, in particular, the individual and societal impacts of long COVID.

Effective deliberation in this context requires (among other things):

- the dynamic integration of complex, uncertain, proliferating and evolving evidence,
- surfacing, listening to, and understanding the stories of the people affected,
- identifying impacts across multiple interrelated policy areas, and
- identifying and exploring multiple potential public policy responses.

The International Pilot aims to ground and support this process by:

- building a dynamically updated and collaboratively editable deliberation graph of long COVID using DebateGraph, and
- using the graph to engage with international stakeholders – including patient groups, scientists, health professionals, and policy makers – in the places where these deliberative conversations are already taking place.

The International Pilot also aims to explore whether:

- AI tools can help stakeholders engage effectively with the knowledge represented in the graphs of this kind, and
- Machine reading can accelerate the human curation of graphs, and the graphs can increase the signal-to-noise ratio arising from the machine reading of the policy-related documents.

The International Pilot differs from the other pilots in that it:

- (1) aims to create a global sensemaking resource to support deliberative processes wherever and whenever they are occurring in the world, rather than delivering an end-to-end deliberative and/or decision-making process in a given place at a specific time.
- (2) focuses on scaling the ideas that are guiding the deliberative processes rather than the quantity of people who are participating in the process directly.

These distinct objectives also create distinct interests and needs with respect to the application of AI to the process.

2.3.2. AS-IS state

Overall

The AI4Deliberation pilot is using the DebateGraph platform, which has been used in multiple government and other institutional contexts over the last 20 years, and has featured in national and international TV, radio and newspapers discussions of public policy.

The platform is designed to support continuous, cumulative, collaborative, open-ended deliberative sensemaking through the co-creation of large-scale deliberation graphs, focused on complex policy topics with multiple interrelated dimensions (e.g., climate, global health challenges, nuclear policy, etc.).

Participation is typically via self-selection: anyone can sign up to participate, with a log-in required and pseudonymous participation (linked to a valid email address) permitted. Participants are not offered an incentive to participate beyond the intrinsic motivation of using a free tool to share and build on their thinking openly and globally to support public understanding of important policy topics.

In principle, an unlimited number of people can participate in all aspects of the graph-building process; in practice, the majority of people participate as readers, a minority are intermittent contributors, and a few individuals act as the primary curators. Thus, the deliberative process focuses more on identifying and weaving together the ideas and evidence that are being

expressed in other communication channels than on requiring people to (re)express their views directly on the platform, and the guiding ethos for contributors is to seek identify and represent the perspectives of all relevant policy stakeholders fairly and in full.

The deliberation proceeds as a live, continuous, evolution of the graph through new contributions (including adding new nodes, comments, citations, cross-links, and ratings), with the graph acting as an open, central repository for the whole community's thought, and the graph embodying its own narrative output; a living document of the community's current reflections on the subject at hand.

Based on the WP2 matrix

The International Pilot frames societal deliberation on complex policy topics as a continuously updating sensemaking process that informs punctuated decisions in different formal contexts at different times.

The distributed sensemaking process can be captured and surfaced as an open, continuously updated policy graph to support—and/or act as an external, transparent check and balance on—the flow of those punctuated local, national and international decisions.

The building blocks of the graph are the ideas and the connections between them, and the primary participants are (i) people who are already sharing their contributions to the global policy conversation elsewhere, and (ii) people who are using the graph to inform their own sensemaking and decisions on the policy questions.

Figure 5: AS-IS Deliberation Process (International Pilot)

Underlying this process, a (typically) small group of participants engage directly in curating the graph. The curation is carried out openly so that (i) anyone who wishes to contribute directly is welcomed and able to do so (whether contributing a single input or sustained curation over time), and (ii) any errors and/or omissions can be challenged directly and iteratively improved.

Historically, the deliberative utility of these policy graphs has been constrained by two factors:

1. the reliance on the underlying layer of curators for creating and evolving the policy graphs (which is a painstaking, time- and labour-intensive process that requires significant commitment),
2. the time and attention required from deliberators and decision makers to interpret the policy graphs.

2.3.3. TO-BE state

AI tools have the potential to significantly reduce the frictions involved in each of these dimensions. Hence, the primary goal for the TO-BE state is to integrate AI capabilities into the graphing process to make it easier and faster for people to build and interpret the graphs, and to achieve this with similar levels of quality and trust as the human curation process.

Potential enhancements sought as part of this process include: enabling participants to use AI to add new structure to the graph (including ideas and citations), question, expand, and deepen aspects of the graph, and automatically generate summaries of parts or the whole of the graph.

Figure 6: TO-BE Deliberation Process with AI Support (International Pilot) – The dimensions in which the potential for AI enhancement is being explored are highlighted in green.

The stretch goal is to be able to use AI to rapidly and automatically generate large scale graphs – akin to those generated by expert curators – on any policy topic; thereby enabling these rich policy graphs to be deployed quickly and simply to support collective sensemaking in a multitude of formal deliberative decision-making contexts.

Other emerging features of the AI4Deliberation toolkit – such as gamification – will be studied carefully for potential opportunities to enhance the existing social processes involved in the graph curation.

2.3.4. Pilot planning, activities and lessons learned

The first (internal) sprint of the International pilot – evaluated by Thoughtgraph’s senior management team – has focused on creating and building the first (private) iteration of the long covid deliberation graph to a point of maturity at which it can be credibly shared with the

external stakeholders in the second and third sprints. The current iteration of the long covid graph, illustrated below, comprises 4,150 nodes, 10,200 citations and 10,230 cross-links.

The deliberation graph also includes an initial landscape analysis of long covid international stakeholders, who will be approached as potential participants in the subsequent public AI4Deliberation pilot sprints.

As expected, the set of science, advocacy and policy publications on long COVID has continued to expand rapidly since the AI4Deliberation project was first conceived; a pattern that increases the practical challenge for the human curators and strengthens the case for (effective) AI enhancement.

Figure 7: An Overview of the Current Iteration of the Long Covid Deliberation Graph

As detailed later in this document, the outcome of the first round of testing of the AI tools was not immediately promising in the context of the specific characteristics and high bar of need and expectation for the AI tools in support of the goals of the International Pilot. However, the first sprint tests have identified promising pathways for the second sprint, including experimenting with using the outputs of the LLMs as inputs for the argument mining tools. Moreover, the rate of release of the new AI models and the observed improvements in the capabilities of the new models offer grounds for optimism that the specific needs of International Pilot may be met between the start of the second sprint and the end of the third sprint.

In parallel with the initial development of the long covid graph and the testing of the AI tools, the International Pilot team has engaged in a detailed and productive review with the AI4Deliberation Consortium's internal ethics team on the data protection and other ethical dimensions of the International Pilot; including identifying UK-based options for the

subsequent external ethical review, and the mitigation of the initial potential risks identified as part of the internal ethics review.

2.4. Italian pilot

2.4.1. Background and objectives

The Italian pilot is implemented by ActionAid Italy (AAIT) within the AI4Deliberation project and focuses on a national-level deliberation on the National Climate Change Adaptation Plan (NCCAP). Climate change adaptation is a complex and technical policy field, characterised by long-term planning horizons, uncertainty, and the need to balance scientific evidence with social, economic, and territorial evidence and forecasts. In Italy, public participation in climate adaptation policies remains limited and often fragmented. This pilot responds to the need to provide feedback to a national policy that needs to be updated and experiment with innovative deliberative formats capable of fostering informed, inclusive, and meaningful citizen engagement.

The main **objective** of the Italian pilot is to test how AI-supported tools can enhance deliberative democracy processes on a national policy level. More specifically, the pilot aims to: (i) improve citizens' access to complex policy information through AI-based summarisation and simplification; (ii) support moderators in managing discussions and synthesising outcomes; (iii) generate evidence and results that can inform a public policy and future large-scale deliberative processes. These objectives are also accompanied by the need to assess the ethical, organisational, and technical implications of introducing AI tools and functionalities in deliberative settings.

Key **stakeholders** involved in the pilot include AAIT staff for the first sprint; project technical partners within AI4Deliberation for the AI-enabled setting and evaluation; experts for the information phase; and public institutions responsible for NCCAP for the second and third sprints. Also, citizens are central stakeholders in the second and third pilot sprint, where a deliberative process will be tested on a small and large scale, simulating a citizens' panel.

The expected **impact** of the pilot includes improved quality and inclusiveness of deliberation, enhanced understanding of climate adaptation policies among participants, structured and well-defined recommendations for the Plan update, and increased organisational capacity to run AI-supported deliberative processes. At the project level, the pilot - along with the other three - contributes to building a shared knowledge base on the responsible use of AI in democratic innovation.

2.4.2. AS-IS state

Overall

The overall AS-IS state of deliberative processes in the Italian context highlighted several recurrent challenges. The primary challenge is representation and inclusion: even well-designed deliberative processes can struggle to recruit participants who truly reflect the diversity of the broader population, leading to unequal participation and unheard voices. Another common problem is information asymmetry and cognitive load. Participants often face complex information without sufficient support, which can disadvantage those with lower levels of prior knowledge or education and can skew deliberation towards more informed or vocal individuals. Facilitation quality and neutrality are also important elements

to take into consideration. Lack of professional moderation can lead to domination by more assertive participants, unequal speaking time, conflict, and polarisation, which can undermine constructive dialogue if they aren't managed properly. Another important concrete element is the process fatigue and low participation rates at the end (with a significant drop-out phenomenon along the process), especially if citizens feel deliberation does not lead to real influence, reinforcing cynicism rather than engagement. Furthermore, the processes involve a very demanding organisational and managerial burden for those who initiate them and require considerable human and financial resources to be completed. Finally, political will and institutional embedding are frequently lacking. Without strong commitment from policymakers and institutional frameworks that recognise deliberative outcomes, recommendations can be ignored or sidelined.

The most common deliberative formats in recent years in Italy have been deliberative assemblies on climate change, which in many cases reflected the challenges and the issues mentioned above.

Based on the WP2 matrix

Prior to the pilot, deliberative processes within AAIT relied primarily on traditional, moderator and organiser-led methodologies and techniques. Information materials were prepared manually, often resulting in long and technically complex documents. Moderation, note-taking, and reporting were highly resource-intensive and depended on the skills and availability of human resources. In a hybrid deliberative process, the entire digital part was organised by the staff, who put a great effort into moderating the process, checking and accepting comments before publishing them.

The overall AS-IS state addresses various and recurrent issues: difficulty in navigating extensive policy documents, limited accessibility for participants with different levels of expertise, time constraints during discussions, and challenges in synthesising diverse viewpoints into coherent outputs.

In particular, the overall AS-IS analysis reveals that the deliberative process relies almost entirely on human facilitation and manual workflows. Generally, context information documents are collected and adapted by staff, often resulting in lengthy and technically complex materials. More specific information is delivered mainly through expert presentations, with limited capacity to tailor content to different levels of knowledge and accessibility needs. During deliberation, moderators play a central role in managing discussions and recording inputs, which creates a significant organisational burden. The synthesis phase is particularly resource-intensive, as facilitators manually aggregate diverse viewpoints into coherent outputs. The post-deliberation phase focuses on consolidating, validating, and translating deliberative outputs into actionable and transparent recommendations. This is a critical stage of the deliberative process, as it determines how participants' inputs are translated into final outputs and how trust in the overall process is consolidated. This phase includes institutional delivery, evaluation and learning of the process, recommendations monitoring, and continuous feedback to participants. Several processes completely miss these steps. All these aspects show structural limitations in terms of scalability, accessibility, and efficiency.

Figure 8: AS-IS state in AAIT deliberative process. The diagram summarises the main critical aspect of the current deliberative processes, broken down by phase.

2.4.3. TO-BE state

In order to tackle the majority of the AS-IS challenges, the TO-BE analysis has enabled the identification of many areas for improvement in the implementation of a deliberative process, reflecting on the potential of AI and its scalability. So, the TO-BE state envisages the integration of AI tools across different phases of the deliberative process. AI does not replace human facilitation or decision-making, but acts as a support layer enhancing comprehension, accessibility, inclusivity, and efficiency.

In a TO-BE deliberative process, AI can address many of the structural challenges of traditional deliberation, while preserving human agency and control, ethical and accountability aspects. The use of AI should be organised across the three main phases of the process: pre-deliberation, during deliberation, and post-deliberation.

In the pre-deliberation phase, AI can assist organisers in designing agendas, identifying key themes, and preparing balanced briefing materials, while human oversight ensures ethical compliance. It can help in establishing common conduct rules. Other functionalities can support document summarisation, audio-video production, translation, and simplification into different formats, reducing cognitive overload and information asymmetry among participants. During the deliberation phase, AI can enhance inclusiveness and process quality, helping human moderation. AI can provide transcription, multilingual support, and structured note-taking/summaries; these elements can support equal participation and reduce domination by more vocal participants. AI can also support argument extraction, discussion flow highlighting key moments, and prioritisation. Also, the voting exercises (if needed) increase transparency and clarity in collective decision-making.

Figure 9: TO-BE state in AAIT deliberative process. The diagram summarises the AI-enabled features that should be implemented according to the three stages of deliberation.

In the post-deliberation phase, AI can assist in synthesising large volumes of qualitative input and drafting a structure oriented to the institutional level. Another support could be the evaluation and learning internal process for future iterations and quality improvement of the process. Finally, AI can also support the production of an advocacy strategy for the acceptance of recommendations and another one for the results dissemination to a wider public, helping to do so.

2.4.4. Pilot planning, activities and lessons learned

The first sprint is designed as an internal test and involves a limited number of AAIT staff (between 10 and 15 people). Participants cover a range of functional roles, including facilitators and simulated participants with specific roles. The process is designed in three meetings and is developed through some distinctive elements of a deliberative process (pre, deliberation and post), like information, discussion, decision, and evaluation. The testing, with the coordination between practitioners, technical partners and ethics and participation expertise, promotes the continuous reflection balanced by and between innovation, democratic and ethical principles.

This first technology configuration enables a testing environment in which tools, workflows, and facilitation practices can be assessed. The AI integration tools and functionalities envisioned are primarily ECHO (provided by project partner Dembrane) and Frankly, an open-source online video-based platform designed to facilitate dialogue and collaborative decision-making processes; the pilot involves testing based on the integration of these two solutions.

A set of preparatory activities is carried out to ensure compliance with ethical standards and project requirements. These include the identification and assessment of potential ethical risks and mitigation actions, the development of clear and accessible informed consent procedures, and the definition of data protection and privacy measures in line with GDPR regulations. Particular attention is paid to the responsible use of AI tools, transparency towards participants, and alignment with the ethical framework structured by the project.

The second sprint foresees the citizens' involvement in a small-scale deliberative process, simulating a citizens' panel. The deliberative process will consist of three meetings and will involve between 25 and 30 participants. This format is intentionally designed to test deliberative dynamics, facilitation practices, and AI-supported tools in a realistic yet manageable setting, providing valuable insights ahead of potential larger-scale implementations that will be tackled in the third sprint.

Some key challenges identified in the actual deliberative process include differences in digital literacy among participants, potential scepticism or mistrust towards AI-supported tools, and limited time available for in-depth deliberation. Mitigation strategies could be focused on clear and transparent communication about the role and limits of AI, meaningful facilitation, and the use of iterative feedback loops to adapt the process. Another essential factor is the accountability of the whole process: from the pre-deliberation to the post-deliberation, passing through AI explainability.

The evaluation of actual deliberative processes underline the needs to implement them taking into account the organizational, implementational and follow-up challenges integrated with AI ones. Among the various lessons learned, are worth mentioning:

- AI tools require careful framing and facilitation mechanisms for participants' acceptance. Clear communication about what AI functionalities help build trust in technology.
- AI support can enhance efficiency and quality structure, but it cannot completely replace the human role in managing the entire process, particularly group dynamics.
- Time should be realistic: participants' engagement needs time and effort; this has implications for agenda setting.
- Ethics and data protection require continuous attention and updating in line with technological developments.
- Deliberative processes do not end with results: subsequent follow-up phases are equally important for continuing to build trust in democratic values.

PENDING EC APPROVAL

3. Evaluation plan – methodology

3.1. Overall Evaluation strategy and dimensions

The evaluation strategy for the AI4Deliberation project follows an agile Research and Innovation approach designed to validate the project's technological and methodological outputs through iterative testing. This strategy considers five key aspects as follows.

Evaluation periods. The AI4Deliberation project is organised into three sprints, each building upon the previous one to progressively scale from internal infrastructure to large-scale citizen engagement. Each sprint concludes with a reporting deliverable:

1. **First sprint: Think big and prepare (M7-M15).** Generally, this period focuses on producing the basic artefacts to provide a socio-technical “infrastructure” for the rest of the work. In the frame of WP5, it includes the first pilot plan (T5.1) and implementation (T5.2). The evaluation is restricted to **consortium members only** (internal testing) to elicit initial lessons and validate feasibility. The results are reported in this deliverable, **D5.1 “Pilots plan, operation and evaluation - first sprint”**.
2. **Second sprint: Start small (M16-M21).** This period aims to produce all artifacts needed for small scale pilots. It includes the second pilot plan update (T5.3) and implementation (T5.4). The evaluation focus shifts to **small-scale pilots with a small number of citizens**. The results will be reported in deliverable **D5.2: “Pilots plan, operation and evaluation - second sprint”**.
3. **Third sprint: Scale fast (M22-M33).** This period aims to develop all essential artefacts to enable deploying, operating, and evaluating deliberations at scale. It includes the third pilot plan update (T5.5) and implementation (T5.6). The evaluation focuses on **large-scale deliberations with citizens**. The results will be reported in deliverable **D5.3: “Pilots plan, operation and evaluation - third sprint”**.

The current deliverable refers to the First sprint and specifically presents the evaluation plan and results for the initial internal infrastructure testing.

Project results. The evaluation scope for all sprints includes assessments of project outcomes deployed across the four pilot sites (Germany, Greece, International, Italy). Specifically, this includes:

- The **AI-enabled Deliberation Process Guidelines and Design Matrix** (WP2);
- The **Comprehensive Framework for Institutionalisation** (WP3), specifically the conditions and requirements;
- The **AI Toolkit** (WP4), covering tools like summarisation, argument extraction, moderation, and the ECHO platform;
- The models for **Acceptance, Trust, and Usability** (WP5).

Stakeholders. Different types of stakeholders are involved depending on the sprint phase:

- **Consortium Members (First Sprint):** The first sprint involved only consortium members (pilot partners and technical partners) acting as testers. This ensured that the socio-technical infrastructure is safe and functional before citizen contact.

- **Pilot Administrators (Second & Third Sprints):** In future sprints, the public servants and administrators responsible for managing the deliberation platforms will be actively involved in evaluating the tools.
- **Citizens (Second & Third Sprints):** Citizens will participate in small-scale pilots during the second sprint and large-scale deliberations during the third sprint, serving as the primary end-users for the acceptance and usability evaluations.
- **Scientific Ethics Advisory Board (SEAB) (Second & Third Sprints):** The SEAB will be actively involved in Sprints 2 and 3 to provide ethical oversight and evaluation support during these live phases.
- **External Experts (Second & Third Sprints):** Alongside the pilot activities, external experts will be engaged in the second and third sprints mainly to evaluate the **WP2 Process Guidelines**, the **WP3 Comprehensive Framework**, and the **WP5 Acceptance Model**, ensuring academic robustness and practical validity beyond the consortium.

Evaluation setting. Evaluations are performed in different settings tailored to the specific nature of the result being tested during this "mega-sprint":

- **Internal Simulations (Sprint 1):** To validate the AI toolkit and initial usability models, pilots utilised controlled environments to generate "ground truth" data. This included **role-play simulations** (German and Italian pilots) where staff acted as deliberators to test real-time tools, and **historical dataset analysis** (Greek and International pilots) to benchmark specific AI functionalities against known outcomes.
- **Live Pilot Operations (Sprints 2 & 3):** Future evaluations will shift from these controlled/internal settings to actual deliberative processes managed by pilot administrators, involving real citizen participants.
- **Structured Surveys & Expert Reviews (Focus on WP2 & WP3):** The methodological frameworks were evaluated through **digital questionnaires** and **structured surveys** distributed internally to consortium partners. Practitioners and experts from the pilot organisations reviewed the documentation (guidelines and conditions) and provided structured feedback on their clarity, feasibility, and completeness.

Evaluation dimensions. To comprehensively assess the project results listed above, this sprint applies four specific evaluation dimensions, which correspond to the subsequent sections of this chapter:

1. **Evaluation of AI-enabled Deliberation processes (WP2):** Assessing the comprehensibility, usability, and practical relevance of the upscaling guidelines and design matrix (Detailed in Section 3.2).
2. **Evaluation of comprehensive framework (WP3):** Assessing the feasibility, importance, and implementation potential of the institutional conditions and requirements (Detailed in Section 3.3).
3. **Evaluation of AI toolkit (WP4):** Assessing the output quality and functionality-specific performance of AI tools (Detailed in Section 3.4).

4. **Evaluation of acceptance, trust and usability (WP5):** Assessing the initial user acceptance and trust factors related to the introduction of AI in deliberative settings (Detailed in Section 3.5).

3.2. Evaluation methodology of AI-enabled Deliberation processes (WP2)

WP outcome to be evaluated: We evaluated the current interim version of the WP2 Process Guideline for designing scalable, gamified, AI-enabled, deliberative processes and the corresponding design Matrix. The focus was on whether the current Guideline and Matrix are clear and useful enough to help pilots design scalable deliberative processes.

Stakeholders involved in the evaluation: The evaluation aimed mainly at the project pilots (the main users of the guideline), and it was also open to colleagues from other work packages to get additional perspectives. We received 19 completed, trackable responses, with four pilots contributing 15 of them.

Evaluation method: We used a short structured survey (the full Survey is available in Appendix C) with Likert-style rating questions and open comment sections. The survey ran from 27 Nov to 12 Dec 2025, after the guideline was shared on 18 Nov 2025. To avoid one organisation having too much influence (e.g., if they submitted multiple responses), we combined responses at the organisational level and treated each organisation as one unit in the summary. We compared rating results to the midpoint of the Likert scale (3 = neutral) and used the open comments to explain the scores and identify concrete improvements. By combining aggregated quantitative assessments with a systematic qualitative analysis of open-ended comments, the report aims to provide a transparent and balanced assessment of the strengths and limitations of the first draft, as well as a clear justification for the revisions planned in the second draft.

This survey forms part of the evaluation activities of WP5 and aims to assess the comprehensibility and practical usability of the first draft of the upscaling process guideline and matrix developed by WP2.

The survey was intentionally designed to be lightweight and focused, concentrating on three core aspects:

1. The clarity and comprehensibility of the different components of the guidelines and matrix.
2. the perceived usefulness of the guidelines and matrix, particularly in relation to the pilots' capacity to translate them into actionable and context-specific implementations; and
3. The ability of the guidelines and matrix to support pilots in self-designing upscalable deliberative processes.

Accordingly, the questions directly targeted these dimensions. Each item also included an open-ended comment field, allowing respondents to provide qualitative feedback, suggestions, or clarifications, especially in cases where elements of the guidelines were perceived as unclear or ambiguous.

While the survey primarily targeted project pilots, it was also open to respondents from other work packages. This broader inclusion was intended to capture complementary perspectives and to assess the guidelines' intelligibility and relevance beyond the immediate pilot context.

The survey focused on the following criteria:

- Usefulness: Is it helpful in practice (can pilots apply it to their context)?
- Support for self-design: Does it help pilots design an upscaling process on their own?
- Clarity: Is the guideline/matrix easy to understand?
- Practical issues such as feasibility constraints and missing elements (e.g., requests for more examples, clearer templates, or concrete AI tool suggestions).

3.3. Evaluation methodology of the comprehensive framework (WP3)

WP outcome to be evaluated: Eventually, WP3 will provide a comprehensive framework that supports public organisations in institutionalising AI-enabled mass deliberation. In this first sprint, we identified and evaluated a preliminary list of conditions and requirements for institutionalising AI-enabled deliberation. Accordingly, these conditions and requirements form the basis for the comprehensive framework that is evaluated in Sprint 1.

Stakeholders involved in the evaluation: The evaluation of the conditions and requirements was performed by a small sample of practitioners working at partners of the consortium. Considering that practitioners of (digital) deliberation work at the pilot partners of the consortium, we focused on those partners. We asked the four pilots and Dembrane (considering that they are part of the AAIT pilot and because of their expertise in bringing AI-enabled deliberation to practice) to nominate employees of their organisations who work on institutionalising deliberative practices and/or digital technology in the context of public organisations.

Evaluation method: The overarching methodological approach of WP3 is design science, more specifically, Action Design Research [1]. This research approach focuses on creating artefacts in a specific organisational context in order to gather generalisable knowledge. Action Design Research consists of four stages: 1) problem formulation; 2) building, intervention, and evaluation; 3) reflection and learning; 4) formalisation of learning. The evaluation presented in this deliverable concludes the first iteration of the build, intervention, and evaluation stage of the comprehensive framework.

The evaluation aimed to explore whether the formulated conditions and requirements comprise a comprehensive set related to the institutionalisation of AI-enabled mass deliberation. Furthermore, it was used to test whether the predominantly theoretical conditions and requirements were considered feasible, important, easy to implement, and a contribution to institutionalisation by practitioners. This explorative evaluation will provide the basis for new iterations of WP3. In other words, the final list of conditions and requirements following from this evaluation is the starting point for the comprehensive framework developed in Sprints 2 and 3.

All participants completed a **questionnaire** in which they scored conditions and requirements on four criteria. This questionnaire presented each condition and requirement to the

participants. They could score the conditions and questionnaire on four criteria using a five-point Likert-scale.

The **criteria** were tested for two elements. First, the criteria ‘importance’ and ‘contribution to meaningful deliberation/sustainable integration’ evaluated the conceptual coverage of institutionalisation. Second, the criteria ‘feasibility’ and ‘ease of implementation’ evaluated the relation of each condition or requirement to practice. We defined the four criteria as follows:

- *Feasibility*: The extent to which the condition/requirement itself can be achieved by public organisations.
- *Importance*: The extent to which the condition/requirement is important for achieving institutionalisation of AI-enabled mass deliberation.
- *Easiness of implementation*: The extent to which public organisations will be able to translate the condition/requirement into their daily practice.
- *Contribution to the related subgoal*: The extent to which the condition/requirement contributes to the subgoal (meaningful deliberation or sustainable integration).

Participants filled out Excel sheets (see **Appendix D**). For each condition or requirement, they assessed the four criteria using a Likert scale 1-5 (1. Strongly disagree, 2. Disagree, 3. Neutral, 4. Agree, 5. Strongly agree)

In addition, we asked four open questions to participants. The four open questions encouraged reflection on the full set of conditions and requirements. Furthermore, the qualitative nature of the answer to the questions enabled us to interpret the scores given to the criteria. The four open questions were as follows:

1. *Do the two subgoals (sustainable integration and meaningful deliberation) cover everything that is needed in your understanding of institutionalisation? Why?*
2. *To what extent are the two subgoals complementary OR contradictory? What contradictions do you see in the full set of conditions and requirements? What can be done about these contradictions?*
3. *To what extent does the full set of conditions and requirements reflect all necessary elements within the subgoals? Why?*
4. *Do you have any remarks, comments, additions, or improvements regarding the conditions and requirements?*

3.4. Evaluation methodology of AI toolkit (WP4)

WP outcome to be evaluated: The focus of the evaluation was an initial, structured appraisal of the results and functionalities of the AI tools selected under WP4 for supporting deliberative processes. Across pilots, the assessment *targeted* core functionalities such as summarisation, LLM-based argument extraction and content moderation (more information about the evaluated tools is provided in Section 4.3.1). In addition, some pilots also assessed adjacent components that are operationally relevant for using the toolkit in practice—most notably moderation/civility detection, transcript-grounded interaction (e.g., “ask/chat with transcript”), and language/translation-related robustness checks. The purpose of this first

round was not to validate full operational integration, but to obtain an evidence-based first view on output quality, usefulness, and fitness-for-purpose under different pilot conditions and datasets, and to identify priority gaps to address in the next sprint.

Stakeholders involved in the evaluation: In the first evaluation phase, the assessment of the WP4 AI toolkit was conducted as an internal process. Each pilot team led the evaluation within its own organisational context and, where useful, invited colleagues and/or external experts with experience in deliberation and facilitation to review the outputs. Technical partners in WP4 supported the process by preparing the datasets, running the selected tools, and providing the outputs to be assessed, alongside short explanations of the tools and their expected behaviour.

Evaluation method: The evaluation was conducted using a standardised **questionnaire-based assessment** applied to each tool output. A key design principle was granularity: the pilots completed one questionnaire per tool result. If a given tool had different variations (e.g., different LLMs used for the summarisation), each variation was assessed separately to enable comparison between configurations or approaches. In addition to structured ratings, pilots provided qualitative comments focusing on strengths, weaknesses, missing elements, and practical usability in deliberative settings. To support consistent interpretation, technical partners presented each tool/functionality using a common template including: tool name, description, functionality overview, input example, output example (assessed result), limitations/considerations, and expected result behaviour. Additionally, for some tools, including moderation, translation and summarisation, partners used **automated evaluations based on: i) existing annotated data or ii) LLM-as-a-judge approaches**.

Regarding the questionnaire based assessment each output was evaluated against (i) general quality criteria and (ii) functionality-specific criteria, using a 1–5 Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree; 5 = strongly agree), complemented by optional open comments. The questionnaire used for the evaluations is the following:

A. Quality of the Output (1–5 Likert scale)

1= Strongly disagree, 5= Strongly agree

1. The output is **coherent** (easy to read, logically structured).
2. The output is **complete** (captures the main ideas).
3. The output is **accurate** (faithfully reflects what participants said).
4. The output is **factually correct** (no incorrect or invented claims).
5. The output is **useful** for understanding the deliberation.

B. Functionality-Specific (1–5 Likert scale)

6. The output reflects the **purpose** of the tool/functionality.
7. The output aligns with the **expected behaviour** described in the guidelines.
8. The purpose of this tool was clear to me.
9. This tool would be useful in real-world deliberation scenarios.

C. Optional Open Comments

Any additional feedback: strengths, weaknesses, errors, missing points, inconsistencies, etc.

The methodology used for the automated evaluations per tool is described below:

- **Summarisation:** LLM-as-a-judge approach. We evaluated results using DeepEval¹ that is an evaluation framework for AI systems that provides several metrics for the quality of model-generated outputs. It supports a wide range of metrics that are able to capture different dimensions of performance, including coherence, correctness, completeness, factual consistency, and contextual relevance. DeepEval uses techniques like automatic question generation, inference comparison with the original content, and the use of LLMs as evaluators in a way that emulates how a human would evaluate the quality of a response. DeepEval also includes a summarisation metric that works by generating questions over the original content (in our case, comments) and then checking whether the answers to these questions appear in the model-generated summary. Following on this, DeepEval does provide a method by which summaries can be appraised even without ground-truth.
- **Moderation:** We used an annotated dataset and compared the results produced by the tool with the ground truth to calculate Precision, Recall and F1 scores.
- **Translation:** We used an annotated dataset and compared the translations produced by the tool with the ground truth. The generated translations were evaluated by calculating the average scores of ROUGE (ROUGE-1, ROUGE-2, and ROUGE-L), METEOR, and BERTScore (Precision, Recall, and F1). ROUGE measures lexical overlap and content coverage between the generated and reference texts, METEOR assesses translation quality through exact, stem, and synonym matches while accounting for word order, and BERTScore captures semantic similarity using contextual embeddings, providing a complementary evaluation of both syntactic and semantic translation quality.

3.5. Evaluation of acceptance, trust and usability (WP5)

In the frame of AI4Deliberation, we aim to develop and validate a citizen acceptance and trust model for Artificial Intelligence (AI)-enabled deliberation platforms by combining Scale Development Theory [2] with Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) approaches [3]. The workflow follows established guidance for rigorous construct measurement (item generation to expert content validation to empirical validation) and then tests a theory-driven structural model using SEM.

The methodology is organised into three sprints. In the first sprint, we define the constructs, generate items, select the response format, and conduct two rounds of expert review. In the second sprint, we will test the first version of the model with a small citizen sample to refine items, assess dimensionality, and produce an initial measurement and structural model. In the third sprint, we will administer the refined instrument to a larger sample to confirm the measurement model, validate the structural model, and finalise hypotheses/paths.

¹ <https://deepeval.com/>

More specifically, we will complete the next steps.

Sprint 1

Step 1. Define what we will measure. In this step, we will define the scope of what the study intends to measure. This includes specifying what acceptance and trust mean in this study, what the study intends to capture, and how the key concepts should be bounded. This step will lay the groundwork in order for the next steps to proceed with consistency.

Step 2. Literature review. In this step, we will conduct two different systematic literature reviews following the PRISMA statement methodology [4]. One literature review will focus on citizens' acceptance and trust in digital participation and deliberation systems (even when AI does not exist), while the second will focus on AI acceptance and trust in general. This step will provide us with a set of candidate constructs, definitions, and relevant items that can be used in the next steps of this methodology.

Step 3. Create an initial group of objects (candidate constructs and items). In this step, using the findings of the two literature reviews, we will create a list of constructs relevant to acceptance and trust in our context and an initial repository of candidate items, adapted to reflect AI-enabled deliberation features.

Step 4. Determine the measurement format. In this step, we will determine the response format and measurement conventions for the instrument and establish the rules for writing the items.

Step 5. Review of the original group of constructs and items by experts. To ensure the validity of the proposed scale for assessing AI-enabled deliberation systems, we will conduct two survey rounds following guidance from experts. The survey approach is selected because it enables structured, anonymous, and iterative input from a heterogeneous expert panel. This reduces dominance bias and promotes convergence of opinion. Regarding the analysis of their input, we will use formulas like Content Validity Indices (Yusoff, 2019), such as item-level content validity index (I-CVI), scale-level content validity index based on the average (S-CVI/Ave), method, Content Validity Ratios (CVR) [6], etc., to quantify agreement and validation [7] and produce the final set of selected items. The following sub-steps provide a detailed description of the approach we employed.

Step 5.1. Experts Selection. In this step, we will select a group of 8-12 experts across domains such as AI governance scholars, deliberative democracy academics, and deliberation practitioners. These experts are part of the consortium of the project.

Step 5.2 Construct level validation and parsimony (Round 1). In this sub-step, we will collect experts' quantitative ratings and qualitative comments through a survey and a focus group to validate the construct domain. More specifically, we will identify which constructs are most relevant and essential for modelling acceptance and trust in our context, evaluate whether the construct definitions are clear and conceptually sound, detect overlaps or redundancies between the constructs, and identify any missing constructs based on expert knowledge. The results of this sub-step will be used to refine construct definitions, merge or remove overlapping constructs, and ensure that the construct domain is complete before moving to item generation.

Step 5.3 Construct, Facet, and Item refinement. In this sub-step, based on the feedback from the round 1 expert validation, we will revise the construct inventory

and the measurement content needed for item-level evaluation. In cases where the constructs are multifaceted, we specify their facets or dimensions and ensure each construct and its facets are represented by a set of candidate items.

Step 5.4 Facet and item content validation (Round 2). In this sub-step, we will evaluate the quality of the facets and items before citizen deployment. Experts will rate how well each facet belongs as a component of the overall construct, how well each item measures its intended target (either a specific facet or the overall construct), and how clear each item is for citizens in terms of being understandable and unambiguous.

Sprint 2

Step 6. Consider including validation items. In this step, based on experts' evaluations, items with low measurement fit, poor clarity, or strong redundancy are revised, and facet structures are simplified in cases where experts do not support their distinctiveness. Furthermore, additional measures to support validity (e.g., new items), as well as basic response quality checks (e.g., attention checks), will be considered for addition.

Step 7. Manage items in a deployment sample. In this step, we will organise the expert-reviewed items into a single tank, prepare the measurement instrument, and run the first deployment with a small sample of citizens. This first deployment will provide empirical evidence to inform the transition from expert validation to citizen validated instrument.

Sprint 3

Step 8. Evaluate the items and develop the first empirical measurement model: In this step, we will use the data from the previous step's deployment to evaluate item quality, dimensionality, and behaviour in relation to their constructs. Revision or removal of items will be considered based on the evaluation results.

Step 9. Optimise the scale size. In this step, we will optimise the length of the scale, balancing brevity with reliability and content coverage. We will ensure that each construct and its facets (where they exist) are adequately represented. This step will produce a first empirically grounded version of the measurement model.

Step 10. Test the acceptance and trust model. In this step, we will administer the optimised scale to a larger sample of citizens to validate the measurement model and test the structural acceptance and trust model using SEM.

Step 11. Refine and finalise the model. In this step, the acceptance and trust model will be refined and finalised based on evidence from the large-sample SEM analysis. We will remove unsupported hypotheses and make any necessary modifications based on both theory and statistical diagnostics. The final output of this step is a validated measurement instrument and a validated structural model that, together, provide a robust basis for measuring citizens' acceptance and trust of AI-enabled deliberation platforms.

Regarding usability, we aim to develop a methodology in order to evaluate the usability of the AI-enabled deliberation platform. To ensure a comprehensive understanding of usability strengths and issues, we will combine methodologies identified in D1.1, such as:

- Inspection usability methodologies (expert-based), primarily heuristic evaluation (Nielsen & Molich, 1990) extended to include AI-specific heuristics (Langevin et al., 2021).
- Empirical usability methodologies (user-based), including think-aloud protocols (McDonald et al., 2012) and standardised usability questionnaires, like SUS (Brooke, 1996) and SUPR-Q.
- The proposed approach tries to identify early-stage, cost-effective interface problems by using inspection methods and real user behaviour and user experience using empirical methods.

PENDING EC APPROVAL

4. Evaluation results

This section presents the evaluation results per project outcome based on the methodology presented in Section 3.

4.1. Evaluation results for AI-enabled Deliberation processes (WP2)

4.1.1. Quantitative evaluation

The survey was open between 27 November and 12 December 2025, after the guidelines were distributed on 18 November 2025. A total of 19 responses were obtained, considering all the completed and trackable responses. Figure 10 displays responses by organisation.

Figure 10: Descriptive respondents

Four pilots, who constituted the primary target group of the survey, accounted for a total of 15 responses. Responses were averaged at the organisational level to derive a single aggregated assessment per organisation and to limit the influence of extreme or unrepresentative values. This aggregation strategy also helps mitigate potential bias arising from uneven response patterns or multiple responses from the same person.

To ensure transparency, all non-aggregated responses are reported in Appendix E.

In general, the guidelines and the matrix were perceived positively by all the organisations (Figure 11), displaying a certain degree of clarity.

Figure 11: Questions-respondents' matrix averages

On average, the guidelines and matrix were perceived positively, with all scores exceeding the neutral threshold of 3. Particularly high levels of comprehensibility were observed for the pre-deliberation stage and the scaling mechanisms, both receiving an average score of 4.28 out of 5. Lower, though still positive, scores were reported for the perceived usefulness of the matrix (3.53/5) and the clarity of the socio-technical challenges (3.66/5).

When examined at the respondent level (Figure 12), the results indicate a generally strong level of comprehensibility across all organisations.

Figure 12: Respondents-organisation overall average

Overall, comprehensibility assessments are positive across all pilots, with limited variability in responses. The only neutral assessment was provided by GFOSS, reflecting the specific institutional and legal constraints of the Greek pilot context (Figure 13).

As shown in Figure 4, GFOSS expressed particularly critical views regarding the actionability of deliberative principles, the clarity of guidance across process stages, the usefulness of the design matrix, and the self-perceived capacity to design a deliberative process based on the guideline. Additional critical feedback was also provided by IK, specifically concerning the clarity of socio-technical risks.

Figure 13: Box-plot outlier per question

All the other values are above the neutral line, with the majority of responses falling within the satisfaction zone.

4.1.2. Qualitative evaluation

To further explore the critiques and suggestions raised, we present a summary of the qualitative comments provided by respondents in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Summary of the suggestions-critical points

Organisation	Main focus of comment	Substantive critique (what is really at stake)
ActionAid	Scaling mechanisms, Matrix	Scaling mechanisms insufficiently specified; matrix too abstract. Request for pre-filled matrices and concrete AI tool examples.
	Core principles	Conceptual ambiguity between <i>Inclusivity</i> and <i>Plurality</i> ; missing multi-level governance dimension in scaling.
	Implementation support	Need for stronger guidance on participant selection, information provision, gamification, and facilitation roles.

	Missing elements	Lack of concrete AI tools and applied examples; checklist too focused on deliberation quality, not large-scale multimodal design.
GFOSS	Scaling by division	Structural incompatibility between guideline assumptions and legal–institutional constraints of the Greek pilot.
	Implementation feasibility	Small-group deliberation infeasible under legal framework; human facilitation required but not legally/operationally supported.
	Deliberation conditions	Asynchronous, anonymous platform undermines trust, synchrony, and consequentiality; deliberation is not institutionally guaranteed.
Smart City Bamberg	Structure & readability	Formatting and structure hinder comprehension (missing table of contents, headings, and numbering).
	Language	Language is perceived as too complex and not practitioner-friendly.
UBAM	Core principles	Full understanding requires prior deliberative expertise, a mismatch with practitioners from traditional participation backgrounds.
	Socio-technical challenges	Missing human cues in AI-supported processes.
Delft	Core principles	Inconsistency: Meta-consensus is framed as a core principle but treated as a sub-principle elsewhere.
	Implementation support	Insufficient emphasis on multimodality and gamification.
	Mitigation strategies	Mitigation strategies are seen as overly optimistic and insufficiently grounded; unclear terminology.
TG	Socio-technical challenges	Resource constraints and limited treatment of consequentiality.
	Implementation support	Guide perceived as overly theoretical; need for practitioner-oriented synthesis and cross-group integration.
	Missing elements	Need for vivid examples and a visual abstract.
CBAM	Implementation support	Preference for ready-to-use templates.
	Missing elements	Need for more concrete examples.

Qualitative feedback highlighted a limited number of recurring issues that cut across organisations and questions. These issues do not challenge the overall direction or ambition of the guideline, but rather concern its format, level of operational detail, and fit with diverse institutional contexts. We group these issues into three main categories, which are outlined in detail below.

4.2. Evaluation results for comprehensive framework (WP3)

This section discusses the evaluation results of WP3. First, Section 4.2.1 presents briefly the WP3 outcome that was evaluated. Section 4.2.2 presents the quantitative results of the assessment of individual conditions and requirements. Thereafter, Section 4.2.3 discusses qualitative results based on the four open-ended questions.

4.2.1. WP3 evaluated outcome: Conditions and requirements for institutionalising AI-enabled deliberation

The AI4Deliberation project aims to provide public organisations with a toolkit and process design that enables them to scale up their deliberative practices using AI applications. The scientific literature suggests that a focus on technology and process is insufficient to ensure a long-term uptake of digital participation or digital deliberation [8]. Over the last two decades, numerous digital platforms for public participation and deliberation have been initiated and adopted; however, these initiatives tend to be phased out relatively quickly after implementation or are overly dependent on the efforts of a small group of enthusiasts instead of being widely supported by all involved actors [8], [9], [10], [11]. In these cases, digital deliberation or digital participation failed to become a main activity or integral part of the work practices of public organisations.

Therefore, the AI4Deliberation project also studies the needs of public organisations related to *institutionalising* AI-enabled mass deliberation. Institutionalisation means that AI-enabled mass deliberation becomes a sustainable integrated activity in policy- and decision-making in such a way that it is meaningful to participating deliberators cf. [10]. This definition of institutionalising encompasses two subgoals that are elaborated on in this subsection: sustainable integration and meaningful deliberation. The conditions and requirements will follow from these two subgoals.

We define *sustainable integration* as AI-enabled mass deliberation that has become a routine or standard activity in the daily practice of a public organisation. In that case, mass deliberation has passed the pilot phase and is no longer dependent on specific individuals organising the deliberation. To sustainably integrate AI-enabled mass deliberation, public organisations should:

1. cultivate long-term support by all actors involved in or affected by mass deliberation [12], [13],
2. Situate AI-enabled mass deliberation in their existing organisational practices [14], and
3. continuously respond to changing deliberative practices and AI applications through adaptive governance [15], [16].

Sustainable integration of AI-enabled mass deliberation does not mean that the goals behind deliberative democracy are achieved. The deliberation also must be meaningful to citizens who participate in the process.

We consider *meaningful deliberation* to be achieved when deliberators (citizens participating in the deliberation) influence actual decision-making within the public organisations. To achieve this, deliberators should have equal positions in the deliberative process, and the

deliberative output should be of enough quality to be useful to policymakers. More generally, meaningful deliberation requires that:

1. (deliberative) democratic values are fostered [17], [18], [19], [20], and
2. that the effectiveness of mass deliberation is guaranteed [21].

The extent of influence on decision-making by deliberation is difficult to measure and achieve. When do deliberators have real influence? And what influence can be granted to deliberators? This is mainly dependent on the context in which AI-enabled mass deliberation is deployed. For example, the digital deliberative practice might need to be embedded in a representative democratic context.

For both subgoals, we formulated conditions and requirements that public organisations can or should follow to institutionalise AI-enabled mass deliberations. **Conditions** are elements that must be guaranteed in order to achieve institutionalisation. Conditions can be considered a *need-to-have*. **Requirements** are elements that can be pursued increase the likelihood of institutionalisation. Requirements can be considered a *nice-to-have*.

Deliverable 3.1 will contain a full description of how we arrived at the 22 conditions and 16 requirements below. In short, we performed two literature reviews (one systematic review presented in Deliverable 1.1 and one narrative review that expanded on gaps in the systematic review). Moreover, we performed five co-creation sessions. Three co-creation sessions were performed with partners of the consortium. The other two sessions were done with experts outside the consortium.

Meaningful deliberation

Meaningful deliberation consists of two elements. *Table 2* presents the conditions and requirements following from the need to foster (deliberative) democratic values. This aspect of meaningful deliberation guarantees that deliberation is not only instrumental but also has a normative basis.

Table 2. Conditions and requirements related to fostering democratic values (meaningful deliberation)

Conditions	Requirements
Ensure accessibility of mass deliberation for all possible deliberators	Put deliberators in the lead of organising the mass deliberation
Enlarge the capacities of deliberators to engage in mass deliberation	Respond to concerns regarding AI among potential deliberators
Guarantee influence on official decision-making	Guarantee meaningful human control over AI by involved and affected actors
Ensure transparency about the use of AI in mass deliberation	Guarantee the traceability of deliberative output's influence on official decision-making
Develop AI and digital literacy among deliberators	

Table 3 presents the conditions and requirements following from the need to guarantee the effectiveness of mass deliberation. Effectiveness or efficacy is related to the substantive

element in deliberation. From the perspective of a public organisation, the output of deliberation should be useful, understandable, and actionable for decision-makers who, in the end, have to translate deliberative output into policies.

Table 3. Conditions and requirements related to guaranteeing the effectiveness of mass deliberation (meaningful deliberation)

Conditions	Requirements
Establish a structured deliberative process that allows for mass deliberation	Measure deliberative quality by monitoring discussions
Balance the added value of AI applications with its costs	Allow for updating the deliberative output
Address safety problems caused by AI (such as manipulation, hallucination, and bias) that undermine deliberative quality	

Sustainable integration

Sustainable integration comprises three elements. **Table 4** shows the conditions and requirements that follow from the need to practice adaptive governance. Adaptive governance as an approach provides public organisations with the agility to respond to changes in mass deliberative practices. Especially the volatility of innovations in Gen AI applications urges public organisations to be flexible on the technological side of mass deliberation. At the same time, the political, institutional, and cultural context of mass deliberation changes continuously. The AI-enabled deliberation practices should be adapted to that context.

Table 4. Conditions and requirements related to practising adaptive governance (sustainable integration)

Conditions	Requirements
Design both the technological and governance parts of AI-enabled mass deliberation concurrently	Take time to organise AI-enabled mass deliberation
Establish spaces for (mutual) learning about AI-enabled mass deliberation	Formulate a vision on AI-enabled mass deliberation
React to changing interests and needs among involved and affected actors in AI-enabled mass deliberation	Map the risks of using AI in mass deliberation
React to continuous developments and innovations in technology, especially AI	Enlarge the capacity of public organisations to intervene in deliberative practice
	Encourage monitoring changes in deliberative practices

Table 5 presents the conditions and requirements that follow from the need to cultivate long-term support. Ensuring long-term support is needed to prevent AI-enabled mass deliberation from stopping after the pilot phase

Table 5. Conditions and requirements related to cultivating long-term support (sustainable integration)

Conditions	Requirements
Demonstrate commitment as public organisation to AI-enabled mass deliberation	Dedicate organisational capacity for AI-enabled mass deliberation
Confer legitimacy to the AI-enabled mass deliberative practice	Identify possible tensions between stakeholders
Adopt a deliberative stance/attitude within the public organisation	
Establish political will to engage in AI-enabled mass deliberation	
Guarantee the needed resources to enact AI-enabled mass deliberation	

Table 6 shows the conditions and requirements derived from the need to situate AI-enabled mass deliberation in existing organizational practices. Organisational practices provide stability to the behaviour of public organisations and, therefore, ensures trust, predictability and efficiency. At the same time, such stable practices are hard to change. Mostly, adaptations of practices will take a long time. A smooth integration of AI-enabled mass deliberation is more likely to be successful when it is fitted to already existing practices. From there, through adaptive governance, existing organisational practices can be adapted to better fit innovations in deliberative practices.

Table 6. Conditions and requirements related to situating AI-enabled mass deliberation in existing organizational practices

Conditions	Requirements
Situate mass deliberative practices in official decision-making processes	Combine AI-enabled mass deliberation with classic (mini public) deliberation
Issue a formal mandate for deliberative practices	Relate AI-enabled deliberative practice to representative democratic practices (if applicable)
Respect the Rule of Law within the deliberative practice	Limit dependency on third parties
Establish data and AI governance	
Embed the AI applications in a broader technical infrastructure	

4.2.2. Quantitative evaluation

Participant of the WP3 questionnaire: The target number of participants for each pilot was four. In the end, the numbers of participants per pilot were as follows:

- Italian pilot: 6
- Greek pilot: 4

- German pilot: 3 (More evaluations performed by public servants of the city are expected after this deliverable is submitted and will be included in the analysis presented in Deliverable 3.1)
- International pilot: 2

Results: The conditions and requirements formulated in WP3 were assessed by practitioners using Likert-scales scores. Considering the small sample of practitioners, we will focus the discussion of results on a descriptive analysis of the scores. This means that we focus on frequencies of scores and the medians of these scores. The frequencies and medians per criteria for each condition and requirement can be found in the appendix.

In general, the evaluation shows a difference between the assessment of the criteria that evaluate the conceptual coverage of institutionalisation and the assessment of the criteria related to the translation to practice. The conceptual coverage criteria score higher compared (medians per condition or requirement are 4 or 5) to the practice-related criteria (medians per condition or requirement vary between 2, 3, 4, and 5). This suggests that participants observe a gap between theory and practice.

Regarding the conceptual coverage criteria, we observe high scores of the two criteria. Almost all conditions and requirements were scored with a median of 4 or 5 on 'importance'. The only requirement with a median of 3 on 'importance' is *put deliberators in the lead of organising the mass deliberation*. Looking at the frequencies of scores for this requirement, we observe a greater variety among participants compared to the scores of other conditions and requirements. The low median of this requirement compared to the rest is remarkable considering that self-governance is a key fundament of deliberative democracy.

The scores of the criterion 'contribution to the related subgoal' are similar to those of 'importance'. Again, almost all the medians of conditions and requirements on this criterion are 4 or 5. One condition has a median of 3: *embed the AI applications in a broader technical infrastructure*. Also, for this condition, we observe more variety in scores given by participants compared to the rest.

Following the descriptive analysis of the conditions and requirements on 'importance' and 'contribution to the related subgoal', we will not discard any condition or requirement from the full set. Considering the relatively high scores given by participants, we argue that all conditions and requirements contribute to a comprehensive understanding of institutionalising AI-enabled mass deliberation.

The scores of the practice-related criteria show much more variety. The medians of the 'feasibility' of conditions and requirements varies between 2 and 5. Most conditions and requirements have a median of 3 – a neutral assessment. These conditions and requirements need more attention when translated into practices. One requirement has a median of 2 on 'feasibility': *put deliberators in the lead of organising the mass deliberation*. Participants consider it the most difficult element of institutionalising AI-enabled mass deliberation to achieve.

Regarding 'easiness of implementation', participants seem to be more pessimistic. Again, most conditions and requirements have a median of 3. However, eight conditions and requirements have a median of 2. These are the following:

- *Enlarge the capacities of deliberators to engage in mass deliberation (condition)*

- *Guarantee influence on official decision-making (condition)*
- *Put deliberators in the lead of organising the mass deliberation (requirement)*
- *React to continuous development and innovations in technology, especially AI (condition)*
- *Adopt a deliberative stance/attitude within the public organisation (condition)*
- *Establish political will to engage in AI-enabled mass deliberation (condition)*
- *Guarantee the needed resources to enact AI-enabled mass deliberation (condition)*
- *Dedicate organisational capacity for AI-enabled mass deliberation (requirement)*

The low medians for these conditions and requirements suggest that participants have low confidence in public organisations being open to meaningful and integrated deliberation. They think it is difficult to guarantee the influence of deliberators, that political will is hard to encourage, and that public organisations will not provide the needed resources.

4.2.3. Qualitative evaluation

For the Qualitative evaluation, we used the same questionnaire (and the same participants) as to the quantitative evaluation.

This section presents and reflects on the answers given to the four open questions by participants. Before moving to the respective questions, we discuss some general reflections based on participants' answers. First, the answers seem to suggest that the scope of institutionalisation should be broadened. Participants provided many additions and identified many gaps in the current understanding of institutionalisation. On the other hand, their remarks often are about process or technological elements which are covered in the guidelines of WP2 and the toolkit of WP4. It seems hard for evaluators to distinguish the focus of the different work packages in the separate deliverables.

In addition, we asked participants to evaluate a set of conditions and requirements. Nevertheless, several participants provided suggestions in the form of (institutional) interventions. As such, they already moved towards the 'how' concerning institutionalisation, while the conditions and requirements are focused on the 'what'. This section will refrain from discussing solutions mentioned by participants, as the conditions and requirements are meant to be agnostic to how they will be realised.

1) Do the two subgoals (sustainable integration and meaningful deliberation) cover everything that is needed in your understanding of institutionalisation? Why?

Five participants stated that the subgoals cover everything related to the institutionalisation of AI-enabled mass deliberation. Contrarily, one person answered the question with no. This participant argued that the subgoals are 'not truly analytically discrete' (other participants also indicated the interrelatedness of the subgoals but did not consider that to be a problem to coverage). In addition, the participant considered the subgoals (and the related conditions and requirements) to be too much focused on the fact that deliberation takes place in or is organised by a single organisation. Other participants have also pointed out the lack of acknowledging the network setting in which deliberation takes place. For example, they point out that the full set of conditions and requirements does not cover the multi-level nature of governing deliberative processes.

The majority of the 15 participants reported that the two subgoals do mostly cover institutionalisation, but have provided remarks. Partly, these remarks are about missing

elements on the level of conditions and requirements (and, therefore, are not necessarily about the coverage of the subgoals). We will discuss these missing elements under question 3. Here, we focus on the comprehensiveness of the subgoals. In other words, we reflect on the understanding of institutionalisation conveyed in the subgoals. Participants provided the following general remarks.

First, as mentioned earlier, participants indicated that the interrelation between the subgoals needs to be emphasised more. One participant stated: ‘What the framework leaves implicit is that these aren't parallel goals but coupled dynamics. They form a single feedback system: meaningful participation generates legitimacy, legitimacy justifies institutional investment, investment enables responsiveness, and responsiveness maintains meaning. When this loop is intact, both subgoals reinforce each other. When it breaks - when input is gathered but not acted upon - both erode together, often producing stakeholder fragmentation as groups form competing structures to meet needs the institution no longer serves.’ The interrelatedness of the subgoals confirms that both are needed to achieve institutionalisation of AI-enabled mass deliberation.

Second, participants remarked on the lack of specificity about or emphasis on *mass* deliberation in the subgoals. This omission might result in a comprehensive framework on institutionalisation that is not specific to AI-enabled mass deliberation but comprises all types of democratic deliberation. Following the aims of the AI4Deliberation project, the conditions and requirements should be specific to AI-enabled mass deliberation. One participant argued that the *mass* characteristic of deliberation considered in the project needs a separate set of conditions and requirements and, therefore, its own subgoal.

Third, participants felt that the two subgoals should emphasise power imbalances and the need for citizen empowerment more. Where some participants literally mentioned the power imbalances, other participants suggested missing elements in the subgoals that can be related to power imbalances and citizen empowerment. The missing elements identified by participants indicate a lack of attention to accountability and oversight mechanisms, transparency guarantees, and protection against capture (by well-resourced interests).

Fourth, participants tend to interpret institutionalisation (as presented in the subgoals and full set of conditions and requirements) as a process that is to be realised through formal institutions. This surfaces in their answers to all four open questions. Participants often indicated that elements related to culture or informal interactions between actors are missing in the understanding of institutionalisation presented to them. For example, several participants mentioned the need for cultural change in public organisations to address the scepticism often observed among public servants. Although the subgoals, conditions, and requirements were formulated as being agnostic to formal or informal institutions, the remarks by participants indicate that the need for both types of institutions in the comprehensive framework must be made clearer.

In conclusion, the two subgoals seem to cover most elements of institutionalising democratic deliberation. At the same time, the subgoals need to be specified to the situation of AI-enabled mass deliberation and the power imbalances in this type of deliberation. This can be done by either adding an extra subgoal or adapting the two subgoals. In changing the subgoals, the interrelation between them needs to be preserved.

2) To what extent are the two subgoals complementary OR contradictory? What contradictions do you see in the full set of conditions and requirements? What can be done to these contradictions?

Four participants stated that the subgoals are fully complementary. Their answers come down to the general conclusion of question 1: the subgoals reinforce one another. The other participants also confirmed the complementarity between the subgoals, but also indicated possible tensions between the two subgoals. They expect tensions between the subgoals when the related conditions and requirements are put into practice. This gap between theory and practice is also reflected in the lower scores on 'feasibility' and 'easiness of implementation' for all conditions and requirements. One participant argued that these tensions do not necessarily have to be a problem but can also be productive. Interestingly, some participants argued that the full set of conditions and requirements is too detailed and even redundant, whereas others provided lists of recommendations to further detail the full set. The recommendations provided by participants will be discussed under question 4. Here, we will discuss two main tensions identified in the evaluation.

The first main tension comes down to a well-known tension between stability and change. Several participants felt that sustainable integration requires formal and more rigid procedures, while meaningful deliberation asks for flexibility and adaptation. As one participant stated: 'several conditions under "sustainable integration" emphasise embedding deliberation in existing processes and formal mandates, while "meaningful deliberation" requires responsiveness to participants. If existing processes are rigid, these can conflict. The adaptive governance conditions address this, but implementers may find the balance difficult in practice.' Another participant argued that to achieve meaningful deliberation demands 'resource-intensive and complex designs', while attaining sustainable integration 'requires easiness, agility, cost-efficiency, and long-term management.' These tensions are considered to be the main barrier to bringing institutionalisation to practice, since the simultaneous implementation of the subgoals brings trade-offs between speed and quality, between control and autonomy, and between standardisation and responsiveness.

The second main tension revolves around participants' doubts over genuine interest among public organisation in real and meaningful deliberation. Considering that the institutionalisation of deliberation heavily depends on public organisations (see the power imbalance discussed under question 1), this lack of interest can be a problem. In many cases, it is the public organisations that have to pay for deliberative processes and they have to incorporate the processes in their official decision-making procedures. Participants argued that public organisations tend to have reservations towards the pressure that follows from deliberative outputs. The disinterest of a public organisation is not necessarily intentional. One participant stated that 'high standards [regarding mass deliberation] clash with limited organisational capacity, fragmented responsibilities and mismatches of competences between levels of government.' Another participant argued that a deliberative attitude is contrary to the current administrative culture within public organisations.

Apart from the two main tensions, participants mentioned more detailed tensions. Here, we list examples of tensions on the condition and requirement level:

- Put deliberators in the lead of organising the mass deliberation vs. issue a formal mandate for deliberative practices

- React to continuous developments and innovations in technology, especially AI vs. embed the AI applications in a broader technical infrastructure
- Limit dependency on third parties vs. embed the AI applications in a broader technical infrastructure
- Limit dependency on third parties vs. guarantee the needed resources to enact AI-enabled mass deliberation
- Balance the added value of AI application with its costs vs. guarantee the needed resources to enact AI-enabled mass deliberation

Most answers by participants focused on tensions that are expected to emerge when the subgoals are to be achieved in practice. Interestingly, one participant argued that the subgoals are also theoretically contradictory: ‘they inhabit a fundamental tension relating to deeper conflicts between institutional and citizen interests.’ The theoretical contradictions are somewhat similar to the tensions named by other participants. They revolve around conflicts between institutional logics and citizen power, between efficiency and inclusion, and between formal compliance and substantive engagement.

The answers to question 2 show that it will be a challenge to realise the conditions and requirements in practice. The tensions between the conditions and requirements will emerge in efforts to put them into practice. The tensions mentioned by participants mainly seem to be related to the current ways of working in public organisations. The insights from question 2 emphasise the importance of, apart from structuring deliberative practices in line with existing practices, that sedimented ways of working in public organisations also need to be adapted.

3) To what extent does the full set of conditions and requirements reflect all necessary elements within the subgoals? Why?

Participants have commented on both the substance and the nature of the conditions and requirements. Before discussing the comments on substance, we discuss the insights related to the nature of conditions and requirements. One participant argued that the ‘distinction between condition and requirement feels rather forced/arbitrary or unnecessarily subtle.’ Another participant indicated that ‘the two sets seem to be illustrative rather than comprehensive.’ A third participant stated that ‘there are almost too many conditions and requirements, and some of them overlap to a certain extent.’

These comments suggest that institutionalisation might be too context-dependent to formulate in general conditions and requirements. A way to deal with this can be found in a proposal by a different participant. This participant proposed to conceptually reframe the conditions and requirements to ‘ongoing practices or vectors of continuous improvement.’ This framing also aligns with the interpretation of institutionalisation as ‘entering a reflexive process [rather] than achieving a state.’ This implies that public organisations need to be provided with mechanisms to ignite and fuel institutionalisation of AI-enabled mass deliberation. This understanding of institutionalisation is similar to the notion of adaptive governance, which is an element already included under sustainable integration.

Regarding the substance of conditions and requirements, participants provided similar answers given to the two preceding questions. Participants felt that the full set of conditions and requirements covers institutionalisation (following the understanding conveyed by the

two subgoals) to a great extent. One participant stated: ‘The conditions and requirements cover accessibility, capacity, influence, transparency, governance, resources, and legal embedding – this is thorough!’

At the same time, they provided remarks, suggested additions, or pointed out gaps in the full set. Here, we will focus on what participants felt were absent conditions and requirements related to the two subgoals.

Regarding meaningful deliberation, participants mostly missed conditions and requirements on the quality of deliberation. They provided examples such as criteria for qualitative assessment of contributions and guidelines for handling low-quality or off-topic submissions. More specifically, they expected to see more in relation to the influence of AI on deliberative quality. Participants mentioned, for example, clear communication of how AI processes and summarises inputs, clear communication protocols for AI limitations and potential errors, independent verification of AI fairness and accuracy, safeguards against “consensus manufacturing” through AI summarisation, requirements for human facilitators alongside AI tools, and multi-language requirements.

Other main themes lacking under meaningful deliberation according to participants are accessibility (e.g., specific accessibility standards), influence (e.g., clear, enforceable standards for what constitutes ‘influence’ on decisions), accountability (e.g., accountability mechanisms when deliberative input is ignored), and stimulation of participation (e.g., participant compensation, or equity and inclusion monitoring).

Regarding sustainable integration, participants would like to see more emphasis on the competency of public servants, facilitators, moderators or other roles involved in organising and governing deliberations. More importantly, some participants felt that the conditions and requirements do emphasise that citizens participating in deliberations are empowered through strengthening their competencies, but that skills and capabilities of public servants are not mentioned or included. The full set of conditions and requirements should include training of both civil servants and technical staff, incentives for public servant participation, and the allocation of necessary resources. In line with this, a participant suggested including conditions or requirements for capturing and transferring learnings on AI-enabled mass deliberation.

Other themes that participants felt missing under sustainable integration are coordination between involved actors (e.g., cross-ministerial coordination mechanisms as deliberation often spans multiple policy areas), reporting and monitoring for diagnostics (e.g., mandatory reporting on deliberation outcomes and governmental responses), and positive incentives for working on deliberation (e.g., change management strategies for organisational transformation, or career recognition for officials who champion deliberation).

4) Do you have any remarks, comments, additions, or improvements regarding the conditions and requirements?

This question was mostly aimed at eliciting feedback not yet surfaced in the three preceding questions. Participants provided input on the form of conditions and requirements, the consequentiality conditions and requirements, conditions to the framework itself, current barriers in practice, AI/technology specific remarks, and possibilities on how to further develop the framework. We will shortly discuss each of these themes.

To keep the document provided to the participants concise, we only presented them with a list of conditions and requirements. We did not provide any detailed explanation of each single condition or requirement. Participants mentioned that this made the evaluation difficult. Some participants commented that the short and abstract formulation made it hard to understand the full extent of the conditions and requirements. This has implications for the evaluation; probably, there is variation in how participants interpreted the information provided to them. In addition, participants commented on the phrasing of conditions and requirements. Some felt that they could be more nuanced, while others felt that they were too ambiguous. Finally, participants argued that not all conditions and requirements are on the same hierarchical level. Some conditions are prerequisites to others.

Participants also commented on the consequentiality of conditions and requirements. They argued that in their current form, there are no consequences when conditions are not met. Similarly, some participants suggested including success indicators for each condition or requirement. In general, the main consequence for not fulfilling the conditions is that institutionalisation will not be achieved. However, as another participant commented, this position can result in a situation in which public organisations only focus on satisfying the conditions and requirements, without being concerned about actual institutionalisation. This would disregard the fact that institutionalisation is a process, not a state (see question 3).

We intended to formulate conditions and requirements for institutionalisation. In answering question 4, participants have suggested conditions for the comprehensive framework itself. For example, participants mentioned the need for a framework that is flexible and adaptable to national and sub-national contexts, that provides a phased implementation roadmap that accounts for different levels of organisational maturity and resource availabilities, and that complies with laws and regulations such as, the AI act, GDPR, and applicable national laws.

In answering question 4, participants also provided remarks related to the role of AI in mass deliberation. We interpret this in line with the comments under question 1 that argue for more emphasis on *AI-enabled mass* deliberation. On the other hand, some of the remarks apply more to the AI toolkit of WP4. As such, the remarks can be a starting point for exploring the intersections between work packages 3 and 4. Example of AI-related remarks by participants are: 'AI must be explainable so citizens understand how their views were processed'; 'transparency about AI limitations and potential biases'; and 'the framework's AI conditions focus appropriately on safety and transparency, but could also name AI's positive function: making responsiveness possible at scales where human processing alone would introduce loop-breaking latency.'

4.3. Evaluation results: AI toolkit (WP4)

This section synthesises the results of the first evaluation phase of the WP4 AI toolkit across the four pilots. It analyses how the selected tools performed when applied to different types of deliberative material (e.g., simulated discussions, consultation comments, and policy texts), and how outputs were perceived in terms of coherence, completeness, accuracy, factual correctness, usefulness, and alignment with the intended functionality. The section, therefore, aims to provide a grounded picture of the toolkit's current maturity and practical value, while acknowledging the exploratory nature of this first round and the context-specific requirements of each pilot.

The rest of the section is organised as follows, section 4.3.1 briefly describes the evaluated tools, section 4.3.2 describes the data that were used for the evaluations, section 4.3.3 presents the evaluations results per tool and section 4.3.4 includes a discussion of the results per pilot.

4.3.1. WP4 evaluated outcomes: AI tools

This section briefly describes the WP4 AI tools that were evaluated.

Summarisation: for the summarisation tool, we developed and evaluated a pipeline that comprises the following steps:

- It takes as input the context of the deliberation, along with a list of deliberation comments in a csv form.
- The comments are first filtered based on their relevance to the given context (the step uses LLMs).
- Then they are divided into batches that can fit the LLM context window.
- Then a summary is generated for each batch (the step uses LLMs).
- Finally, the batch summaries are combined to produce a coherent overall summary (the step uses LLMs).

For the summarisation task, we used the LLM models Claude 4 Sonnet, LLaMA 3.3 70B, DeepSeek R1, and Pixtral Large 25.02. The LLM models were accessed through the Bedrock API.

Moderation: for the moderation tool, we developed and evaluated three pipelines that combine three different tools:

- Pipeline 1: LLM. The first pipeline relied completely on an LLM.
- Pipeline 2: LLaMA Guard² → LLM. The third pipeline integrated Detoxify (a moderation tool), LLaMA-Guard, and an LLM.
- Pipeline 3: Detoxify³ → LLaMA Guard → LLM. The second pipeline combined LLaMA-Guard (a locally hosted LLM fine-tuned for moderation) with an LLM.

The specific tools used in the pipelines are:

- LLM: Claude Sonnet 4
- LLaMa Guard: a specialised large language model designed for safety and content moderation.
- Detoxify: machine-learning-based toxicity detection tool used to identify offensive, abusive, or toxic language

LLM-based Argument Extraction: for the LLM-based argument extraction task, we developed and evaluated a pipeline that comprises the following steps:

² <https://ollama.com/library/llama-guard3>

³ <https://github.com/unitaryai/detoxify>

- It takes as input a list of comments from a csv.
- For each comment, we extracted information based on the IBIS model. Focusing mainly on the extraction of positions and relative positive/negative arguments of each position. The outputs were generated using a combination of LLM models and Python libraries (Pydantic, Instructor). (The step uses LLMs).

For the argument extraction task, we used the LLM models Claude 4 Sonnet, LLaMA 3.3 70B, and Pixtral Large 25.02. The models were called through the Bedrock API.

oAMF: The oAMF is a collection of open source modules for argument mining tasks. It is designed as a modular pipeline with swappable components which can be accessed as web services or run locally as Docker containers. Input and output for almost all modules is a JSON file in the eXtended Argument Interchange Format (xAIF): an initial module can be used to convert plaintext into xAIF. For the evaluation, this conversion was done locally using python and standard NLP libraries (Natural Language ToolKit (nlk), BeautifulSoup). This converted the text into an xAIF file populated with potential Argumentative Discourse Units (ADUs). This version of initial processing can be made available as a new module to users.

The modules were run locally as Docker containers.

- **Input:** plaintext or xAIF JSON
- **Output:** xAIF JSON
- **Internal architecture:** The following configuration was used for evaluation in conjunction with a local conversion to xAIF.
 1. **Argument Relation Identification:** Pairs of ADUs are classified as being in a relation of argumentative support or conflict, or in a 'rephrase' relation. Uses a fine-tuned ROBERTA model for classification (https://github.com/arg-tech/AMF_ARI), and window size (how distant ADU pairs for classification can be) can be customised.
 2. **SVG Visualiser:** The SVG Visualiser module produces a visualisation of an xAIF JSON file as an argument map, for easy inspection of the output.
- **Technologies used:** Docker, ROBERTA (finetuned for argument relation classification, model also available separately from HuggingFace)

Translation: for the translation tool, we developed and evaluated a pipeline that takes as input the text to be translated, as well as the source and target languages. These are then passed to an LLM for the translation. The LLM models used are the Claude 4 Sonnet, LLaMA 3.3 70B, and DeepSeek R1, as well as the LibreTranslate tool. The generated output was then evaluated against the reference text to assess its correctness.

ECHO: For the Italian and German pilot, ECHO was used as a practical environment to run and demonstrate audio-supported deliberation and rapid analysis. ECHO is presented as an accessible flow for "scaling small-scale deliberation", supporting physical conversations, multilingual support (50+), and real-time analysis through three custom AI tools, with separate participant and host portals. In the demo format, it is shown as a short sequence (introduction → deliberation → joint analysis).

ECHO is therefore relevant both as:

- a data capture and interaction layer (especially when audio is central), and

- a reference implementation of how analysis outputs can be surfaced to moderators/facilitators in near real time. In this sense, we evaluated the “reporting” and “ask” features of ECHO.

Topic modeling: For topic extraction, two initial methods were used:

- Zero-shot classification, using the pre-trained multilingual language model joeddav/xlm-roberta-large-xnli. Zero-shot classification is an emerging technique which makes predictions about specific knowledge that models may not see during training. Larger models tend to perform better than smaller ones.
- Classification with text embeddings, using the model sentence-transformers/paraphrase-multilingual-mpnet-base-v2, which maps sentences and paragraphs to a vector space. This method analyses text to produce representations of data (embeddings), in order to label text based on semantic meaning. Both methods are classified as on-the-fly, meaning that they have no prior knowledge of an existing corpus and act on a single text entity. Furthermore, both methods used an initial list of pre-determined topics relative to deliberation, in order to assist the models in topic extraction.

The input for the evaluation of topic extraction was six selected articles in the Greek language, obtained from the Greek public consultation platform opengov.gr and spanning various topic categories. The generated output was one list of topics per article, per method, which was then evaluated by the Greek pilot.

4.3.2. Data used for the evaluation

For the evaluations, we used data that were either provided/produced by the pilots, and/or data openly available.

Regarding the **pilots, two data collection approaches** were followed:

- **Previously existing data (Greek and International pilots):** existing datasets from previous pilot activities (Greek pilot) or raw data provided by the associated partner (International pilot) were provided.
- **Deliberation simulation (German and Italian pilots):** in this case there was no previously existing data, so a short, structured discussion was simulated to generate controlled and comparable data (including disagreement, argumentation, and attempts at consensus). The simulation output (e.g., transcript, chat logs, basic metadata) was captured using ECHO.

Specifically, the data we used for the evaluation, as well as the AI tool that they were used are described below:

- Pilot-provided data:
 - **Moderation (Greek pilot):** the Greek pilot provided a set of 42 annotated comments including inappropriate, appropriate and border line comments.
 - **Moderation (German pilot):** the German pilot provided a set of 65 annotated comments based on their deliberation simulation

- **Summarisation/Topic Modeling (Greek pilot):** we used selected deliberations from opengov.gr⁴ (the Greek pilot). For each of these deliberations, we selected specific articles comprising a range of comment 48 – 505. The specific deliberations/articles used are: i) Article 11⁵ (202 comments), ii) Article 24⁶ (135 comments), iii) Article 2⁷ (505 comments), iv) Article 3⁸ (93 comments), v) Article 4⁹ (56 comments) and vi) Article 70¹⁰ (48 comments).
- **Summarisation/ LLM-based Argument Extraction (German pilot):** The German pilot provided a deliberation transcript (based on their deliberation simulation) consisting of 65 text lines. We separated the lines so they could be used as comments. For the summarisation we used the full dataset. For the LLM-based Argument Extraction we used the first 10 lines to enable the manual evaluation of the extracted arguments.
- **Summarisation (Italian pilot):** The Italian pilot provided a deliberation transcript consisting of 71 text lines. We separated the lines so they could be used as comments, and then we created the summaries. For the summarisation we used the full dataset. For the LLM-based Argument Extraction we used the first 10 lines to enable the manual evaluation of the extracted arguments.
- **oAMF/ LLM-based Argument Extraction (International pilot):** The International pilot provided three datasets. For the evaluation a subset of these datasets was used. The specific datasets provided are: i) UK House of Lords Parliamentary Debate on Long Covid,¹¹ ii) UK House of Commons Parliamentary Debate on the Impact of Long Covid on the Workforce,¹² iii) UK House of Commons Library Research Briefing report on Long Covid.¹³
- Openly available data
 - **Translation:** annotated data from the Helsinki-NLP/europarl¹⁴ dataset. The data include a parallel corpus extracted from the European Parliament web site and includes translations for 21 languages.
 - **Moderation:** annotated dataset [mmathys/openai-moderation-api-evaluation](https://huggingface.co/datasets/mmathys/openai-moderation-api-evaluation)¹⁵, which contains many comments labeled across eight categories (sexual, hate, violence, harassment, self-harm, sexual/minors, hate/threatening, violence/graphic). We considered the comments as flagged (inappropriate) and unflagged (appropriate).

⁴ <http://opengov.gr>

⁵ <https://www.opengov.gr/types/?p=7908>

⁶ <https://www.opengov.gr/types/?p=7895>

⁷ <https://www.opengov.gr/ypepth/?p=9>

⁸ <https://www.opengov.gr/types/?p=321>

⁹ <https://www.opengov.gr/types/?p=319>

¹⁰ <https://www.opengov.gr/ypepth/?p=2380>

¹¹ <https://hansard.parliament.uk/lords/2022-11-17/debates/E105F485-3B07-4020-AA3A-118870DCF534/LongCovid>

¹² <https://hansard.parliament.uk/commons/2022-03-31/debates/26A12690-C886-4A8F-AC0A-1247DF5D1BB3/LongCovidImpactOnTheWorkforce>

¹³ <https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk/research-briefings/cbp-9112/>

¹⁴ <https://huggingface.co/datasets/Helsinki-NLP/europarl>

¹⁵ <https://huggingface.co/datasets/mmathys/openai-moderation-api-evaluation>

Comments annotated with at least one category in the original dataset were considered flagged.

4.3.3. Pilot activities for WP4 evaluation

Greek Pilot: The Greek pilot carried out an internal first-round evaluation of selected WP4 functionalities using data drawn from Greek public consultations (opengov.gr) and a small, annotated set of pilot comments for moderation. The purpose of this phase was to assess whether the current tool outputs are sufficiently accurate, usable, and language-consistent to support analysis and reporting in a Greek-language deliberation setting, and to identify priority gaps before any broader deployment.

The evaluation combined (i) pilot-based assessments of outputs produced on Greek consultation material and pilot comments, and (ii) targeted testing of specific functionalities where the Greek language requirement is a hard constraint (e.g., topic extraction and argument extraction). For summarisation, the pilot relied on opengov.gr consultations of varying size; for argument extraction, a consultation dataset of 26 comments was used; for moderation, the pilot provided 42 annotated comments (including appropriate, inappropriate, and borderline cases). For more info on the data see section 4.3.2.

Evaluated tools include: i) summarisation, ii) moderation, iii) LLM-based Argument Extraction and iv) Topic Modeling.

International Pilot: The International Pilot evaluated selected WP4 tools in the specific context of creating and curating an open Long Covid policy graph. In this setting, the first evaluation phase aimed to gauge the immediate capability and potential of argument mining and LLM tools to identify and surface semantic elements and argument structure in an illustrative corpus of Long Covid documents, and to do so accurately, comprehensively, and in a form that is practically useful for graph creation and curation.

The pilot identified an illustrative corpus of candidate sources (e.g., parliamentary debate transcripts and a research briefing, among others). A subset of this corpus was selected for the first evaluation stage (see section 4.3.2). WP4 partners then generated tool outputs for evaluation on this subset. The pilot explicitly notes that this first round was exploratory and context-specific, and that a more conclusive assessment would require a substantially larger corpus.

Evaluated tools include: i) LLM-based Argument Extraction, and ii) oAMF.

Italian pilot: The Italian pilot conducted an internal evaluation round to assess the performance and practical usefulness of selected WP4 AI tools for deliberation support. The assessment was organised in two strands: (i) evaluation of LLM-based summarisation and argument extraction tools using the provided data, and (ii) a focused test of Dembrane's ECHO environment, concentrating on transcription and its report/ask functions.

For the LLM-oriented tests, four ActionAid staff members participated in a structured discussion in Italian (approx. 20 minutes), with assigned roles to ensure contrasting positions. The deliberation took place via Teams with transcription enabled; the transcript was revised only to remove artefacts (e.g., "background noise" references and likely transcription hallucinations), while the substantive content of participants' contributions was left unchanged. The cleaned transcript was shared with CERTH, which returned tool outputs in

two files (summarisation and argument extraction) for evaluation. Individual questionnaires were completed by participants and then consolidated into a single summary sheet.

For the ECHO-related tests, two Italian-language recordings of remote discussions (also role-based) were uploaded to ECHO. The pilot first checked transcript fidelity against the audio and then evaluated ECHO's "report" and "ask" functions.

Evaluated tools include: i) summarisation, ii) LLM-based Argument Extraction, and iii) ECHO.

German pilot: The German pilot conducted an early-stage evaluation of selected WP4 tools under controlled conditions, with the explicit purpose of understanding tool behaviour, strengths and limitations before any citizen-facing deployment, and in view of municipal requirements around procedural accountability and legal certainty. The assessment was based on a deliberation simulation (rather than an existing real-world dataset) to generate comparable and role-diverse discussion data for tool testing.

A small group of N = 5 municipal staff members from different professional backgrounds participated in the simulation and were randomly assigned deliberative roles (e.g., pro/contra/aggressive/moderating) to emulate pluralistic dynamics. The discussion topic ("trade-off between parking lots and bicycle infrastructure in the inner city") was provided in German, supported by short background information to ensure a shared baseline. The transcript was produced in German using ECHO, with informed consent documented.

Evaluated tools include: i) summarisation, ii) LLM-based Argument Extraction, iii) ECHO, and moderation.

4.3.4. Evaluation results per tool

This section reports the evaluation results per tool. Based on the dedicated evaluations per tool, the results can include:

- Quantitative and qualitative pilot-based evaluations (All tools)
- Automated evaluations (annotated data or LLM-as-a-judge) (Some of the tools)

4.3.4.1. Evaluation results of Summarisation

Quantitative pilot-based evaluation

- **Greek pilot:** In the consolidated assessment of summarisation outputs, Claude was rated most positively and most consistently, achieving an average score of 4.43/5 across Q1–Q7 (coherence 5/5, completeness/accuracy/factual correctness 4/5, usefulness 5/5, purpose fit 5/5, guideline alignment 4/5), reflecting outputs perceived as highly topic-specific, well structured, and reliably grounded in the deliberation content. By contrast, Llama performed weakest, with a very low overall average of 1.43/5, driven by poor ratings on completeness (2/5) and uniformly "strongly disagree" ratings on accuracy, factual correctness, usefulness, purpose fit, and guideline alignment (1/5 each), alongside qualitative feedback pointing to generic templating, severe hallucinations, and mixed-language artefacts. Pixtral was assessed as intermediate, with an average score of 2.93/5: most dimensions clustered around "neutral" (3/5 for coherence, accuracy, factual correctness, usefulness, purpose fit, and guideline alignment), while completeness was lower (2.5/5, reflecting split ratings between "disagree" and "neutral"); comments

highlighted excessive length, topic drift/padding, and English-language outputs as practical constraints for Greek administrative use.

- German pilot: In the consolidated assessment, Claude was rated most positively overall, achieving an average score of 3.50/5 across Q1–Q7, with “agree” ratings for coherence (4/5), accuracy (4/5) and purpose fit (4/5), while completeness (3/5), factual correctness (3/5) and guideline alignment (3/5) remained closer to “neutral”; usefulness was rated between “neutral” and “agree” (3.5/5), indicating generally usable but not fully comprehensive summaries. By contrast, Llama showed a strongly uneven profile: despite very high coherence (5/5), it scored extremely low on completeness (1/5) and guideline alignment (1/5), with usefulness and purpose fit closer to “disagree” (2/5 each), resulting in a lower overall average of 2.43/5, reflecting outputs perceived as too vague and insufficiently aligned with expected behaviour for this pilot context. Pixtral was assessed as weakest, with “neutral” coherence (3/5) but “strongly disagree” ratings for accuracy (1/5), usefulness (1/5), purpose fit (1/5) and guideline alignment (1/5), leading to the lowest overall average (1.57/5) and indicating limited reliability for summarisation in this setting.
- Italian pilot: In the consolidated assessment, Claude and Pixtral were consistently rated more positively than Llama 3.3. Specifically, for coherence and completeness, Claude/Pixtral were rated at the level of “agree”, while Llama 3.3 was closer to “neutral”; for accuracy, factual correctness, and usefulness, Claude/Pixtral remained at “agree”, whereas Llama 3.3 fell to “disagree”. This pattern indicates that the main differentiator for Llama 3.3 was not readability alone, but weaker grounding and reliability in reflecting what participants actually said.
- International pilot: In the consolidated assessment, Claude was rated most positively overall, with an average score of 3.00/5 across the seven criteria. Evaluators rated it neutral on coherence (readability/structure) and neutral on factual correctness (no major invented claims), while scoring it lower on completeness and accuracy (it did not capture a sufficiently comprehensive and faithful set of arguments from the source texts). At the same time, Claude scored higher on usefulness and purpose-fit, indicating it can support rapid orientation and triage for curators even if it cannot yet be relied on for structured downstream use; alignment with expected behaviour was rated neutral. By contrast, Llama 3.3 and Pixtral were rated lower and essentially identical, each achieving an average score of 2.29/5. Both were rated low on coherence and accuracy (less clear structure and weaker faithfulness to what is in the texts) and very low on completeness (substantial omissions), while remaining neutral on factual correctness and neutral on usefulness/purpose-fit—suggesting they may still provide some limited support for scanning text, but with more inconsistency and less reliable structure than Claude. Guideline/expected-behaviour alignment was rated low for both models, reflecting a mismatch with the structured extraction needs of the International Pilot.

Qualitative pilot-based evaluation

Summary of evaluation for LLaMA 3.3 70b:

- Greek pilot: The response shows several critical weaknesses. It relies too heavily on generic templates that are unrelated to the actual deliberation topics and lacks topic-specific details or references to proposals. There are also hallucinations and

misinterpretations of the task, including irrelevant statements. Key policy issues, stakeholder concerns, and procedural details are missing. Finally, the output contains mixed Greek–English content, corrupted hybrid terms, and quality degradation in shorter deliberations, indicating unstable content.

- German pilot: The response has several weaknesses. While not factually incorrect, it is often vague and fails to capture the exact topic of discussion for example, summarizing a debate on bike lanes versus parking as merely a “discussion about transportation infrastructure.” Some arguments are mentioned but lack context or connection, and the model’s perception of neutrality is inaccurate, leaning more negative and detecting frustration later in the text. Additionally, the summary does not indicate any consensus reached. Also, there were language mismatches comprehension.
- Italian pilot: There is a general tendency to emphasize positive aspects and areas of agreement rather than critical elements and disagreements. The outputs may contain inaccuracies, generic interpretations, and oversimplifications, particularly with regard to disagreements or subtle interpersonal dynamics. It was good at thematic clustering, coherent basic structure, and sometimes picks up interpersonal dynamics.

Summary of evaluation for Claude 4 Sonnet:

- Greek pilot: The response demonstrates several strengths. It is topic-specific and highly relevant to each deliberation’s content, presenting a well-structured answer with clear numbered points and logical flow. It effectively identifies key themes, captures both majority and minority viewpoints, and highlights specific proposals and concerns raised by commenters. The main limitation is that it does not provide sufficient quantitative indicators.
- German pilot: The response shows some strengths. It correctly identifies the discussion’s negative-leaning sentiment, indicating that Claude goes beyond summarisation to capture connotations. It provides a strong focus on majority arguments and presents them in a single-page bullet-point format. However, it does not assess argument quality and often omits important minority points. The structure is limited, with no organised pro–con layout, making it harder to trace the full discussion. On the positive side, it does capture the consensus reached.
- Italian pilot: Claude performs the most consistently and reliably. Its summaries are accurate, balanced, and avoid major errors, though they tend to be too concise and may miss nuance or deeper motivations behind participants’ positions. It was good at capturing arguments flow and providing coherence overviews.

Summary of evaluation for Pixtral Large 25.02:

- Greek pilot: The response is well-organised, with clear section headers, and attempts to provide comprehensive coverage from multiple angles. However, it also contains hallucinations, language mismatches, and excessive length.
- German pilot: The response captures sentiments accurately, showing that Pixtral can detect the overall tone. However, it is very vague, mentioning topics like “bug fixes” or airport expansions that were not part of the discussion, and fails to address the actual topic. The output is two pages long, somewhat redundant, and follows its own structure

rather than the context of the discussion. Overall, while Pixtral handles sentiment well, it does not capture any arguments in their entirety or reflect the true discussion content.

- Italian pilot: In Pixtral the arguments are well reported, as the general course of the discussion; it is quite remarkable for clarity, structure, and completeness, producing well-organised summaries that are easy to read and understand. However, it sometimes misinterprets metaphors or stances and may overemphasize critical elements rather than positive ones. It was good at well-structured and readability, main ideas are clearly captured and effective chronological reconstruction.

The pilot-based evaluation highlights clear performance differences across the three summarisation models. LLaMA 3.3 70B shows substantial weaknesses across languages, including vague and generic outputs, hallucinations, poor alignment with the actual deliberation topics, and instability in multilingual settings—most notably in the Greek pilot. Claude Sonnet 4 performs most consistently and reliably, producing topic-specific, well-structured summaries that capture key themes, argument flows, and majority–minority positions, particularly in Greek and Italian. Its main limitations are the underrepresentation of minority or weaker arguments and the absence of quantitative indicators. Pixtral Large performs unevenly, offering strong structure, readability, and sentiment detection—especially in Italian—but suffering from verbosity, hallucinations, and frequent topic misalignment in Greek and German.

Automated evaluation (LLM-as-a-judge)

For the evaluation, we use the summarisation metric from the Deepeval framework. To obtain a more reliable score, we run three evaluations on three summaries for each LLM, using two different LLMs as judges and three automatically generated sets of questions for each.

		DeepEval's Summarisation Metric						
		The two judges						
Comments	LLM	Summary	Claude Sonnet			Llama 3.3		
15 comments	Llama 3.3	1st	0.00	0.17	0.00	0.38	0.00	0.30
		2nd	0.07	0.11	0.00	0.11	0.00	0.00
		3rd	0.12	0.06	0.25	0.35	0.29	0.06
	Claude 4 Sonnet	1st	0.18	0.15	0.15	0.16	0.18	0.06
		2nd	0.21	0.6	0.15	0.14	0.09	0.11
		3rd	0.17	0.06	0.17	0.12	0.21	0.06
120 comments	Llama 3.3	1st	0.02	0.03	0.2	0.2	0.5	0.00
		2nd	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.7	0.1	0.7
		3rd	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.9
	Claude 4 Sonnet	1st	0.11	0.40	0.25	0.30	0.31	0.00
		2nd	0.11	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.35	0.19
		3rd	0.40	0.00	0.40	0.45	0.00	0.50
68 comments	Llama 3.3	1st	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.5	0.38	0.38
		2nd	0.62	0.12	0.18	0.75	0.38	0.5
		3rd	0.12	0.12	0.09	0.25	0.25	0.12
	Claude 4 Sonnet	1st	0.23	0.39	0.81	0.00	0.10	0.52
		2nd	0.62	0.19	0.65	0.32	0.00	0.48
		3rd	0.73	0.77	0.10	0.63	0.44	0.62

The effect of the Deliberation Size

Across three different deliberation sizes, there are differences in the distribution of mean summary scores. The summaries of the 15 comments deliberation showed the lowest performance with a mean score of 0.14 and a tightly clustered distribution, indicating limited summary quality. In the 68-comment deliberation, the mean was 0.35 and the median was 0.34, with a broader distribution evenly distributed across the mid and higher ranges of the scale. Meanwhile, in the 120-comment deliberation, the mean score was 0.26, with a more dispersed distribution, suggesting greater variability and a mild positive skew, but not of the same quality as the 68-comment deliberation. Overall, the descriptive results suggest that summary evaluation scores improve from 15 to 68 comments deliberation, but when the deliberation size increases to 120, they decline again.

To further test whether the quality of summaries differed across deliberation sizes, we conducted a Kruskal-Wallis H test with deliberation size as the grouping variable. The analysis revealed a significant effect of deliberation size on the mean score. Furthermore, the mean ranks show a clear pattern. The 15 comments Mean Rank of 17.17, the 68 comments Mean Rank of 36.94, and the 120 comments Mean Rank of 28.39 confirm the results of the descriptive statistics that from a moderately sized deliberation of 68 comments, LLMs can produce far better summaries than the very small ones, and somewhat better from the very large ones.

Non-parametric Spearman correlation showed a small but significant positive correlation between deliberation size and mean scores. This indicates that summaries of large deliberations indeed tend to receive higher scores than those of smaller deliberations. However, the effect size is modest, and, in light of the descriptive and Kruskal-Wallis H test results, this correlation should be interpreted as capturing a general upward trend rather than a strictly linear improvement in the quality of the summary as deliberation size increases.

The Summariser performance level

Across the three summariser models we used in this study (i.e., Claude, Deepseek, Llama), the distributions of the mean scores show noticeable differences in central tendency and variability. Claude produced the highest average scores, closely followed by Deepseek, while Llama generated lower scores. The medians follow a similar pattern, with Claude and Deepseek centered around 0.23-0.24, and Llama at 0.175. The 95% confidence intervals indicate reasonably tight, overlapping bounds for Claude and Deepseek, whereas for Llama the interval shows greater variability. Overall, the patterns suggest that Claude and Deepseek produce more comparable and consistent scores while Llama tends to yield more variable and less stable results with a few high scoring outliers. Furthermore, the Kruskal-Wallis H test on the mean scores of the summarisers suggests that there is no statistically significant difference in evaluation scores across the three LLMs, with equal sample sizes (18 summaries per model). Although the mean ranks of the summarisers varied from 23.03 to 30.06, these differences are within the range of random variation, meaning that the three models perform comparably on the summarisation task.

The judges' performance level

The analysis suggests that the two judges apply the scoring scale in a similar but not identical way. Claude assigns, on average, somewhat lower scores, with a median of 0.180 and an SD of 0.156, ranging from 0.00 to 0.55. In contrast, Llama is more generous and more variable in

its scoring, with a mean of 0.284, a median of 0.233, an SD of 0.171, and scores ranging from 0.004 to 0.63. Overall, the two judges tend to disagree on which summaries are better or worse, highlighting substantial subjectivity in automated LLM-as-a-judge evaluation.

Furthermore, to assess the agreement of the two judges, we computed a Spearman rank correlation between their mean scores. The correlation was very low and non-significant, indicating that Claude and Llama do not systematically rank the summaries in the same way. In other words, a summary that receives a relatively high score from one judge is not reliably scored high by the other, suggesting weak consistency between the two models. Regarding the judges' scores for the same summaries, the Wilcoxon signed-rank test indicated that the scores were systematically different between the two judges. Out of 27 paired evaluations, 15 cases received a higher score from Llama, whereas 12 cases received a higher score from Claude, with no exact ties. Although this pattern suggests a slight tendency for Llama to give higher ratings, the difference was not statistically significant. Thus, although Llama is, on average, more generous, we cannot conclude that the two judges differ reliably in their overall scoring.

4.3.4.2. Evaluation results of Moderation

Quantitative pilot-based evaluation

- Greek Pilot: Across the seven evaluation criteria—coherence (readability/structure), completeness (captures the main elements needed for a moderation decision), accuracy (faithfully reflects the content being moderated), factual correctness (no incorrect/invented claims), usefulness (helps understand what should be moderated and why), purpose fit (serves the moderation function), and alignment with expected behaviour (matches the guideline logic)—the Detoxify → LlamaGuard → LLM pipeline (Pipeline A) performed best, with an average score of 3.71/5 (rated “agree” on coherence, accuracy, usefulness, purpose fit and guideline alignment; and closer to “neutral” on completeness and factual correctness). The LLM-only pipeline (Pipeline C) showed a “middle-ground” profile with an average score of 3.00/5, i.e., consistently “neutral” across all criteria, aligning with comments that it performs better than Pipeline B but still misses categories such as spam/off-topic content. By contrast, LlamaGuard → LLM (Pipeline B) received the lowest ratings with an average score of 2.14/5 (neutral coherence but “disagree” across completeness, accuracy, factual correctness, usefulness, purpose fit and guideline alignment), consistent with the reported 35.7% error rate (15/42) and qualitative notes on Greek profanity blind spots, masked profanity not being detected, and personal attacks passing through.
- German Pilot: Across the seven evaluation criteria—coherence (readability/structure), completeness (captures the main elements needed for a moderation decision), accuracy (faithfully reflects what is in the content), factual correctness (no incorrect/invented claims in the moderation rationale), usefulness (helps interpret what should be moderated and why), purpose fit (serves the civility/moderation function), and alignment with expected behaviour (matches the guideline logic)—the Detoxify→LlamaGuard→LLM pipeline achieved the highest overall average score (3.86/5; tied with LlamaGuard→LLM), driven by very strong ratings for coherence and completeness (both 5/5) and consistently “agree” ratings on accuracy/usefulness/purpose-fit/guideline alignment (all 4/5), while receiving a notably low score on factual correctness (1/5), reflecting concerns about incorrect or insufficiently justified moderation decisions despite better context sensitivity.

The LlamaGuard→LLM pipeline reached the same average (3.86/5) through a different profile—very strong completeness and accuracy (both 5/5), but more “neutral” assessments for factual correctness, purpose-fit, and guideline alignment (each 3/5), consistent with comments that it can catch some negative context (e.g., sarcasm) but still misses certain problematic formulations. The LLM-only pipeline scored slightly lower (3.57/5), with high coherence/completeness (both 5/5) but weaker factual correctness (2/5) and weaker alignment with expected behaviour (2/5), aligning with feedback that it mainly flags the most explicit cases (e.g., overt racism/insults) and therefore functions more like “insult moderation” than broader civility moderation.

Qualitative pilot-based evaluation

Summary of evaluations for Pipeline 1 (LLM):

- Greek Pilot: The system shows a 31% error rate, it was better than LLaMA-Guard → LLM and worse than Detoxify → LLaMA-Guard → LLM. Good with personal attacks and offensive content. But still lacks at detecting spam and off topic content.
- German Pilot: The system shows a 16% error rate. Only flags straight up racism and other very obvious cases of insults. So, this is only an ‘insult moderation’ no ‘civility moderation’.

Summary of evaluations for Pipeline 2 (LLaMA-Guard → LLM):

- Greek Pilot: The system shows a 36% error rate, making it unusable for production use. It exhibits a critical Greek profanity blind spot, failing to detect some Greek slurs, indicating the absence of effective Detoxify coverage. Personal attacks were also wrongly allowed. Overall, this pipeline would require four times more human review compared to Pipeline Detoxify → LLaMA-Guard → LLM.
- German Pilot: The system shows a 15% error rate This pipeline catches some negative connotated context like sarcasm and harshly denying provided evidence. On the other hand, it does not flag bad language about thirds

Summary of evaluations for Pipeline 3 (Detoxify → LLaMA-Guard → LLM):

- Greek Pilot: The system shows a 26% error rate. Best overall accuracy among three pipelines. Strong hate speech (homophobia, transphobia, antisemitism, racism), threat detection and disinformation. But still lacks at detecting spam and off topic content.
- German Pilot: The system shows a 4% error rate. This was the best of the three provided pipelines. It is more context sensitive than the others and more aware of ‘rudeness’, while the others only flagged direct insults. But still this pipeline did not catch all of the rude or even conspiracy comments.

In general, pilots agreed that Pipeline 3 performed best overall among the three. However, all pipelines show weaknesses in handling spam, off-topic content, and advertisements, indicating limitations in the prompt instructions.

Automated evaluation

We passed each comment of the dataset¹⁶, through the three pipelines and classified it as either flagged or unflagged. We then compared the predicted label with the ground-truth annotation and computed the number of true positives (TP), false positives (FP), true negatives (TN), and false negatives (FN). And subsequently calculated Precision, Recall and F1 scores.

Languages	Scores	Pipeline 1	Pipeline 2	Pipeline 3
English	Precision	0.840	0,859	0.674
	Recall	0.958	0,944	0.984
	F1 Score	0.895	0,899	0.800
German	Precision	0.861	0,835	0.709
	Recall	0.958	0,930	1.000
	F1 Score	0.907	0,880	0.830
Italian	Precision	0.850	0,838	0.759
	Recall	0.958	0,944	0.984
	F1 Score	0.901	0,887	0.857
Greek	Precision	0.840	0,838	0.690
	Recall	0.958	0,944	0.984
	F1 Score	0.895	0,887	0.811

The evaluation shows that Pipeline 1 (LLM-only) and Pipeline 2 (LLaMA Guard → LLM) achieve the best overall performance across all languages, with high F1-scores indicating a strong balance between Precision and Recall. Pipeline 2 consistently provides the most robust results, suggesting that combining a specialized moderation LLM with a general-purpose LLM improves moderation accuracy without introducing excessive filtering.

Pipeline 3 (Detoxify → LLaMA Guard → LLM) achieves near-perfect Recall, minimizing false negatives (FN) and ensuring that harmful content is rarely missed. However, this comes at the cost of substantially lower Precision, leading to a high number of false positives (FP), where benign content is incorrectly flagged.

From a moderation policy perspective, these results highlight a key trade-off: systems prioritizing maximum safety may tolerate higher FP rates, while systems designed for balanced, user-facing moderation should aim to reduce unnecessary content blocking.

¹⁶ <https://huggingface.co/datasets/mmathys/openai-moderation-api-evaluation>

It is important to note that the annotated approach favors Pipeline 2 (LLaMA Guard → LLM) for its balanced precision and recall, minimizing false positives and negatives, making it suitable for fully automated moderation. In contrast, Pipeline 3 (Detoxify → LLaMA Guard → LLM) performs best in pilot-based, human-in-the-loop evaluations, detecting a broader range of harmful content despite more false positives. This highlights that the optimal pipeline depends on moderation context, risk tolerance, and policy priorities.

4.3.4.3. Evaluation results of Argument extraction (LLM-based & oAMF)

Quantitative pilot-based evaluation

- Greek pilot: Across the seven evaluation criteria—coherence (easy to read/structured), completeness (captures the main ideas), accuracy (faithfully reflects what participants said), factual correctness (no incorrect/invented claims), usefulness (helps understand the deliberation), purpose fit (serves the argument-extraction function), and alignment with expected behaviour (matches the guideline expectations)—Claude was rated most positively overall, with an average score of 4.29/5, scoring 5/5 on coherence and factual correctness and 4/5 (“agree”) on completeness, accuracy, usefulness, purpose fit, and guideline alignment, consistent with comments highlighting clear separation of positions and arguments and fully Greek-language output suitable for policy reporting. Pixtral was the second-best option, with a strong and stable profile and an average score of 4.00/5, receiving 4/5 (“agree”) across all seven criteria, reflecting assessments that its balanced presentation of positions/counter-arguments and consistent Greek language make it usable for official reports (albeit as a second choice to Claude). By contrast, Llama performed weakest, with an average score of 2.00/5, scoring 2/5 (“disagree”) across all criteria, aligning with qualitative feedback that language inconsistency (English positions appearing in a Greek consultation output) undermines credibility and practical usability for policy-facing analysis.
- Italian pilot: Across the seven criteria—coherence (readability/structure), completeness (captures the main ideas), accuracy (faithfully reflects what participants said), factual correctness (no incorrect/invented claims), usefulness (helps understand the deliberation), purpose fit (serves argument extraction), and alignment with expected behaviour (matches the guideline expectations)—Claude and Pixtral were rated most positively and essentially identically, each achieving an average score of 3.71/5. Both tools scored “agree” (4/5) on coherence, completeness, factual correctness, usefulness, and purpose fit, while scoring “neutral” (3/5) on accuracy and guideline alignment, indicating outputs that are generally readable and usable but not consistently faithful enough (or sufficiently aligned to the expected extraction behaviour) to be treated as fully reliable structured representations. By contrast, Llama 3.3 scored lower overall (average 2.29/5), with neutral coherence and completeness (3/5), but “disagree” (2/5) on accuracy, factual correctness, usefulness, purpose fit, and guideline alignment—suggesting that the key limitation is not readability alone, but weaker grounding and methodological fit for extracting arguments in a stable, decision-relevant way.
- German pilot: Across the seven evaluation criteria—coherence (easy to read/structured), completeness (captures the main ideas), accuracy (faithfully reflects what participants said), factual correctness (no incorrect/invented claims), usefulness (helps understand the deliberation), purpose fit (serves the argument-extraction function), and alignment with expected behaviour (matches the guideline expectations)—Claude and Pixtral performed

similarly and highest overall, each achieving an average score of 2.71/5. Claude was rated mostly “neutral” on coherence/accuracy/factual correctness/usefulness/purpose fit (3/5 each), but lower on completeness (2/5) and guideline alignment (2/5), reflecting outputs that are readable but not fully capturing all positions and not consistently behaving as expected for structured extraction. Pixtral showed a comparable pattern (mostly 3/5), with slightly stronger completeness (3/5) but weaker factual correctness (2/5) and similarly low guideline alignment (2/5), consistent with concerns about stance/relations not being captured reliably despite a more complete list of positions/arguments. Llama 3.3 scored lowest with an average of 2.29/5, driven by lower completeness and accuracy (2/5 each), weaker purpose fit (2/5), and especially very low guideline alignment (1/5), aligning with comments that it mis-assigns positions and can over-associate negative wording with negative stances without sufficient contextual grounding.

- International pilot: Across the seven evaluation criteria—coherence (easy to read/structured), completeness (captures the main ideas), accuracy (faithfully reflects the source text), factual correctness (no incorrect/invented claims), usefulness (supports understanding/curation), purpose fit (serves argument extraction), and alignment with expected behaviour (matches the guideline expectations)—Claude was rated most positively overall, with an average score of 3.00/5, driven by higher ratings on usefulness and purpose-fit (both “agree”) while remaining weaker on completeness and accuracy (both “disagree”), indicating value for rapid triage but not for reliable structured extraction. Llama 3.3 and Pixtral were rated lower and essentially identical, each with an average score of 2.29/5, reflecting very low completeness (“strongly disagree”), lower coherence/accuracy (“disagree”), and only neutral usefulness/purpose-fit—suggesting limited support for scanning, but insufficient reliability for downstream use in the policy-graph workflow. oAMF performed weakest overall, with an average score of 1.57/5: despite a comparatively higher rating on factual correctness (“agree”), it was rated “strongly disagree” on coherence, completeness, usefulness, purpose-fit and guideline alignment, indicating outputs that were not considered readable, complete, or operationally useful for the International Pilot’s argument-structuring needs in this first round.

Qualitative pilot-based evaluation

Summary of evaluation for LLaMA 3.3 70b:

- Greek pilot: Llama’s output is unsuitable for use in policy reports due to language inconsistency. The presence of English positions in a Greek consultation would create confusion and reduce the credibility of any analysis.
- Italian pilot: Much of the extracted information was neither arguments nor positions but simple observations or attitudes. It would be useful to distinguish more clearly between arguments and other observations. Additionally, the extraction contains numerous hallucinations, including the appearance of English words or entire sentences that are not present in the original data. A “?” appears in place of some letters containing accents.
- German pilot: Some positions are not captured accurately, and certain statements are interpreted as argumentative positions when they are not, for example, “There must be a middle ground” versus the corresponding argument “there has to be a good middle

ground.” The system also appears to associate negative wording with a negative stance, without fully considering the actual content of the position.

- International pilot: Based on the initial testing, the output from Llama 3.3 appears to be less precise than Claude and more comprehensive than Pixtral. The primary case for persisting with Llama 3.3 (and Llama’s subsequent releases would be its open-source nature and the potential to shift the precision closer to Claude’s output via systematically improved prompting.) As with Claude, Llama 3.3’s output is helpful to some degree in offering the human curator a quick insight into some of the arguments contained within the relevant texts. However, the output is not yet sufficiently comprehensive, nor accurately structured, nor coherently interrelated to facilitate automatic, non-human supervised inclusion in the graph or to remove the need for the human curator to work directly from the original texts.

Summary of evaluation for Claude 4 Sonnet:

- Greek pilot: Claude delivers an excellent extraction structure, with clear separation of positions and arguments, and maintains full language consistency (Greek only). Positions are clearly articulated and faithfully reflect the content of the consultation on Regulation (EU) 2022/868. The clarity of formulation allows the output to be used directly in policy reports. However, better coverage of objections would improve the balance of the presentation.
- Italian pilot: The extraction was the most comprehensive, however, sometimes it did not extract elements that were significant for the deliberation.
- German pilot: The tool captures a lot of positions, but not all of them. It is not reliable when judging the stance of arguments depending on positions. It does not filter out nonsense. E.g., one “Argument” was: ‘this.. is trash’ which is by definition no argument.
- International pilot: Based on the initial testing, Claude appeared to be most promising of the three LLMs for the specific goals of the International Pilot, while still not demonstrating sufficient, immediate utility to meet the high and precise demands of the International Pilot. Claude’s output is helpful to some degree in offering the human curator a quick and reasonably clearly expressed insight into some of the arguments contained within the relevant texts, and the practical utility of this dimension might well increase when applied across a much larger corpus of texts. However, the output is not yet sufficiently comprehensive, nor accurately structured, nor coherently interrelated to facilitate automatic, non-human supervised inclusion in the graph or to remove the need for the human curator to work directly from the original texts.

Summary of evaluation for Pixtral Large 25.02:

- Greek pilot: Pixtral offers reliable output for policy analysis. The balanced presentation of positions and counter-arguments allows for a more complete picture of public opinion. Consistent Greek language makes the output suitable for official reports. It is a good second choice after Claude.
- Italian pilot: Much of the extracted information are not arguments or positions but simple observations or attitudes. It would be useful to distinguish more clearly between arguments and other observations. Additionally, the extraction contains numerous

hallucinations, including the appearance of English words or entire sentences that are not present in the original data. A “?” appears in place of some letters containing accents.

- German pilot: The tool performs better with judging relations between arguments and positions than the others, but is still far away from reliable. Argument stances to positions are not captured appropriately. But the list of positions and arguments is more complete compared with the other tools.
- International pilot: Based on the initial testing, the output from Pixtral was the most variable in quality; with some signs of relatively promising capability in a few instances outweighed by the overall comparative weakness versus Claude (and to a marginal extent versus Llama 3.3.). The occasional high-quality instance – allied with Pixtral’s open-source nature – suggests that there might be a case for persisting with the Pixtral and experimenting with the prompts to explore whether it is possible to systematically shift its general performance closer to its peak performance. Refined prompts might also help to avoid the cases in which Pixtral misinterprets a Pro idea expressed via a negative sentiment as a Con. As with Claude, Pixtral’s output is helpful to some degree in offering the human curator a quick insight into some of the arguments contained within the relevant texts. However, the output is not yet sufficiently comprehensive, nor accurately structured, nor coherently interrelated to facilitate automatic, non-human supervised inclusion in the graph or to remove the need for the human curator to work directly from the original texts.

Summary of evaluations for oAMF:

- International pilot: The oAMF (Open Argument Mining Framework) output was the most surprising in this first round of testing, as the anticipated extra fidelity and precision that argument mining offers (in principle) versus LLMs didn’t manifest in the outputs generated for the small set of short texts used – and the outputs demonstrated no immediate utility for the International Pilot. The Default Inference annotations that the tool generated displayed significant noise and little usable signal, and, while the argument mining output generated longer chains of thought than the LLMs, the chains of thought offered less analytical insight to the human curator than the shorter fragments identified by the LLMs. The observation that the argument mining tool didn’t identify any Propositional Relations other than Default Inference and Default Rephrase in test corpus was puzzling too.

Across pilots and languages, Claude performed best overall, producing clear and relatively policy-ready extractions. However, it still lacks sufficient depth, balance, and structural rigor for fully automated use. Pixtral was a strong secondary option, with good structure and completeness, but showed variability, stance misinterpretation, and occasional bias. LLaMA showed limited analytical promise but suffered from language inconsistency, imprecision, and weak structure, making it unsuitable for unsupervised or official policy use. oAMF resolved some issues, but its outputs remain weak and require further investigation.

Argument extraction and structuring proved the most challenging task across all pilots. The German pilot reported the weakest results and low guideline alignment. The Italian pilot confirmed stronger performance by Claude and Pixtral, but persistent difficulties remained in distinguishing arguments from attitudes, representing disagreement, and capturing conclusions. The International pilot requires graph-ready argument reconstruction, a

threshold that none of the tools met; LLMs were useful only for rapid scanning or triage. The Greek pilot showed comparatively better results, especially with Claude, but still required safeguards and improved coverage of objections.

4.3.4.4. Evaluation results of Translation

Automated evaluation

Based on the automated evaluations the following scores occurred.

German - English				
<i>Averages</i>	CLAUDE	DEEPSEEK	LLAMA	LIBRETRANSLATE
BERTScore Precision	0.8125	0.7900	0.8027	0.7941
BERTScore Recall	0.8001	0.7916	0.7920	0.7660
BERTScore F1	0.8052	0.7887	0.7963	0.7787
METEOR Score	0.5273	0.5020	0.5183	0.4826
ROUGE-1 Score	0.6231	0.6017	0.6161	0.5948
ROUGE-2 Score	0.3897	0.3614	0.3793	0.3495
ROUGE-L Score	0.5795	0.5501	0.5641	0.5411

Greek - English				
<i>Averages</i>	CLAUDE	DEEPSEEK	LLAMA	LIBRETRANSLATE
BERTScore Precision	0.7904	0.7672	0.7896	0.8119
BERTScore Recall	0.7978	0.7840	0.7960	0.8042
BERTScore F1	0.7929	0.7729	0.7916	0.8069
METEOR Score	0.5260	0.4962	0.5422	0.5727
ROUGE-1 Score	0.6221	0.5913	0.6240	0.6573
ROUGE-2 Score	0.3849	0.3524	0.3903	0.4398
ROUGE-L Score	0.5784	0.5511	0.5859	0.6199

Italian - English				
<i>Averages</i>	CLAUDE	DEEPSEEK	LLAMA	LIBRETRANSLATE
BERTScore Precision	0.7706	0.7581	0.7698	0.7554
BERTScore Recall	0.7727	0.7713	0.7756	0.7492

Italian - English				
BERTScore F1	0.7709	0.7628	0.7720	0.7515
METEOR Score	0.4719	0.4628	0.4772	0.4463
ROUGE-1 Score	0.5708	0.5721	0.5735	0.5556
ROUGE-2 Score	0.3207	0.3236	0.3229	0.2894
ROUGE-L Score	0.5230	0.5173	0.5221	0.5011

Claude and LLaMA emerge as the strongest models for German–English and Italian–English translation, particularly in terms of semantic understanding and meaning preservation, as reflected by their consistently high BERTScore Precision, Recall, and F1 values. This indicates that these LLMs are effective at capturing the underlying intent of the source text, even when syntactic structure or lexical choices differ between the source and target languages.

In contrast, for Greek–English translation, LibreTranslate clearly outperforms all LLM-based models across both semantic and lexical metrics, including BERTScore, METEOR, and all ROUGE variants. This suggests that, for Greek, the rule-based or statistical foundations and linguistic resources of LibreTranslate provide better handling of morphological complexity, inflection, and language-specific constructions, leading to translations that more closely align with reference texts at both the semantic and surface levels. Among the LLMs, LLaMA performs best for Greek, while DeepSeek shows noticeably weaker performance.

DeepSeek demonstrates moderate performance for Italian–English, with scores comparable to the other models in several lexical metrics, but it struggles significantly with Greek–English, where lower BERTScore and ROUGE values indicate reduced semantic coverage and weaker lexical alignment. This highlights variability in model robustness across language pairs, particularly for morphologically rich or lower-resource languages.

Finally, across all language pairs, the evaluation shows that BERTScore consistently yields higher and more stable results than METEOR and ROUGE. Since BERTScore emphasizes semantic similarity rather than exact word or phrase matching, this pattern indicates that, even when different wording is used, the models generally succeed in preserving the core meaning of the source text. This reinforces the suitability of semantic-aware metrics for evaluating LLM-based translation pipelines, where paraphrasing and lexical variation are expected and often desirable.

4.3.4.5. Evaluation results of ECHO

Quantitative pilot-based evaluation

- Italian pilot: Based solely on the questionnaire completed for both tests (reported as identical), ECHO received very high scores across all assessed dimensions, with an overall average of 4.86/5 across the seven criteria. Specifically, evaluators rated the output as strongly agreeing on coherence (easy to read/structured), completeness (captures main ideas), accuracy (reflects what participants said), and usefulness (supports understanding of the deliberation), and also strongly agreeing that it fits the purpose of the functionality and aligns with expected behaviour. The only slightly lower score was factual correctness,

rated at the level of “agree” (4/5) rather than “strongly agree,” indicating that while the output was assessed as highly reliable overall, it was the only criterion with any reported reservation in the quantitative scoring.

- German pilot: Based on the questionnaire, ECHO received very high scores across all seven criteria, with an overall average of 4.86/5. Evaluators strongly agreed (5/5) that the output was coherent (easy to read/structured), complete (captures main ideas), accurate (reflects what participants said), and useful for understanding the deliberation; they also strongly agreed (5/5) that the output fits the purpose of the tool/functionality and aligns with expected behaviour. The only slightly lower rating was factual correctness at 4/5 (“agree”), indicating a minor reservation on whether all elements were fully free of incorrect or non-grounded claims, while overall quantitative performance remained very strong.

Qualitative pilot-based evaluation

Summary of results:

- Italian pilot: Across both Italian-language tests, transcription quality was assessed as very high, providing a reliable basis for subsequent analysis. The generic “summary” function was reported to perform poorly in Italian; however, the “report” function was assessed very positively, both for clustering key points (supported by quotes) and for producing a balanced synthesis that reflects different positions. The “ask” outputs were described as useful for understanding the stages of discussion and surfacing proposals/solutions. Observed issues and risks. Two recurring issues were highlighted. First, the report sometimes included references to ECHO’s performance and treated them as substantive topics within the deliberation, rather than separating tool/process commentary from the debate. Second, certain behavioural nuances (tone, intensity, interaction patterns) were not explicitly highlighted, and therefore may be flattened when the output is presented in an intentionally balanced way. The pilot also raised cross-cutting concerns regarding anonymity and the handling of language deemed inappropriate for reporting purposes (e.g., swear words reproduced in quotations).
- German pilot: ECHO was the by far best summary. It gets a very specific grasp about the sentiment, as well as it captures all core arguments and the proposed solution (no consensus was found, but next steps defined). The output was very concise ~ half a page (compared to 1-2 pages for the other tools). Depending completeness: ECHO captures everything that is relevant for the ongoing discussion and, while it does not list specific arguments, does name all core arguments.

4.3.4.6. Evaluation results of Topic Modeling

Quantitative pilot-based evaluation

Across the seven evaluation criteria—coherence (easy to read/structured), completeness (captures the main ideas), accuracy (reflects the content), factual correctness (no incorrect/invented claims), usefulness (helps understand the deliberation), purpose fit (reflects the goal of topic extraction), and alignment with expected behaviour (matches the guideline expectations)—Output 1 received low ratings overall, with an average score of 2.25/5 (calculated over the six scored criteria, as usefulness was not rated in both questionnaires). Quantitatively, evaluators rated coherence as neutral-to-agree (3–4/5), but

scored completeness, accuracy, factual correctness, purpose fit, and guideline alignment consistently at “disagree” (2/5), indicating that while the output is readable, it fails to extract topics that are meaningfully linked to the text. Output 2 showed a modest improvement, achieving an average score of 3.07/5 (across all seven criteria), driven by neutral ratings (3/5) on completeness, accuracy, factual correctness, usefulness, purpose fit, and guideline alignment, and neutral-to-agree coherence (3–4/5)—suggesting occasional relevance but still inconsistent and not robust enough for reliable analytical use. Notably, in both outputs, evaluators flagged that results were delivered in English instead of the required Greek, which—independently of the topic-quality scores—constitutes a failure to meet basic pilot specifications.

Qualitative pilot-based evaluation

The Greek pilot also evaluated the topic extraction functionality and reported two core issues.

First, language compliance: in both evaluated outputs, results were delivered in English rather than Greek, which the pilot explicitly identified as a failure to meet basic specifications for the Greek pilot context.

Second, topic relevance and reliability: the pilot concluded that Output 1 not very effective for topic extraction, repeatedly producing generic governance topics (e.g., migration, housing, polarisation) that did not align with the actual content across test cases (e.g., education staffing, animal welfare definitions, offshore taxation, regulation of animal exhibitions). The pilot interpretation was that the system appeared to apply a static/predefined taxonomy rather than extracting themes from the text, rendering the output unusable and potentially misleading.

Output 2 showed some improvement in some cases (e.g., correctly identifying education-related topics for the education staffing input, and economic policy topics for offshore taxation), but still injected irrelevant generic governance terms in other cases and remained inconsistent. The pilot concluded that further improvements are needed to make the tool fully operational.

4.4. Results: acceptance, trust and usability (WP5)

This sub-section presents the main results from the methodology presented in section 3.5.1.

The scope of the measurement instrument is explicitly focused on citizens. The items will be designed to be answered by citizens after they have used the AI-enabled deliberation platform.

We define both aspects based on our context. Acceptance is treated as an evaluative and behavioral orientation reflecting citizens’ willingness and readiness to participate through the platform, to continue using it in future deliberations, and to rely on its outputs as part of a democratic process. This definition focuses on citizen adoption rather than institutional adoption. Trust is not defined as a single belief but as a multi-aspect target compatible with the sociotechnical and institutional nature of AI-enabled deliberations. More specifically, it is framed as a citizen’s confidence in the dependability and appropriateness of the deliberation arrangement under conditions of uncertainty. In this way, trust will reflect more than one target that matters for deliberation legitimacy and system reliance. This means that it is possible to be represented by more than one construct. Finally, another important decision is

that multifaceted constructs are allowed. This will help us capture distinct but related components of various aspects.

To develop an initial construct and item pool, we conducted two systematic literature reviews following the PRISMA guidelines. The first literature review focuses on eDemocracy, eParticipation, deliberation, consultation, and acceptance, while the second focuses on AI and acceptance.

For both literature reviews, we conducted searches in Scopus and Web of Science databases. The steps identified by the PRISMA methodology, i.e., Identification, Screening, Eligibility, and Included, resulted in 164 articles in total. Appendix F presents the findings of the eDemocracy, eParticipation, deliberation, consultation, and acceptance literature review, while Appendix G presents the AI and acceptance.

Based on the two literature reviews, we have prepared an initial pool of constructs and items that will serve as a foundation for expert review and validation.

The initial pool consists of 18 main constructs (with or without constructs as facets) and 19 candidate constructs. The main constructs were proposed as the primary building blocks of the acceptance and trust model, while the secondary constructs were proposed as candidates that could enhance explanatory power, provide conceptual nuance, or capture different technological or deliberative aspects in more context-specific situations. For the 18 main constructs, items were also generated. For the constructs that had no facets, we created two to four items, and for the ones with facets, we created around two items for the construct and two items per facet.

It is important to note that before the initial pool construction, we had a phase in which we merged some constructs. The merges were done according to some “rules” for harmonizing constructs from different acceptance/trust models into a single model. Some rules are (i) treat synonyms as the same construct (e.g., “Perceived Usefulness” is functionally “Performance Expectancy”), (ii) merge highly overlapping dimensions under a broader umbrella when they describe the same underlying belief (e.g., privacy/security/ethical worries under one “Perceived Risks” construct), (iii) decompose high level constructs (e.g., multidimensional “fit” or community constructs) into specific constructs that already existed in the literature, (iv) rename for clarity, and (v) exclude constructs that do not generalize in our context (e.g., price/cost, and various background demographics).

Next, we had to select the measurement format. A standardized questionnaire format was selected in which constructs are measured through multiple citizen-facing items, and respondents indicate their level of agreement using a Likert-type response scale (5- or 7-point Likert scale from “Strongly Disagree” to “Strongly Agree”). Each item will be written in plain language, focusing on a single idea and avoiding technical or overly deliberative terminology. Finally, items will be organised thematically, and the use of reverse worded items will be minimized.

To move forward with the next steps, we needed to establish an expert panel to support content validation of the proposed acceptance trust model and its measurement instrument. We reached out to experts from the project consortium. By selecting experts from the project, we ensured strong alignment with the research context and the practical realities of developing, implementing, and evaluating AI-enabled deliberation platforms.

The panel included experts from multiple relevant fields like AI governance and policy, deliberative democracy, eGovernment and eParticipation research, as well as deliberation practice.

After the expert identification, we proceeded with the evaluations.

In the first expert round, the experts assessed several aspects of the proposed set of constructs (e.g., relevance, essentiality, clarity of definitions, redundancy, and completeness). In this round, we have completed a questionnaire survey and a focus group.

In the questionnaire survey, each construct was rated by 10 experts.

Experts Profile

The panel was deliberately interdisciplinary, reflecting the socio-technical nature of AI-enabled deliberations. Experts reported substantial expertise in various domains, including eParticipation/eDemocracy/eGovernment, political science and deliberative democracy, human-computer interaction, information systems, and AI in the public sector, with several experts identifying as practitioners working directly with public participation and deliberation processes or platforms.

In terms of professional experience, the panel (13 experts in total) represented a wide range of seniority, from 0-5 years (1) to highly experienced profiles exceeding 20 years. A substantial share of experts had more than 20 years of professional or research experience (6), while others had 6 to 10 (1), 11 to 15 (2), or 16 to 20 (3).

Relevance Ratings

Relevance evaluation showed generally high expert agreement that the proposed construct pool contains important drivers of acceptance and trust in our context (CVI/Ave=0,835). Also, several constructs achieved high levels of relevance agreement, including those related to trust and quality, as well as those commonly used in technology acceptance research.

Some constructs reached unanimous agreement (I-CVI = 1,00), while many reached strong agreement (I-CVI = 0,90). At the same time, a smaller subset received weaker relevance agreement (I-CVI = 0,60) and one construct was rated as borderline (I-CVI = 0,70). This pattern suggests that experts broadly recognized the conceptual value of most constructs, while expressing lower consensus about a limited number of constructs being central at this point.

Essentiality ratings

Essentiality evaluation provided a more selective view of the construct pool by distinguishing what is important from what is strictly essential for a parsimonious core model. More specifically, only a small number of constructs reached strong essentiality according to CVR. Two constructs emerged as most strongly supported as essential, with CVR values of 0,80 and 0,60, indicating that 9/10 and 6/10 experts, respectively, rated them as essential. One additional construct achieved a borderline essentiality score (CVR = 0,40, 7/10 experts rated it as essential). For most of the remaining constructs, CVR values ranged from 0,20 to -0,60, indicating that experts more often viewed them as useful but not essential, rather than core requirements of a minimal model.

An important outcome of the assessment is that these essentiality results did not imply rejection of the lower CVR constructs since the number of “not essential” responses was low.

This means that reduced CVR was often driven by experts selecting intermediate judgment rather than dismissing constructs altogether.

Clarity of the definitions

The definitions achieved acceptable clarity. Most ICV-I values were between 0,70 and 0,90. This shows that 7 to 9 of 10 experts considered the definitions sufficiently clear. The highest clarity agreement (I-CVI = 0,90) was observed for several central constructs, reflecting strong expert consensus on their conceptual articulation. The definitions that received comparatively lower clarity agreement (I-CVI 0,60, 6 of 10 experts rated them as clear) were selected for revision, since this could indicate that, although experts found them understandable, ambiguity or definition overlap may exist.

Additional candidate constructs evaluation

Apart from the main construct pool, experts were also asked to evaluate a set of additional candidate constructs that emerged from the literature. Each construct should be considered for exclusion, retained as part of an extended model, or included in the core model to understand how experts viewed the potential value of additional explanatory variables beyond the initial core.

The results show that expert preferences regarding the additional candidate constructs were generally conservative. Most constructs received relatively low support for inclusion as core candidates, and the majority of the responses were distributed between “exclude” and extended model only”. This indicates that the candidate constructs were not considered central to our goal of measuring acceptance and trust in AI-enabled deliberation platforms by experts.

Qualitative feedback (survey comments and focus group)

Qualitative comments provided deeper insight into how experts interpreted the constructs and how they believed the model should be refined in later steps. More specifically, several experts expressed concerns about conceptually close constructs and the context-dependent meanings of some constructs in deliberation settings (e.g., effort could be a barrier as well as an inherent part of meaningful deliberation). Experts also emphasized the need to avoid ambiguity around the “object” being evaluated, especially when constructs refer simultaneously to technology, the platform, and political institutions. Other feedback also suggested that clearer distinctions between system-level trust and institution-level trust may be needed.

A number of experts additionally raised the issue of causal direction in the broader model framing, noting that certain constructs may be interpreted as outcomes rather than antecedents depending on the structure of the theoretical model, and some experts proposed additional themes that may be important for AI-enabled deliberation contexts, i.e., constructs that related to governance and legitimacy expectations around AI systems. Finally, experts also highlighted that AI-enabled deliberation platforms may differ substantially across implementations, an issue that raises questions of how broadly the model generalizes and whether platform-specific design assumptions should be made more explicit.

Before round two of expert evaluation, we refined the constructs, their facets, and their items. Table 9 presents the main constructs and their facets, and Table 10 presents the items.

Table 7. Constructs and their facets definitions

	Construct Name	Construct Definition	Facet	Facet Definition
1	Behavioral Intention (BI)	The strength of a person's intention to use the AI-enabled deliberation system in the near future.	-	-
2	Attitude (ATT)	The extent to which an individual holds a positive evaluation (appraisal) of using the AI-enabled deliberation platform for participating in deliberation.	-	-
3	Performance Expectancy (PE)	The extent to which a user believes that using the AI-enabled deliberation platform improves the effectiveness and quality of their participation in deliberation (e.g., understanding issues, forming arguments, contributing useful input).	-	-
4	Effort Expectancy (EE)	The degree to which a person perceives that they must exert mental or physical effort to use the AI-enabled deliberation system.	-	-
5	Trust in the AI-enabled platform (TS)	Confidence that the AI-enabled deliberation platform (including its AI components and outputs) is reliable and can be relied on, and that it operates in an ethically appropriate manner.	AI output trust (AIT)	Confidence that the AI-generated outputs are trustworthy and can be relied on.
			Value Alignment (VA)	The alignment of AI's values and ethics with human values and societal norms.
6	Trust in the Government (TG)	The degree of citizens' confidence in the honesty, competence	Government truthfulness (GTR)	Belief in sincere political will to use deliberations

	Construct Name	Construct Definition	Facet	Facet Definition
		and commitment of government to act in the interests of the community, especially in managing deliberations and using their results.		genuinely (not symbolically).
			Procedural justice (PJ)	Perceived fairness, consistency, and impartiality of the procedures and rules governing how AI-enabled systems are implemented and used.
7	Perceived Risk (PR)	Perception that using the AI-enabled deliberation system involves potential negative consequences, such as privacy violations, security breaches, biased or harmful outputs, or reputational and ethical harms.	Privacy & Security Risk (RS)	The perceived possibility that using the platform could lead to unauthorized access, misuse, or exposure of one's personal data (e.g., privacy loss, data breaches).
			Ethical Risk (ETH)	The perceived possibility that using the platform could result in morally unacceptable or unfair outcomes (e.g., violations of fairness, respect, or equal treatment).
			Reputational Risk (RR)	The perceived possibility that participating on the platform could harm one's social standing or reputation (e.g., negative judgment, criticism, or unwanted attention).
			Bias/harm Risk (BH)	The perceived possibility that the platform's AI could generate biased, harmful, or misleading outputs that negatively affect the deliberation (e.g., misrepresenting views or

	Construct Name	Construct Definition	Facet	Facet Definition
				disadvantaging groups).
8	Knowledge quality (KQ)	Perceived accuracy, completeness, relevance, timeliness, clarity, organisation, and balance of the information and knowledge provided by the system to support citizens' understanding and participation in deliberations.	Accuracy & Balance (AB)	The extent to which the information provided for the deliberation is correct and impartial (not favoring one viewpoint).
			Relevance & Support (RS)	The extent to which the information is relevant to the deliberation topic and helps users understand the issue and participate effectively.
			Accessibility & Timeliness (ATI)	The extent to which the information is easy to understand and available at the right time for participation.
9	Facilitating Conditions (FC)	The extent to which a user believes that the resources, access, and support needed to use the platform are available (e.g., devices/internet access, guidance, help, and organizational support).	Ubiquitous connectivity (C)	Perception that the system is accessible anywhere and anytime through available networks/devices.
10	Participation Efficacy (PEFF)	The extent to which a user believes in their capability to effectively participate in deliberations (knowledgeable & qualified) and believes that the participation through the AI-enabled deliberation platform will be considered and will influence decisions or collective understanding.	Participation Self-Efficacy (SE)	Belief in one's capability/knowledge to contribute meaningfully.
			Empowerment (E)	Feelings that, through the system, citizens influence the decisions made by the government.
			Perceived Outcome (OU)	Belief that contributions made through the system are actually taken into account and can influence decisions or

	Construct Name	Construct Definition	Facet	Facet Definition
				collective understanding.
11	Civic Orientation (CO)	Underlying orientation towards civic and political engagement, including interest in public affairs and a sense of civic duty.	Community commitment (CC)	Desire to help improve one's community and take responsibility for its common good.
			Altruism (A)	Prosocial motivation to act for the benefit of others or the wider public, not just oneself.
			Community ownership (CO)	Sense of psychological ownership of the city/community (feeling like an owner who should not ignore what happens there).
12	Digital & AI capability (DAIC)	A person's overall capacity to use digital technologies and AI-enabled systems, including confidence, experience and knowledge.	Computer self-efficacy (CSE)	Belief in one's own ability to use digital technologies successfully.
			Familiarity (F)	Prior experience with similar tools and systems.
			AI literacy (AIL)	Self-perceived understanding of what AI is, what it can and cannot do, and how it works in broad terms.
13	Process & Communication Quality (PCQ)	The extent to which the platform supports a well-structured and smooth deliberation process and provides clear, responsive, and respectful interaction and feedback during participation.	Process quality (PQ)	How well the system runs the deliberative process.
			Communication quality (CQ)	Perception that the platform (and its AI components) provides clear, respectful, and responsive interaction and feedback during participation.

	Construct Name	Construct Definition	Facet	Facet Definition
14	AI output quality (AIQ)	Perceived accuracy, relevance, and correctness of AI-generated content within the AI-enabled deliberation platform.	-	-
15	Hedonic Motivation (HM)	The degree to which "the activity of using the AI-enabled deliberation platform is perceived as pleasurable in itself, apart from any performance consequences arising from using the platform".	Flow experience (F)	A state of deep absorption and concentration while using the system, where time passes quickly, and the activity feels intrinsically rewarding.
			Perceived novelty value (N)	Perceived newness/uniqueness of using the system compared to familiar ways to participate.
16	Social Influence (SI)	The extent to which a person perceives important that others and the wider community shape their use of the AI-enabled deliberation platform through social expectations (normative pressure) and social status/image considerations.	Normative influence (NI)	The perceived social pressure from important others (e.g., family, friends, community leaders) to use the AI-enabled deliberation platform.
			Image (I)	The degree to which the use of an innovation is perceived to enhance one's image or status in one's social system

Table 8. Items per construct (In parentheses, the target construct or facet of the item is presented)

Item	Item
BI1. I intend to use the AI-enabled deliberation platform in future deliberations. (BI)	FC3: I have the resources (e.g., device and internet access) necessary to use the AI-enabled deliberation platform. (Facilitating conditions)
BI2. I predict that I will use the AI-enabled deliberation platform in future deliberations. (BI)	FCC1: The AI-enabled deliberation platform is accessible whenever I need it (Ubiquitous connectivity)

Item	Item
BI3: I plan to use the AI-enabled deliberation platform in the near future. (BI)	FCC2: The AI-enabled deliberation platform worked reliably with the internet connection I normally use. (Ubiquitous connectivity)
ATT1: Using the AI-enabled deliberation platform is a good idea. (ATT)	PEFFSE1: I believe I can provide valuable ideas, opinions, and rational perspectives related to community affairs. (Participation Efficacy)
ATT2: Using the AI-enabled deliberation platform is a wise idea. (ATT)	PEFFSE2: I have a pretty good knowledge and good understanding about the important issues my community faces. (Participation Efficacy)
ATT3: Overall, I like the idea of using the AI-enabled deliberation platform. (ATT)	PEFFE1: I believe my contributions on the AI-enabled deliberation platform can make a meaningful difference to decisions or collective understanding. (Empowerment)
PE1: Using the AI-enabled deliberation platform enables me to participate in deliberations more efficiently. (PE)	PEFFE2: Through this platform, I feel more empowered to influence public discussions about community issues. (Empowerment)
PE2: Using the AI-enabled deliberation platform makes it easier for me to contribute to deliberations. (PE)	PEFFOU1: I believe my contributions to the AI-enabled deliberation platform will be taken into account. (Perceived Outcome)
PE3: Using the AI-enabled deliberation platform enhances my effectiveness in participating in deliberations. (PE)	PEFFOU2: I believe decision-makers will seriously consider citizens' contributions made through the AI-enabled deliberation platform. (Perceived outcome)
PE4: I find the AI-enabled deliberation platform useful for participating in deliberations. (PE)	CO1: I feel a personal responsibility to engage in issues that affect my community. (Civic orientation)
EE1: I find the AI-enabled deliberation platform easy to use. (EE)	CO2: Overall, I am motivated to contribute to my community's public affairs when I have the opportunity. (Civic orientation)
EE2: Learning to use the AI-enabled deliberation platform is easy for me. (EE)	COCC1: I feel responsible for contributing to solving problems in my community. (Community commitment)
EE3: I find it easy to do what I want to do on the AI-enabled deliberation platform. (EE)	COCC2: I feel a responsibility to get involved in issues that affect my community. (Community commitment)
TS1: Overall, I trust the AI-enabled deliberation platform. (Trust in the system)	COA1: I feel happy to support other participants in the community to solve their problems through deliberation. (Altruism)
TS2: Overall, I can rely on the AI-enabled deliberation platform. (Trust in the system)	COA2: I am willing to help other participants in the deliberations community (Altruism)

Item	Item
TSAIT1: I trust the AI outputs when using the AI-enabled deliberation platform. (AI Output Trust)	COCO1: I think I should not ignore what happens in my community. (Community ownership)
TSAIT2: I can rely on the AI-generated outputs provided by the platform. (AI Output Trust)	COCO2: I feel responsible for my community's future. (Community ownership)
TSVA1: I trust the AI-enabled deliberation platform to operate ethically. (Value Alignment)	DAICCSE1: I feel confident when utilizing digital technologies, even when no one is there for assistance. (Self-efficacy)
TSVA2: I think the AI-enabled deliberation platform follows appropriate ethical guidelines for AI use. (Value Alignment)	DAICCSE2: I have sufficient skills to use digital technologies. (Self-efficacy)
TG1: The government of our community is reliable. (Trust in the Government)	DAICAIL1: I have a basic understanding of what AI systems can and cannot do. (AI literacy)
TG2: In my opinion, the government defends the interests of its citizens. (Trust in the Government)	DAICAIL2: I know that AI outputs are not always correct. (AI literacy)
TGGTR1: I believe the local government genuinely wants to consult citizens through this platform. (Government truthfulness)	DAICF1: I already know similar platforms. (Familiarity)
TGGTR2: I believe the local government is open to discussion with citizens to reach shared decisions. (Government truthfulness)	DAICF2: I have already used similar platforms. (Familiarity)
TGPJ1: The government makes decisions in fair ways. (Procedural Justice)	PCQPQ1: The steps of the deliberation process on the AI-enabled deliberation platform are clear and easy to follow. (Process quality)
TGPJ2: The government's rules are applied consistently to all citizens. (Procedural Justice)	PCQPQ2: The deliberation process on the AI-enabled deliberation platform is well organised and runs smoothly. (Process quality)
PRRS1: Using the AI-enabled deliberation platform could have negative consequences for me in terms of my privacy or data security. (Privacy and Security Risk)	PCQCQ1: The AI-enabled deliberation platform provides timely and helpful feedback or responses during participation. (Communication quality)
PRRS2: I am concerned that using the platform could compromise my privacy or data security. (Privacy and Security Risk)	PCQCQ2: Communication on the AI-enabled deliberation platform is clear and respectful. (Communication quality)
PRE1: Using the AI-enabled deliberation platform could conflict with my values (e.g., fairness and respectful treatment of participants). (Ethical risk)	AIQ1: I think the AI-generated outputs from the platform are correct most of the time. (AI Output Quality)

Item	Item
PRE2: I am concerned that using the platform could lead to unethical outcomes (e.g., unfair treatment of certain views or groups). (Ethical risk)	AIQ2: The AI-generated outputs of the platform are accurate. (AI Output Quality)
PRRR1: Using the AI-enabled deliberation platform could harm my image. (Reputational risk)	AIQ3: AI outputs were relevant/useful for the deliberation. (AI Output Quality)
PRRR2: I worry that participating on the platform could expose me to criticism or negative attention. (Reputational risk)	HM1: The use of the AI-enabled deliberation platform is fun. (Hedonic Motivation)
PRBH1: I am concerned that the AI in the platform could produce biased or harmful outputs that affect the deliberation. (Bias/harm risk)	HM2: I feel excited about using the AI-enabled deliberation platform. (Hedonic Motivation)
PRBH2: I am concerned that the AI in the platform could distort or misrepresent participants' views. (Bias/harm risk)	HMF1: I lose track of time while using the AI-enabled deliberation platform. (Flow)
KQAB1: Information concerning the deliberation is accurate. (Accuracy & Balance)	HMF2: I am fully absorbed in what I am doing while using the AI-enabled deliberation platform. (Flow)
KQAB2: Information about the deliberation is balanced and does not favour one viewpoint. (Accuracy & Balance)	HMN1: Using the AI-enabled deliberation platform feels new and different compared to other ways I participate. (Novelty value)
KQRS1: The information provided on the platform was relevant to the deliberation topic and its goals. (Relevance & Support)	HMN2: I find the AI-enabled deliberation platform interesting because it offers a new way to participate. (Novelty value)
KQRS2: Information concerning the deliberation supported my needs for understanding the issue and participating in the deliberation. (Relevance & Support)	SIN1: People who influence my behavior think that I should use the AI-enabled deliberation system. (Social Influence)
KQATI1: Information about deliberations is announced to citizens on time. (Accessibility & Timeliness)	SIN2: People who are important to me think that I should use the AI-enabled deliberation system. (Social Influence)
KQATI2: Information concerning the deliberation is easy to understand. (Accessibility & Timeliness)	SII1: People in my community who use the AI-enabled deliberation platform have more prestige than those who do not. (Image)
FC1: Clear instructions concerning the AI-enabled deliberation platform were available to me. (Facilitating Conditions)	SII2: People in my community who use the AI-enabled deliberation platform have a high profile. (Image)
FC2: A specific person (or support service) is available for assistance with the difficulties I face in the AI-enabled deliberation platform. (Facilitating Conditions)	

For the second round of expert evaluations, to avoid overloading experts and ensure careful, consistent evaluation, we created four versions of the questionnaire, each containing approximately 8 constructs and their items. In total, we aim to collect 6 expert responses per construct, since each construct is represented in two versions. In total, we had 12 answers. From these answers, one expert was asked to complete two questionnaires that did not overlap in their constructs. One new expert from the consortium who did not participate in the first round was asked to complete a questionnaire. The results of the evaluation are presented below.

Facet fit

Facet to construct fit was high across the responses, with an average I-CVI = 0,87, indicating strong expert convergence that the proposed facet structure was conceptually appropriate. Furthermore, because two responses exhibited a possibility of straight lining patterns, an additional robustness summary was computed by excluding these ratings where occurred. In the adjusted analysis, the new I-CVI remained high (0,83), showing that the overall pattern of facet fit was robust and not driven only by the possible straight lining responses. These findings provide strong enough support for conceptual alignment between the proposed facets and their respective constructs, while also highlighting a small number of facets with comparatively weaker agreement.

Item to construct/facet fit

Item to construct/facet fit was generally high (average I-CVI = 0,80), indicating that experts considered the items to be conceptually aligned with their intended measurement targets. In total, 54 items achieved strong target fit (I-CVI \geq 0,83), 16 items achieved borderline range (I-CIV from 0,67 to less than 0,83), and 11 items achieved weaker agreement (I-CVI $<$ 0,67). In an adjusted I-CVI, where the possible straight lining answers were removed, the I-CVI was equal to 0,76. This indicates that overall, the results remained consistent. These findings suggest strong initial evidence that most items demonstrate appropriate fit, while a subset needs refinement.

Item clarity

The clarity of the items, based on expert ratings, was high overall, with an average I-CVI of 0,83, indicating that most items were clear. In total, 57 items showed strong clarity (I-CVI \geq 0,83), 13 items were identified as borderline (I-CVI from 0,67 to less than 0,83), and 11 items showed weak clarity agreement (I-CVI $<$ 0,76). The findings suggest that while the overall instrument is largely understandable as written, some items need refinement to reduce ambiguity or improve accessibility for non-expert respondents.

Qualitative feedback

Apart from the quantitative feedback, we also had several comments. In these comments, experts highlighted some redundancy and overlaps between items in some cases, the need for facet boundaries refinement (e.g., risk related facets may overlap), terminological precision, and vague wording (e.g., phrases like “most of the time”), technically subtle distinctions that citizens may not easily understand (e.g., correctness vs accuracy), and ambiguous labels (e.g., “image”). Linguistic standardization across language versions was also noted, about inconsistencies in tense and phrasing in translated items.

Regarding usability: The usability evaluation methods identified in D1.1 will be used at a later stage of the project to evaluate the AI-enabled deliberation platform's usability.

An example of the ten-item SUS questionnaire (5-point Likert-scale) adapted to our context¹⁷ is the following:

- I think that I would like to use the AI-enabled deliberation platform frequently.
- I found the AI-enabled deliberation platform unnecessarily complex.
- I thought the AI-enabled deliberation platform was easy to use.
- I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this AI-enabled deliberation platform.
- I found the various functions in this AI-enabled deliberation platform were well integrated.
- I thought there was too much inconsistency in this AI-enabled deliberation platform.
- I would imagine that most people would learn to use this AI-enabled deliberation platform very quickly.
- I found the AI-enabled deliberation platform very cumbersome to use.
- I felt very confident using the AI-enabled deliberation platform.
- I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this AI-enabled deliberation platform.

PENDING EC APPROVAL

¹⁷ <https://www.surveylab.com/blog/system-usability-scale-sus/>

5. Discussion and feedback for next sprints

5.1. Lessons learned per pilot

This section presents the main lessons learned by the pilots in the 1st sprint that will act as a basis for the 2nd sprint.

Greek Pilot: (i) Greek language performance is critical for tool selection. Tools that perform well in English may exhibit significant degradation with Greek content. Language compliance must be a threshold requirement. (ii) Multi-stage moderation pipelines outperform single-model approaches. The Detoxify → LlamaGuard → LLM configuration achieved the lowest error rate and demonstrated more stable detection across harm categories. (iii) Summarisation shows near-term operational value. Claude 4 Sonnet produced topic-specific, well-structured summaries that captured key themes including majority/minority viewpoints and concrete proposals. The main limitation was the lack of quantitative indicators (e.g., frequency of themes) that would enhance reporting utility. (iv) Argument extraction remains the weakest capability. While Claude demonstrated relatively stronger performance for Greek-language argument extraction with clear structure and policy-ready output, the functionality across tools remains insufficiently reliable for automated use. Human oversight is essential, and outputs should be treated as supporting material rather than authoritative records. (v) Historical data corpus provides valuable validation resources. The extensive archive of past consultations enables systematic testing and comparison of AI outputs against human-generated reports, supporting iterative improvement of tools before live deployment. (vi) Human oversight must remain central. Consistent with both legal requirements and ethical principles, AI tools should function as supporting material for facilitators and administrators rather than as autonomous decision-makers. This positioning also helps manage stakeholder expectations and build trust in the technology.

International Pilot: Based on the initial observation that neither the LLMs nor the Argument Mining tools tested so far appear to be sufficiently mature (in their current forms) to make an immediate contribution to the International Pilot, potential next steps might include: (1) to use the outputs of the LLMs as the inputs to the Argument Mining tools (to explore whether the combination of their potentially complementary strengths helps to elicit more effective outputs), and (2) to investigate the extent to which iterative refinements to LLM prompts can enhance the accuracy, comprehensiveness, and structural complexity of the LLM outputs. Opening the (currently) private long covid deliberation graph to public view will be an important next step to building engagement with the long covid stakeholders in, and across, the subsequent sprints.

Italian Pilot: Based on the first sprint and the past deliberative experiences of AAIT, several improvements can be introduced in the next sprints. In the pre-deliberation phase, the support in agenda setting and information structuring provided by AI will be crucial to help minimise the degree to which the pre-deliberation phase remains particularly demanding in terms of time, coordination, and cognitive load. The AI functionalities can support summarisation, argument extraction, audio-video materials. During deliberation, to reduce moderation effort, especially in managing turn-taking, synthesising inputs, and maintaining focus, the AI functionalities can help clusterization and discussion flows (emphasising agreement and disagreement), improving the highlighting of nuances and tones. The AI integration could support note-taking and real-time synthesis tools, combined with

facilitation. Transparency around how inputs are captured and processed is critical and should be guaranteed to participant trust building. In the post-deliberation phase, improvements should focus on faster, more transparent AI-assisted synthesis, coupled with structured human validation. Another point is that timely feedback to participants should be ensured. Overall, the next sprint should prioritise usability, clarity, transparency (including traceability) across all phases, avoiding introducing additional complexity.

German Pilot: Based on the experience from CBAM's first sprint, the next sprint should place greater emphasis on earlier and more deliberate process planning, as the evaluation showed that tool performance is strongly shaped by the underlying deliberation lifecycle. Clearer upfront definitions of use cases and evaluation criteria are needed to better distinguish between functional limitations and mismatches with intended purposes. In addition, the participant base should be expanded and diversified to better reflect real-world deliberative dynamics, moving beyond simulated roles and small, homogeneous groups. Tool testing should combine re-evaluation of existing solutions with the inclusion of new tools, while exploring more systematic interaction between standalone systems and existing platforms. Finally, stronger feedback loops for participants should be established to improve transparency, trust, and the practical relevance of the evaluation outcomes.

5.2. Lessons learned per WP2–WP5 components

This section reports the main lessons learned by WP in the 1st sprint that will act as a basis for the 2nd sprint.

5.2.1. Lessons learned for AI-enabled Deliberation processes (WP2)

Overall, respondents received the first draft positively: all aggregated scores were above the neutral midpoint (3/5), suggesting that the guideline's main structure and logic are understandable and meaningful to users. In particular, comprehensibility was rated highest for the pre-deliberation stage and scaling mechanisms (both 4.28/5).

At the same time, two areas were consistently identified as weaker (though still positive): the **perceived usefulness of the matrix** (3.53/5) and the **clarity of socio-technical challenges** (3.66/5).

Across open comments, the feedback clustered into three recurring improvement needs.

1. Several partners highlighted **format and accessibility issues** (missing navigation elements such as clear headings/numbering, and language that felt too dense for practitioner audiences), which can reduce uptake even when the content is solid.
2. Respondents pointed to an “**operationalisation gap**”: it was sometimes hard to translate principles and stages into concrete design decisions. Multiple organisations asked for more applied examples, pre-filled matrices/templates, and concrete AI tool references, so the guideline can be used more directly in real planning work.
3. Feedback indicated that some **socio-technical risks** and constraints **were missing** or under-specified and should be expanded.

Finally, one pilot (GFOSS) stood out as a critical outlier, largely due to a perceived mismatch between the guideline's assumptions and the legal–institutional constraints of their context (e.g., feasibility of small-group deliberation, facilitation requirements, platform conditions).

For each category, we also specify the corresponding next steps that WP2 will undertake in response to the feedback received.

i) **Format-related issues (structure, language, accessibility):** Some respondents reported difficulties related to document structure, readability, and accessibility, particularly for practitioners without a background in deliberative democracy. Others pointed out some ambiguities in terminology as distinction between inclusivity and plurality. Issues included missing navigational elements (e.g. table of contents, headings, numbering) and language perceived as overly dense or conceptual. These issues affect *comprehensibility* rather than substance. If practitioners struggle to navigate or interpret the document, even well-designed content risks being underused or misapplied.

WP2 next-step action: The second draft will introduce improved formatting (clear structure, headings, signposting) and revise the language to enhance practitioner accessibility, without diluting conceptual rigor.

ii) **Operationalisation gap (from principles to practice):** A general concern was the difficulty of translating the guideline into concrete action. Respondents asked for applied examples, pre-filled matrices, concrete AI tool references, and practitioner-oriented guidance.

WP2 next-step action: While the guideline was conceived to provide general guidance on upscaling processes based on ideal-typical designs, the revised version will extend this approach by addressing specific contextual circumstances. In particular, it will consider common features of existing participatory processes, such as synchronous versus asynchronous communication and institutional or legal boundaries. At the same time, it is recognised that not every participatory tool or platform can be deliberative *per se*. However, such processes may still benefit from one or more 'deliberative process treatments' that can enhance their overall quality. To address this operationalisation gap, the revised guidelines will therefore include the complete upscaling matrix, complemented with practical propositions of AI tools and design elements.

iii) **Socio-technical elements:** some respondents provided some important insight into missing socio-technical issues

WP2 next-step action: We recognize these limits and will complement the socio-technical table with the new suggestions.

In general, on the basis of these evaluations we will undertake the following actions:

- Reformatting the guideline
- Clarify existing ambiguous terminology and concepts
- Complement the current ideal-typical scenario (Part I) with a Deliberative treatment scenario (Part II) in which specific feature of participatory platforms will be discussed in light of concrete processes
- Integrate the full upscaling matrix with example of AI-tools, gamified and multimodal elements and processes.

At the same time, we would still like to make the boundaries of the guideline's mandate clear, acknowledging that certain requests, such as highly context-specific templates or institutional

reforms, fall outside the scope of a general and transferable deliberative framework proposed by WP2.

In conclusion, taken together, the findings confirm that the guidelines provide a solid foundation for supporting the upscaling of deliberative processes, while also offering clear, evidence-based directions for improvement. The revisions informed by this evaluation aim to strengthen the guidelines' practical usability without compromising their generality, conceptual coherence, or applicability across diverse democratic contexts.

5.2.2. Lessons learned for comprehensive framework (WP3)

The evaluation has identified at least four focal points for updates of the conditions and requirements. First, participants argued that the translation of conditions and requirements to practice will be the main challenge within WP3. Theoretically, the understanding of institutionalising AI-enabled mass deliberation as conveyed in the conditions and requirements is comprehensive. But participants identified several barriers in practice that will impede institutionalisation. As we will move from the 'what' of institutionalisation to the 'how' in the next sprint, we need to explore what changes in current organisational and administrative practices are needed to make way for institutionalisation. Concretely, we will first reformulate the conditions and requirements that scored worst on the criteria of feasibility and easiness of implementation.

Second, the subgoals (and related conditions and requirements) of institutionalisation need to be specified to deliberative practices that involve *AI applications to upscale engagement of deliberators*. This can be done in two ways. First, the current subgoals can be adapted. In that case, the implications of AI-enabled and mass deliberation need to be explored for both meaningful deliberation as well as sustainable integration. The other option is to formulate a third subgoal that represents the institutionalisation of the AI-enabled and mass characteristics of the kind of deliberation that the AI4Deliberation project focuses on. This third subgoal should focus on ensuring (deliberative) quality when integrating AI applications and guaranteeing all support needed for scaling up deliberative processes.

Third, a main theme identified by participants is the position of citizens and inherent power imbalances. Currently, our framing of institutionalisation pays too little attention to these aspects. To strengthen the position of citizens, we will detail the role of democracy and Rule of Law values in institutionalisation efforts. Accountability, empowerment, and other elements suggested by participants follow from these values. We will elaborate this theme within subgoal meaningful deliberation, more specifically, the fostering of democratic deliberative practices. Again, it is important to explore the implications for democracy and Rule of Law values when deliberative processes are upscaled using AI applications.

Finally, the subgoals, conditions, and requirements should emphasise more that institutionalisation is an (organisational) change process instead of a stable state that can be achieved. This can be done by elaborating on the role of cultural aspects in institutionalisation.

5.2.3. Lessons learned for AI tools (WP4)

Across the pilots, the first evaluation phase generated consistent and actionable feedback to guide improvements in WP4 and the AI toolkit for the second sprint.

A central cross-cutting requirement is **stronger grounding and output reliability**. In multiple pilots, evaluators noted that even when outputs were coherent and well-structured, they

could include hallucinated elements, structural mislabelling, or omissions of key discussion outcomes (e.g., failure to capture the closing vote). This points to the need for clearer constraints in prompting, tighter linkage between outputs and supporting evidence (e.g., traceable quotes or references to source segments), and explicit handling of uncertainty (e.g., flagging low-confidence extractions rather than presenting them as definitive).

A second recurring improvement area concerns **language compliance and multilingual robustness**. The Greek pilot highlighted that outputs delivered in English (or mixed-language artefacts) are not usable in an official consultation context, and similar language instability was observed elsewhere. For the next sprint, pilots recommend enforcing strict language settings end-to-end (input → processing → output), strengthening translation and language-detection safeguards, and preventing hybrid or corrupted terms in generated text. The translation benchmarking results further suggest that non-LLM translation components may offer more stable performance for specific language pairs, implying that the toolkit should remain flexible in selecting the most reliable component per language.

Functionality-Specific Feedback

For **summarisation**, pilots emphasized that a single, generic approach is insufficient, as the definition of quality depends strongly on the intended use of the output. Evaluators pointed to the need for multiple, explicitly defined modes tailored to different deliberative functions: summaries supporting *ongoing* deliberation should focus on accurately listing arguments, positions, and disagreements without evaluative framing, while *retrospective* outputs may legitimately emphasize sentiment, convergence, or consensus. To support these varied use cases, pilots requested better calibration of abstraction and length—avoiding the extremes of near-verbatim redundancy or overly generic synopses—along with the improved capture of deliberation dynamics (such as tone and the evolution of disagreement) and the optional inclusion of simple quantitative signals (e.g., frequency of themes) to aid reporting.

For **argument extraction/structuring**, feedback was more critical: across the pilots this was repeatedly identified as the weakest capability, struggling to distinguish arguments from remarks/attitudes, to assign stance reliably, and—particularly in the International Pilot—to reconstruct and interrelate arguments at a level suitable for downstream structured use. Pilots proposed the following actions for improvement for the LLM-based argument extraction:

- Focusing on refining the prompts used to generate outputs from the LLMs – as well as continuing to implement the latest versions of the models – to explore the degree to which it might be possible to increase the accuracy, comprehensiveness, and structural complexity of the LLM outputs.
- Models should prioritize the substantive content of arguments in relation to positions over semantic connotation or affective wording. Current tendencies to overreact to negative phrasing risk misclassifying stance and argument quality. A stronger focus on propositional structure and argumentative relevance would substantially improve reliability.
- Improve precision in argument extraction by clearly distinguishing arguments, examples, attitudes, and contextual remarks.

- Enhance formatting options (headings, bullet points, topic clustering) to make outputs immediately usable during live facilitation without extra post-processing.
- Increase robustness to noisy or imperfect transcripts, especially in handling metaphors, informal speech, or contradictory statements, which currently lead to misinterpretation.
- Improve coverage of deliberation dynamics, including explicit capture of disagreements, evolution of positions, and final outcomes (e.g., votes), which were often missing.

oAMF (Argument Mining) The 1st sprint has identified constructive pathways to further explore and refine the application of the Open Argument Mining Framework (oAMF). First, the pilot team plans to **collaborate closely with the University of Dundee** to investigate the optimal alignment between the tool's configuration, the sample texts, and the specific objectives of the International Pilot. This joint review will help determine if the preliminary observations from the first sprint were influenced by test-specific factors—such as corpus size or text type—and if broader experimentation might unlock the tool's full potential. Second, the project will **explore alternative integration scenarios** in which the distinct and potentially complementary strengths of argument mining and LLMs might be mutually-reinforcing.

For **moderation**, Pilots converged on the view that layered pipelines outperform standalone LLMs, yet the scope, transparency, and operational logic of moderation require significant expansion to be viable in deliberative settings. Beyond the standard detection of hate speech and threats, coverage must extend to include spam, advertisements, off-topic content, and language-specific profanity, specifically addressing identified gaps such as the "Greek profanity blind spot". Furthermore, systems should explicitly define how they address subtle deliberative disruptions—such as sarcasm, cynicism, or the rude undermining of others' arguments—which can be as damaging to discourse as overt abuse. To ensure these interventions are transparent and contestable, outputs should provide clear reason codes that distinguish between the "flagged content," the "recommended action," and the "explanatory rationale". Finally, it is critical to specify the post-flagging mechanism itself, clarifying whether content is removed automatically, routed to a human moderator, or returned to the participant for revision. Making these procedural choices explicit helps align models with clear normative standards and reduces ambiguity in evaluation.

ECHO and Transcript-Grounded Interaction Feedback on ECHO and transcript-grounded interaction highlighted clear opportunities to strengthen facilitator trust and operational usability. While transcription quality and the "ask/report" functions were viewed positively, the pilots identified specific requirements for the next iteration. Key recommendations include establishing clearer criteria to separate substantive deliberation content from process-oriented tool feedback and better surfacing behavioral dynamics without compromising neutrality. Furthermore, pilots called for refined rules regarding quote selection—specifically the treatment of inappropriate language—and strengthened anonymization safeguards. To support these improvements, there is a strong demand for transparency mechanisms, such as a short methodological note explaining how topics are clustered and content selected. Collectively, these inputs point toward a second sprint focus on usability features and governance safeguards (including language controls, transparency notes, and evidence links) alongside targeted model iteration

Translation. Current evaluations show that translation quality is language-dependent. While LLMs like Claude and LLaMA excelled in German and Italian, LibreTranslate proved better performance for Greek. A potential update is that the toolkit dynamically switches between LLMs and standard NMT based on the target language. But this will further be explored in next evaluation rounds. Regarding the evaluation metric, semantic-aware metrics (BERTScore) proved more reliable than lexical matching for evaluating the AI-generated translations.

Topic Modeling Results from the pilot evaluation showed that on-the-fly processing of the texts needs further improvement to derive better results regarding topic modelling. Therefore, for the evolution of the topic modelling task and the evaluation of the next phase, the need to proceed with more advanced topic extraction methods emerges. More specifically, the topic extraction task is scheduled to use more robust methods of identifying themes, by employing a vocabulary dataset and mapping themes to a non-volatile text corpus. This approach is expected to help with the eventual semantic clustering of a larger dataset of articles.

5.2.4. Lessons learned for (WP5)

In this deliverable, regarding the acceptance and trust model, we completed steps 1-5 of the corresponding methodology. The results derived to this point provide an evidence-based starting point for the measurement instrument and the model and offer a structured view of how acceptance and trust can be represented in this context.

At the same time, the findings presented here represent an early stage of the overall validation process. While expert evaluations provide strong support for the relevance and conceptual alignment of the proposed constructs, facets, and items, they also highlight areas that require refinement before citizen deployment. The next phase of the methodology will focus on refining different aspects of the measurement instrument and structuring an initial acceptance and trust model before citizen deployment.

PENDING APPROVAL

6. Conclusion

The current deliverable D5.1 aimed to present the foundational planning and initial operational results of the AI4Deliberation pilots for the "First Sprint" (M7-M15). The document was divided into two main parts respectively: Section 2 on pilots' planning and operation, and Sections 3 through 5 on the evaluation methodology and results. The outcomes presented here are based on the internal simulations, ground-truth benchmarking, and expert validations performed by the consortium to ensure the project's socio-technical infrastructure is ready for deployment.

Section 2 presented the detailed context and operational planning for the four pilot sites: the German pilot, the Greek pilot, the International pilot, and the Italian pilot. For documenting the pilots' details, a uniform structure based on the WP2 Design Matrix was used, mapping the current "AS-IS" deliberation processes against the envisioned "TO-BE" AI-enabled states. This section reported on the specific activities of the first sprint, where emphasis was placed on internal validation. Activities included role-play simulations (German and Italian pilots) and the curation of historical datasets (Greek and International pilots) to generate the necessary evidence for testing technical feasibility before engaging citizens.

Sections 3, 4, and 5 presented the project's agile evaluation strategy and the specific results of this first sprint. In specific, these sections described the methodology used to assess four key dimensions: the process guidelines (WP2), the institutional framework (WP3), the AI toolkit (WP4), and the acceptance/trust models (WP5). In this iteration, **consortium members** acted as the primary evaluators. Furthermore, the sprint worked for achieving Objective O5.1 by starting the work for the development of the Acceptance and Trust Model.

Following this, under Tasks T5.3 and T5.4 (M16-M21), the "Second Sprint" will be executed. The operational plans will be updated based on the feedback recorded here, shifting the focus from internal simulations to **small-scale pilots involving real citizens**. It is expected that this upcoming iteration will test the refined AI features. The results of these activities will be recorded and analysed in **Deliverable D5.2: Pilots plan, operation and evaluation – second sprint**, due in M21.

PENDING APPROVAL

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PENDING EC APPROVAL

Appendix A – AS-IS pilot Questionnaires

Greek Pilot

1. Basic Information

Type of deliberation: (e.g., public consultation, participatory budgeting, legislative crowdsourcing)

National deliberation on legislation for draft legislations

Other uses: public commenting policies, preliminary step for drafting legislation (not many during 2009-2019) for ministries (e.g., open-ended questions) – prior to drafting legislation.

What is the typical duration / frequency of deliberations?

2 weeks mas (official). Can be shortened/extended to +-1 week

In the frame of the project we may generously extend this duration in order to align with EU and OECD countries.

Which topics are generally discussed in deliberations?

Draft Laws on every possible legislation. ALL laws before entering into Parliament. Produce doc with result of the consultation

What is the typical participant size?

Operates 15.5 year

1175 consultations so far

Total number of comments 383250

Per deliberation the numbers vary depending on the theme: big range

2. Deliberation Process

How is the deliberation initiated? (e.g., by law, initiative of government, civil society request)

By law it is mandatory for all legislation. Legally mandated.

Each ministry is responsible for initiating the process for their laws ☑ moderate, approve, respond online in the platform (rare)

“General Secretariat for Parliamentary and Legislative issues” ☑ responsible for the setup

Which recruitment model best describes this pilot? (e.g., random selection, open self-selection ('anyone can sign up'), Invitation only)

Self-selection, open for everyone, no ID check. Only email provided for each comment (email is added per comment)

Are contributions anonymous or non-anonymous?

Both are applicable.

For each comment one can add their real name, pseudonym, or name of organisation.

Are participants offered an incentive? (e.g., honorarium, voucher, reimbursement)

No. Voluntary interest for engagement and policy

Is the process formally divided into stages? If yes, which stages? (e.g., Recruitment, Deliberative-rules presentation, ice-breaking, Factual information input (experts/evidence),

stakeholder input, Learning/quizzes / knowledge checks, Idea generation/proposal drafting, Discussion/deliberation, Decision-making / voting, Other)

Step 1: Government (ministry, General secretariat) publish law + explanatory materials (impact assessment report and feasibility report), open call (brief, typical) for comments

Step2: Commenting period 2 weeks. Comments need to be approved by the Ministry before going public

Step 3: The ministry creates a report

Step4: Report sent to Parliament

How flexible is the process? *(Briefly describe options for adapting stages or timing)*

Fixed by law

Flexibility only on duration +/-1 week in exceptional cases

Does deliberation take place in sub-groups? *(e.g., tables, breakout rooms, online clusters)?*

No. Everyone in the same platforms

What is the format of the deliberation? *(e.g., workshops, open discussion, facilitated discussion)*

Open discussion, asynchronous. No option to reply to comments.

No votes or other reactions.

Each comment needs to be approved by the moderator (ministry personnel).

What kind of output does the process produce, and what happens to it? *(e.g., full report, executive summary, policy binding decision, policy recommendation, impact assessment, agenda setting)*

Summary report created by the moderator – ministry. No official guidelines.

The comments may affect the draft law. The created report may include a reference to how the comments affected the draft law. It depends on the wording.

The report is part of the impact analysis of the draft law that enters the Parliament.

It depends on each ministry.

Are any game-based elements used? *If yes, briefly describe how*

No

Which concrete steps or tools do you use to upscale while maintaining quality (if any)? *(e.g., digital platform, regional hubs, AI moderation)*

Digital platform. No other (currently).

Previous years – email list to invite people and social media posts by ministries.

Is the quality of the deliberative process monitored? If yes, how? *(e.g., participant feedback, discourse monitoring, fact-check, deliberative indexes)*

Manual review by ministry officials. No systematic

Is the quality of the deliberative output monitored? If yes, how? *(e.g., manually reviewed by a subgroup of participants, experts review, AI/LLM-assisted review)?*

Manually reviewed and written.

3. Organisational, Legal, and Ethical Aspects

Who are the key stakeholders and what are their roles/responsibility?
(e.g., **Stakeholders:** coordinating authority, policy makers, civic groups, platform providers, researchers, technical support; **Roles:** initiator, moderator, facilitator, participant)

Coordinating authority: General Secretariat
 Policy makers, moderators, report creators: Individual ministries
 Platform provider: Ministry of Digital government (they offer Gloud to host opengov.gr), EKDAA is technically responsible
 GFOSS: basic stakeholder (Domain expertise and consulting)
 GRNET: procuring services for maintaining/upgrading, etc., opengov.gr
 Participants: citizens, civil society organisations, associations

Are there specific qualifications required for deliberation organisers? And what skills are expected/desired from participants?

The one who creates the report is somehow aware of the theme. But it depends.
 Very basic digital literacy for both.
 There may be some workshops/guidelines unofficial for deliberations organisers (moderation, report creation...)

What financial or other resources are needed to run the current process?

G-Cloud

Who owns and manages the data collected? (e.g., city IT department, external contractor, shared cloud repository)

Ministry of Digital Government

Does the collected data include personal data?

Yes, participant name (maybe), email (mandatory)

Are you re-using personal data collected 1) before the start of this project or 2) from another project for the AI4Deliberation project?

Yes, there are data.

We need to check what the participants consent to. The comments have CC licenses v4.0

Are there internal policies, formal regulations, or laws governing the process¹⁸?

Law 3261/2019 + amendments.

Regulation of the Parliament 87 paragraph 3

Code of

Terms of service

<https://www.opengov.gr/ministryofjustice/?p=17904#respond>

<https://www.opengov.gr/home/services/%CF%80%CE%BB%CE%B1%CE%AF%CF%83%CE%B9%CE%BF-%CE%B1%CF%81%CF%87%CF%8E%CE%BD-%CE%B4%CE%B7%CE%BC%CF%8C%CF%83%CE%B9%CE%B1->

¹⁸ The aim is to identify certain sector-specific regulation (for example in the field of healthcare, digital rights or internet governance), as opposed to very general legislation of personal data and fundamental rights.

[%CE%B7%CE%BB%CE%B5%CE%BA%CF%84%CF%81%CE%BF%CE%BD%CE%B9%CE%BA%CE%AE-%CE%B4%CE%B9](#)

What ethical or legal challenges have emerged, and how are they addressed? (e.g., GDPR compliance, such as informed consent and permission to re-use data; moderation bias, accessibility)

They have a consent form.

Is there a need for legal or policy changes to enable future AI integration? (e.g., data sharing permissions, procurement frameworks, trust guidelines)

It falls under the AI Act.

We need to check where the Greek pilot stands for the AI Act requirements.

Short answer: It depends, we need to check

Are there any training/educational materials for deliberators as well as moderators/facilitators?

Limited guidelines for deliberations.

4. Technical and Infrastructural Aspects

What platform or tools are used?

(e.g., Decidim, Consul, custom platform, email-based, none)

Multisite WordPress (every ministry has its own space/credentials)

Are there existing data for deliberations? If yes, indicate them.

Yes. They are publicly available as CSV.

What types of data are collected from the deliberation process?

(e.g., free-text comments, votes, demographic data, proposals, meeting notes)

Free-text comments, name, email, timestamp

In which language(s) is the data collected?

(e.g., Greek, English, German, Italian, multilingual)

Greek (mainly)

Where is the data stored, and how is it accessed?

(e.g., internal servers, third-party platform, no long-term storage)

GCloud (WordPress is hosted there)

Does the tool need to communicate with other systems? (e.g., for authentication)

No

What are the main technical challenges you currently face?

(e.g., data volume, multilingual input, lack of standard formats, outdated systems)

Manual moderation, large volume of participation (moderation, report, citizens as recipients of deliberation), limited analytical capabilities (summary, argument extraction, sentiment analysis etc.). No robust quality control. Limited interaction between people (e.g., discussion).

5. Reflections on Impact and Future Vision

What impact has the current deliberation process had so far? What is the current engagement (in numbers)?

(e.g., policy changes, increased engagement, trust building, media attention)

Updated draft laws (numbers?).

Impact unclear: how many laws were affected, and did it increase trust?

What are the most significant strengths of your current process?

(e.g., inclusiveness, transparency, simplicity, local relevance)

Political will (for the first years, because there was no legal mandate).

Legal mandate

Established process (15 years running)

Open-source foundation – no license needed to pay for

What are the most significant limitations or bottlenecks to scale this process?

(e.g., large volume of inputs, Cost/funding, recruitment, legal constraints, political support)

Manual processing. Resource-intensive (human effort).

Limited duration of consultation (Greece at the bottom of OECD) , low engagement, and response quality is limited.

How do you imagine AI could enhance your process in the future?

Comment clustering.

An assistant to help build meaningful deliberation processes

Argument mining/extraction

Reasoning associated with evidence

Summarisation

Moderation (check compliance of comments – language usage, raise flags)

An assistant for people to be exposed to facts to frame their comments.

What would you need to start using AI in your process?

(e.g., training, funding, trusted AI tools, legal clarification, community support)

Legal clarification – AI Act

Technical capacity

Plan to get acceptance from the stakeholders

Training plan

International Pilot

1. Basic Information

Type of deliberation: *(e.g., public consultation, participatory budgeting, legislative crowdsourcing)*

DebateGraph supports individual and collective deliberation about complex public policy topics. In the context of the AI4Deliberation project, DebateGraph is, perhaps, best conceived as providing a substrate to support formal deliberative processes rather than providing the formal deliberative process itself.

What is the typical duration/frequency of deliberations?

DebateGraph is designed to support continuous, cumulative, open-ended deliberative thought.

Which topics are generally discussed in deliberations?

Complex public policy topics with multiple intersecting dimensions (e.g., climate, global health challenges, nuclear policy, etc.)

What is the typical participant size?

In principle, an unlimited number of people can participate; in practice, DebateGraph's use follows a familiar pattern for other collaborative social media in which the vast majority of people are readers, a small minority are occasional/intermittent contributors, and small number of people (typically less than 10) act as the primary curators. As such, DebateGraph aims to capture and bring together in a single graph the views expressed by large numbers of people in other channels (rather than requiring those people to express their views directly through DebateGraph).

2. Deliberation Process

How is the deliberation initiated? (e.g., by law, initiative of government, or civil society request)

An informal, open and continuous process that begins with the creation of a starting node for a graph/map.

Which recruitment model best describes this pilot? (e.g., random selection, open self-selection ('anyone can sign up'), Invitation only)

Self-selection: anyone can sign up (requires login)

Are contributions anonymous or non-anonymous?

Contributors are asked to provide a first name, last name, and a valid email address when registering (which is necessary to contribute directly to the graph/map). Real names are usually entered but are not required; so, pseudonymous participation (under an assumed name/username) is an option for participants.

Are participants offered an incentive? (e.g., honorarium, voucher, reimbursement)

No (although DebateGraph is free to use – which is a form of incentive or at least an absence of a disincentive – and offers people a way to share and build on their thinking together openly and globally).

Is the process formally divided into stages? If yes, which stages? (e.g., Recruitment, Deliberative-rules presentation, ice-breaking, Factual information input (experts/evidence), stakeholder input, Learning/quizzes/knowledge checks, Idea generation/proposal drafting, Discussion/deliberation, Decision-making/voting, Other)

No: not by default (although, in principle, as part of a more formal deliberative framework, the process could be broken into different stages and include a form of voting). DebateGraph has also been used map the cumulative outputs from sequential in-person events.

How flexible is the process? (Briefly describe options for adapting stages or timing)

The formalism of the graph supports extremely flexible and detailed sensemaking – that can be applied in multiple ways across a wide range of contexts – but also entails a distinct way of structuring and presenting thought that can be experienced as a form of rigidity when first encountered.

Does deliberation take place in sub-groups? (e.g., tables, breakout rooms, online clusters)?

By default, the graph acts as an open, central repository for the whole group's thoughts. Sub-groups can also create and interlink separate graphs on any topic at any time.

What is the format of the deliberation? (e.g., workshops, open discussion, facilitated discussion)

Live, continuous evolution of the graph through new contributions (including adding new nodes, comments, citations, cross-links, and ratings, etc.)

What kind of output does the process produce, and what happens to it? (e.g., full report, executive summary, policy binding decision, policy recommendation, impact assessment, agenda setting)

The graph is its own output; a living document of the group's current reflections on the subject at hand.

Are any game-based elements used? If yes, briefly describe how

No (although the interface does include some elements of social signalling – e.g., displaying the most recent contributors and the numbers of contributions made by each participant).

Which concrete steps or tools do you use to upscale while maintaining quality (if any)? (e.g., digital platform, regional hubs, AI moderation)

No concrete steps (and the graphs readily scale to thousands of nodes).

Is the quality of the deliberative process monitored? If yes, how? (e.g., participant feedback, discourse monitoring, fact-check, deliberative indexes)

The quality of the deliberative process is monitored directly by contributors to the graph – it's an intrinsic part of the process.

Is the quality of the deliberative output monitored? If yes, how? (e.g., manually reviewed by a subgroup of participants, experts review, AI/LLM-assisted review)?

The quality of the deliberative output is monitored directly by contributors to the graph – it's an intrinsic part of the process.

3. Organisational, Legal, and Ethical Aspects

Who are the key stakeholders and what are their roles/responsibility?

(e.g., **Stakeholders:** coordinating authority, policy makers, civic groups, platform providers, researchers, technical support; **Roles:** initiator, moderator, facilitator, participant)

The creator of the graph has access to additional administrative/moderator features and can invite others to share in these responsibilities.

An important part of the ethos of the mapping process is to seek to identify and represent the perspectives of all stakeholders in the relevant policy issue (that forms the subject of the graph) fairly and in full.

Are there specific qualifications required for deliberation organisers? And what skills are expected/desired from participants?

No.

What financial or other resources are needed to run the current process?

DebateGraph is freely available for people to use; so, the primary resource necessary is the time to enact the process that DebateGraph enables.

Who owns and manages the data collected? (e.g., city IT department, external contractor, shared cloud repository)

The contributors of original content own their contributions (with different licensing options definable per map).

Thoughtgraph manages and maintains the data through the continued operation of DebateGraph.

Does the collected data include personal data?

The only information required on registration is: First name, Last Name, and a valid email address.

IP addresses and browser information are detected by the application as part of the ordinary operation of the site.

The free-form content that participants add to the graph may include personal information – e.g., political opinions – but only at their individual discretion.

Are you re-using personal data collected 1) before the start of this project or 2) from another project for the AI4Deliberation project?

No (only in the sense that some participants may have already registered with DebateGraph over the preceding years).

Are there internal policies, formal regulations, or laws governing the process¹⁹?

None specific to the process (beyond the Terms and Conditions, Privacy Policy and any relevant laws in the different jurisdictions).

What ethical or legal challenges have emerged, and how are they addressed? (e.g., GDPR compliance, such as informed consent and permission to re-use data; moderation bias, accessibility)

No specific issues have emerged to date.

Is there a need for legal or policy changes to enable future AI integration?

(e.g., data sharing permissions, procurement frameworks, trust guidelines)

This is unclear for now, contingent on future decisions within the project, and will be addressed immediately should any decisions introduce needs of this kind.

Are there any training/educational materials for deliberators as well as moderators/facilitators?

Yes: built into DebateGraph.

4. Technical and Infrastructural Aspects

What platform or tools are used?

(e.g., Decidim, Consul, custom platform, email-based, none)

DebateGraph

Are there existing data for deliberations? If yes, indicate them.

¹⁹ The aim is to identify certain sector-specific regulation (for example in the field of healthcare, digital rights or internet governance), as opposed to very general legislation of personal data and fundamental rights.

Yes (not sharable)

What types of data are collected from the deliberation process?

(e.g., free-text comments, votes, demographic data, proposals, meeting notes)

Text, comments, ratings, citations (including some source documents), the structure of the graph, etc. Not demographic data.

In which language(s) is the data collected?

(e.g., Greek, English, German, Italian, multilingual)

Primarily English – with no restriction on entering text in any language (although aspects of the interface are optimised for languages that are written right-to-left).

Where is the data stored, and how is it accessed?

(e.g., internal servers, third-party platform, no long-term storage)

A bare metal server dedicated to DebateGraph that is physically located in an IBM data centre in Dallas, Texas.

Periodic physical backups are also maintained in Australia.

Does the tool need to communicate with other systems? (e.g., for authentication)

No.

What are the main technical challenges you currently face?

(e.g., data volume, multilingual input, lack of standard formats, outdated systems)

The primary (socio-)technical challenge – as it has been from the outset – is to embed the ideal (abstract) form of deliberative dialogue that the graph enables into the pragmatic decision-making processes of our societies.

5. Reflections on Impact and Future Vision

What impact has the current deliberation process had so far? What is the current engagement (in numbers)?

(e.g., policy changes, increased engagement, trust building, media attention)

DebateGraph's maps have been featured and discussed in national and international TV, Radio and newspapers, and used in multiple government contexts (although not yet embedded in the formal decision-making processes). More recently, DebateGraph has focused on behind-the-scenes projects with NGOs, companies, and branches of government (where the private work has been closer to the ongoing sense-making processes of those organisations).

What are the most significant strengths of your current process?

(e.g., inclusiveness, transparency, simplicity, local relevance)

The graph offers the ability to capture and represent all the ideas, perspectives, and evidence that anyone judges salient to the deliberation at hand in a transparent, continuously evolving deliberative map that anyone can add to at any time.

What are the most significant limitations or bottlenecks to scale this process?

(e.g., large volume of inputs, Cost/funding, recruitment, legal constraints, political support)

The process of creating, exploring and interpreting the graph requires a significant commitment of time and attention.

How do you imagine AI could enhance your process in the future?

We are keen to explore the degree to which AI may have the potential to help (1) speed the process of creation of the graph and (2) ease the process of interpretation of the graph (with no attendant sacrifice in quality).

What would you need to start using AI in your process?

(e.g., training, funding, trusted AI tools, legal clarification, community support)

The work in WP4 and WP5 already offers the potential basis for initial experiments in this direction.

Italian Pilot**1. Basic Information**

Type of deliberation: *(e.g., public consultation, participatory budgeting, legislative crowdsourcing)*

Policy-lab (participatory public process design) at the local level, but also in some cases national/regional.

What is the typical duration/frequency of deliberations?

Depend on case: on average, 3-4 months (a series of online/offline meetings in this period). Each meeting has a duration of 2-3 hours, depending on the agenda.

Which topics are generally discussed in deliberations?

Suggestion to public policies, rules and regulations related to, e.g., public (now, for example, accessibility of registry services) and welfare services, public commons, and disaster risk management.

What is the typical participant size?

30 – 400 in total (30-60 per meeting, max 100 per meeting)

2. Deliberation Process

How is the deliberation initiated? *(e.g., by law, initiative of government, or civil society request)*

Civil society request (not an official request, based on open discussions within the civil society network, co-creation process, assessment need).

Which recruitment model best describes this pilot? *(e.g., random selection, open self-selection ('anyone can sign up'), Invitation only)*

Outreach activity -> Self-selection and invitation (e.g., from a list of people from previous activities). For self-selection: newsletter, relevant newsletters or relevant networks, meetings.

No restrictions on participants' profiles. Try to balance (step-by-step engagement to reach balance) with an intersectional approach.

The only restriction is the number, in particular for live meetings (not exceeding a max number).

Are contributions anonymous or non-anonymous?

Non-anonymous (physical meetings).

The consent form is given. The output report (public) is anonymous; it summarises the process outcomes without specifying the contribution of the participants. The list of people who took part in the process may or may not be made public.

Are participants offered an incentive? (e.g., honorarium, voucher, reimbursement)

In some cases, transport and food are covered. Some small gadgets are gifted.

In future: vouchers/gift card could be given to participants to ensure participation.

Is the process formally divided into stages? If yes, which stages? (e.g., Recruitment, Deliberative-rules presentation, ice-breaking, Factual information input (experts/evidence), stakeholder input, Learning/quizzes/knowledge checks, Idea generation/proposal drafting, Discussion/deliberation, Decision-making/voting, Other)

Preparation and Recruitment

Information (to provide to participants about the deliberation topic)

Dialogue, deliberation and decision

Deliver

Deliberation process:

Many workshops (mainly physical). Each is divided into group work and plenary moments. In general, for some sessions, participants are divided into smaller groups. Each group create some outputs and then presents them in plenary. A final report merges the recs per workshop.

After each meeting, the meeting report can be discussed online with participants' comments/inputs/feedback.

Depending on the process, the next workshops may discuss the same or other relevant topics.

At the end, all reports are merged to produce the final report.

Merge/prioritisation of recommendations to create a report → proposal for policy change.

How flexible is the process? (Briefly describe options for adapting stages or timing)

Quite flexible depending on the participant's needs (e.g., timing, place...)

Flexible for the process, and within a meeting.

Various methodologies implemented during the whole process e within meetings.

Does deliberation take place in sub-groups? (e.g., tables, breakout rooms, online clusters)?

Two levels of grouping:

Workshop

Tables within the workshop

Breakout rooms in online meetings

What is the format of the deliberation? (e.g., workshops, open discussion, facilitated discussion)

Workshops with facilitated discussion;

Open discussion at the end of the session or meeting (plenary);

Online comments about the report or document (during the process).

What kind of output does the process produce, and what happens to it? (e.g., full report, executive summary, policy binding decision, policy recommendation, impact assessment, agenda setting)

Full report of policy recommendations.

OR recommendations on how to improve, e.g., services

Are any game-based elements used? If yes, briefly describe how

Ice-breaking → cards/images to inspire participants, role playing

Which concrete steps or tools do you use to upscale while maintaining quality (if any)? (e.g., digital platform, regional hubs, AI moderation)

Digital platform to discuss intermediate reports/documents or pre-final report.

Need to upscale within the project e.g., AI moderation.

Is the quality of the deliberative process monitored? If yes, how? (e.g., participant feedback, discourse monitoring, fact-check, deliberative indexes)

MEAL (Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability and Learning) methodology to monitor and evaluate the ongoing process and output. A specific unit in AAIT is responsible for this.

People/participants leave feedback before, during and after the process.

Direct observation to enable fair participation, deliberation, quality and effect of sessions.

In general, a dedicated person is entrusted with the task of producing the report both within the group work sessions and in plenary.

Is the quality of the deliberative output monitored? If yes, how? (e.g., manually reviewed by a subgroup of participants, expert review, AI/LLM-assisted review)?

Through MEAL tools.

Participants' comments/feedback on the final report → a way of quality check.

3. Organisational, Legal, and Ethical Aspects

Who are the key stakeholders and what are their roles/responsibility?

(e.g., **Stakeholders:** coordinating authority, policy makers, civic groups, platform providers, researchers, technical support; **Roles:** initiator, moderator, facilitator, participant)

Coordinators, facilitators/moderators → AAIT

Participants → people, civic groups...

External experts or relevant stakeholders → to inform about the topic or share experiences/actions

Policy makers → participants or recommendation recipients

Are there specific qualifications required for deliberation organisers? And what skills are expected/desired from participants?

No for participants. In general, an attempt is made to establish criteria prior to the process to ensure that it has a fair and appropriate representation.

Facilitators: basic communication skills – there are internal trainings and rules to ensure ethical conduct.

What financial or other resources are needed to run the current process?

Logistics: venue, food, sound system, projector

Facilities for participants and external, e.g., transport/accommodation, food

Printed materials needed for the meetings

Who owns and manages the data collected? (e.g., city IT department, external contractor, shared cloud repository)

AAIT based on consent forms. AAIT has DPO. The role of Dembrane in storage and its own data must be discussed.

Does the collected data include personal data?

The registration of people (name, surname, and contact, if needed: age range, education level, profession);

Sensitive data related to opinions/topics could be gathered, but it is to be confirmed.

Are you re-using personal data collected 1) before the start of this project or 2) from another project for the AI4Deliberation project?

Yes. Just contact me to invite people to the next deliberations for AI4D.

Are there internal policies, formal regulations, or laws governing the process²⁰?

There are general policies, not very specific to the deliberation process. They have been shared after the interview.

What ethical or legal challenges have emerged, and how are they addressed? (e.g., GDPR compliance, such as informed consent and permission to re-use data; moderation bias, accessibility)

Consent forms → review from DPO

Data protection policy.

A lot of ethical internal policies.

For AI4D → concern who owns the data? Dembrane? We need to discuss it.

Is there a need for legal or policy changes to enable future AI integration? (e.g., data sharing permissions, procurement frameworks, trust guidelines)

No current AI policy.

No specific needs (need to check!)

Are there any training/educational material for deliberators as well as moderators/facilitators?

Info material at the beginning of the deliberation about the process and topics, or an expert talk in the information phase.

Internal training for facilitators/moderators

4. Technical and Infrastructural Aspects

²⁰ The aim is to identify certain sector-specific regulation (for example in the field of healthcare, digital rights or internet governance), as opposed to very general legislation of personal data and fundamental rights.

What platform or tools are used?

(e.g., Decidim, Consul, custom platform, email-based, none)

WordPress spaces to give the possibility to comment on reports/documents.

Decidim in future (same as WordPress).

Are there existing data for deliberations? If yes, indicate them.

Just the output reports – policy recommendations have public availability.

What types of data are collected from the deliberation process?

(e.g., free-text comments, votes, demographic data, proposals, meeting notes)

Verbal comments are not collected (sometimes quoted but without any association with personal data) → aggregated in a report. During a live meeting, all material (digital or physical) produced (including by participants) is collected and digitised to create the report.

In which language(s) is the data collected?

(e.g., Greek, English, German, Italian, multilingual)

Italian

Where is the data stored, and how is it accessed?

(e.g., internal servers, third-party platform, no long-term storage)

Report stored in internal folder. MS cloud

Does the tool need to communicate with other systems? (e.g., for authentication)

No

What are the main technical challenges you currently face?

(e.g., data volume, multilingual input, lack of standard formats, outdated systems)

No

5. Reflections on Impact and Future Vision**What impact has the current deliberation process had so far? What is the current engagement (in numbers)?**

(e.g., policy changes, increased engagement, trust building, media attention)

Policy change:

policy recommendations/change → some of them implements e.g., National impact → new law

local plan on civil protection/public service improvement → local level (numbers depending on inhabitants)

Depending on the process and follow-up, increased engagement, and building trust

What are the most significant strengths of your current process?

(e.g., inclusiveness, transparency, simplicity, local relevance)

Accountability/transparency, participation with an inclusiveness approach, trust (because of the nature of the organisation)

Relevance if the process is at local level

Understanding of problems and needs at different scales

What are the most significant limitations or bottlenecks to scale this process?

(e.g., large volume of inputs, Cost/funding, recruitment, legal constraints, political support)

Political support in implementing the process outputs

To scale up: it is difficult to host/moderate high numbers, and it is demanding in terms of effort and resources.

How do you imagine AI could enhance your process in the future?

AI: moderator to scale up, organisation of process (make reports, moderate content, summarise it, facilitate accessibility)

What would you need to start using AI in your process?

(e.g., training, funding, trusted AI tools, legal clarification, community support)

Training, trusted tools

German Pilot**Basic Information**

Type of deliberation: (e.g., public consultation, participatory budgeting, legislative crowdsourcing)

public consultation

What is the typical duration/frequency of deliberations?

~1 month consul, ~1 day in person

Which topics are generally discussed in deliberations?

Traffic planning, re-use of public space. Or anything else, no general restrictions

What is the typical participant size?

In person 50- 100, online current max 200 (can be more)

2. Deliberation Process

How is the deliberation initiated? (e.g., by law, initiative of government, or civil society request)

In person: periodically every three months (announced in newspapers, the specific date)

Online: initiated by the city council when there is a need – political will (based on society's needs and discussions)

Which recruitment model best describes this pilot? (e.g., random selection, open self-selection ('anyone can sign up'), Invitation only)

open self-selection – only for citizens of Bamberg. In consul, they have specific credentials account.

Are contributions anonymous or non-anonymous?

Non-anonymous

Are participants offered an incentive? (e.g., honorarium, voucher, reimbursement)

No

Is the process formally divided into stages? If yes, which stages? (e.g., Recruitment, Deliberative-rules presentation, ice-breaking, Factual information input (experts/evidence),

stakeholder input, Learning / quizzes / knowledge checks, Idea generation / proposal drafting, Discussion/deliberation, Decision-making / voting, Other)

Consul process:

Recruitment – self-selection

Factual info on the first page to describe the theme (not as a specific stage, the info is just there)

Discussion/deliberation

Decision-making after the deliberation by organisers

Regional media, newspaper, results of the deliberation

In person:

People come self-selected

People discuss openly – raise hands

Discuss /deliberate

Voting by raising hands

How flexible is the process? *(Briefly describe options for adapting stages or timing)*

No. Based on consul. There are options to adapt the overview page (e.g., for participatory budgeting purposes), but Consul does support a processual view of deliberations.

Does deliberation take place in sub-groups? *(e.g., tables, breakout rooms, online clusters)?*

No

What is the format of the deliberation? *(e.g., workshops, open discussion, facilitated discussion)*

In person: Open discussion

Consul: open discussion, voting

What kind of output does the process produce, and what happens to it? *(e.g., full report, executive summary, policy binding decision, policy recommendation, impact assessment, agenda setting)*

In person: agenda setting, policy recommendation (maybe internal report)

Consul: policy recommendation, summary of feedback (published in newspapers)

Are any game-based elements used? *If yes, briefly describe how*

No

Which concrete steps or tools do you use to upscale while maintaining quality (if any)? *(e.g., digital platform, regional hubs, AI moderation)*

Consul

Social networks for upscaling

Is the quality of the deliberative process monitored? If yes, how? *(e.g., participant feedback, discourse monitoring, fact-checking, deliberative indexes)*

No

Is the quality of the deliberative output monitored? If yes, how? *(e.g., manually reviewed by a subgroup of participants, expert review, AI/LLM-assisted review)?*

No

3. Organisational, Legal, and Ethical Aspects

Who are the key stakeholders and what are their roles/responsibility?

(e.g., **Stakeholders:** coordinating authority, policy makers, civic groups, platform providers, researchers, technical support; **Roles:** initiator, moderator, facilitator, participant)

Stakeholders (Consul):

Company hosting consul – platform provider
 City council – initiator, policy-maker
 Department of citizen participation (department of the city) – moderation, analysis of outcomes
 Citizens – participants of the deliberation
 Citizen associations/civil multipliers (motivate people to participate – not an institutionalised role, role in the society)

Stakeholders (In person)

Mayor + Other city council members
 Citizens
 Department of citizen participation (department of the city) – moderation – organisation
 Citizen association (motivate people to participate – not an institutionalised role, a role in the society)
 City council – collect info for agenda setting (the output is recommendation not binding for the city council)

Are there specific qualifications required for deliberation organisers? And what skills are expected/desired from participants?

Organisers (no formal qualifications): knowledge of local political structure and topic, participatory planning
 Citizens: No

What financial or other resources are needed to run the current process?

In person: rooms, advertisement (typical medial channels)
 Consul: financial for advertisement, financial to host Consul

Who owns and manages the data collected? (e.g., city IT department, external contractor, shared cloud repository)

Consul: city department of citizen participation (??? Need to check)

Does the collected data include personal data?

Yes – names of participants
 Any personal data included in contributions
 Coming of age is mandatory to participate

Are you re-using personal data collected 1) before the start of this project or 2) from another project for the AI4Deliberation project?

We may use the old deliberation data of our own consul instance.

Are there internal policies, formal regulations, or laws governing the process²¹?

No (maybe participation policy document?) maybe check?

What ethical or legal challenges have emerged, and how are they addressed? (e.g., GDPR compliance, such as informed consent and permission to re-use data; moderation bias, accessibility)

During registration fill out a consent form and liability of contributions

Register once for the whole platform.

In person: Everything is organised in a public manner and by attending, contributors show their consent

Is there a need for legal or policy changes to enable future AI integration?

(e.g., data sharing permissions, procurement frameworks, trust guidelines)

No legal.

Coordinate with DPO, Consul provider

Are there any training/educational material for deliberators as well as moderators/facilitators?

No

4. Technical and Infrastructural Aspects**What platform or tools are used?**

(e.g., Decidim, Consul, custom platform, email-based, none)

Consul

Are there existing data for deliberations? If yes indicate them.

Yes. At consul

What types of data are collected from the deliberation process?

(e.g., free-text comments, votes, demographic data, proposals, meeting notes)

Consul: free text, votes, names of participants

In person: summary of decisions in the end

In which language(s) is the data collected?

(e.g., Greek, English, German, Italian, multilingual)

German

But can also be other languages. No restriction officially

Where is the data stored and how is it accessed?

(e.g., internal servers, third-party platform, no long-term storage)

Internal servers

Does the tool need to communicate with other systems? (e.g., for authentication)

Yes. Authentication service of the municipality for registration.

What are the main technical challenges you currently face?

(e.g., data volume, multilingual input, lack of standard formats, outdated systems)

No specific. Consul somehow outdated itself .

²¹ The aim is to identify certain sector-specific regulation (for example in the field of healthcare, digital rights or internet governance), as opposed to very general legislation of personal data and fundamental rights.

Need to define an API with base Consul to integrate AI4D with Consul

5. Reflections on Impact and Future Vision

What impact has the current deliberation process had so far? What is the current engagement (in numbers)?

(e.g., policy changes, increased engagement, trust building, media attention)

Increased engagement

Some policy recommendations led to policy changes.

Currently 20 deliberations at Consul. ~50% implemented (or parts of them)

What are the most significant strengths of your current process?

(e.g., inclusiveness, transparency, simplicity, local relevance)

Consul: everyone can join, inclusiveness

What are the most significant limitations or bottlenecks to scale this process?

(e.g., large volume of inputs, Cost / funding , recruitment, legal constraints, political support)

Recruitment, Political support

How do you imagine AI could enhance your process in the future?

Consul: chatbot for informing, information/learning phase. Analyse the quality or summary, consensus

What would you need to start using AI in your process?

(e.g., training, funding, trusted AI tools, legal clarification, community support)

API Consul, training for public servants, trusted AI tools. Community support.

PENDING EUROPEAN APPROVAL

Appendix B – WP2 process matrix of pilots

Greek Pilot

		AS IS	TO BE
Pre - Deliberation	Participant Acquisition	Self-selection only. No targeted outreach. No demographic monitoring or inclusive recruitment strategies. Participation requires only email address - no verification of diversity.	<p>Legally Feasible within N. 4622/2019 Art. 61.1 ("πρόσφορα μέσα"):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Email notifications to registered opengov.gr users and past participants • Partnerships with CSOs for outreach to underrepresented groups • SMS notifications (with user consent) • Multilingual invitations (Greek, English, languages of migrant communities) <p>Desirable AI features:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personalized invitation templates based on user interests • Automated translation of invitations
	Agenda Setting	Strictly top down. Ministry decides consultation topics. Citizens can only comment on already-drafted legislation. Legal barrier: N. 4622/2019 repealed N. 4048/2012 which allowed pre-consultation on policy principles before drafting.	<p>Experimental workaround</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI analysis of past consultation patterns to inform ministry agenda planning • "Shadow agenda" tracking: AI analyses citizen comments across consultations to identify emerging priorities
	Establishing Rules	Users click "accept" on generic terms of service. Comment moderation is manual and inconsistent. Basic moderation rules exist.	<p>AI-Assisted Self Moderation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time toxicity detection with warning prompts before posting • Constructive comment examples shown based on AI analysis of high-quality past contributions
	Group Building	No group formation. All participants engage in a single undifferentiated comment thread per article. Comments displayed chronologically, making it difficult to follow	<p>AI-Facilitated Bridging: AI identifies common ground across stakeholders</p>

		thematic discussions. No distinction between individual citizens, organised CSOs, academic experts, or industry representatives.	Visualizations: Stakeholder position maps using tools like Debategraph
	Information & Learning	<p>Current State: Minimal information provision. Each consultation includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Draft legislation text (legal language, often 50+ pages) • Preliminary Regulatory Impact Assessment (technical, bureaucratic) • No plain language summaries or explanatory materials • No background documents, international comparisons, or context • Citizens expected to understand complex legal text without support. Significant barrier to meaningful participation, especially for non-experts 	<p>Plain Language Summaries:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI-generated executive summary (2-page maximum) • - Key changes highlighted in simple Greek • "What this means for you" sections for different audiences <p>AI Chatbot Assistant: 24/7 availability answering questions about:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content of draft legislation, regulatory impact analysis, consultation process and timeline • How to submit effective comments
Deliberation	Problem Definition	No dedicated problem definition phase. Problem is implicitly defined by ministries through the draft legislation itself. Alternative problem definitions or policy approaches outside the draft text are not systematically captured or considered.	<p>.AI Identification of Alternative Framings. AI identifies comments that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenge underlying assumptions • Propose alternative policy approaches • Question whether the law addresses the real problem • These flagged for special attention in the mandatory Article 61.4 report
	Open Discussion	Article-by-article commenting system. Comments displayed in chronological order. No threading or reply structure. No tools for identifying agreement/disagreement, clustering similar positions, or synthesizing discussions. Manual moderation (slow, inconsistent). No real-time feedback or interaction. Comments become fragmented; difficult to see overall patterns or build on others' contributions. High-quality deliberation is accidental, not designed.	<p>Real-Time AI Summarisation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Live synthesis of main arguments on each article • Updated regularly as new comments arrive • Multiple views: by theme, by stakeholder type, by frequency • Visual consensus/dissent meters

	<p>Self-Reflection</p>	<p>No self-reflection phase exists. Consultation opens, runs for 2 weeks, then closes. Participants cannot review synthesis of discussions, request clarifications, or revise their positions based on collective learning. No iterative deepening of deliberation. Once the consultation period ends, no further input is possible even if new information emerges or misunderstandings are clarified. This creates a "snapshot" rather than a "deliberative journey."</p>	<p>Mid-Point Synthesis (48 hours):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI-generated comprehensive interim report • Visualization of main positions and areas of contention • Identification of factual disagreements requiring clarification • Ministry response to most frequent questions/concerns <p>Argument Evolution Tracking: AI shows how discussion has developed</p> <p>Knowledge Gap Identification: AI suggests additional information sources for unclear topics</p> <p>Perspective-Taking Prompts: AI presents strongest counter-arguments to your position</p>
	<p>Finding Solutions</p>	<p>No structured solution-finding phase. Citizens can suggest textual amendments in comments, but:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No collaborative drafting tools • No mechanism to build on others' proposals • No voting or prioritization of citizen amendments • No structured dialogue between amendment proposers and ministry • Ministry reviews comments but no transparent process for considering specific amendment proposals. 	<p>Citizen Amendment Proposals (CAPs) in a Structured Format:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current text [auto-populated from draft] • Proposed change [clear tracked-changes view] • Rationale [free text, minimum 50 words] • Expected impact [user assessment] • Supporting evidence [optional links/citations] • <p>AI Assistance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal language helper (converts plain language to legal text) • Consistency checker (flags conflicts with other articles) • Precedent finder (similar amendments from past consultations) • Impact predictor (suggests potential consequences)

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	<p>Final Decision Making</p>	<p>No final decision-making role for citizens. Consultation closes after 2 weeks. Ministry reviews comments internally with no transparency. Ministry prepares final draft incorporating "conclusions of consultation" (Article 63.6-7) but discretionary interpretation. No voting, no consensus measurement, no structured prioritization. Citizens never know:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What specific comments were considered important? • Why some suggestions accepted and others rejected • How their input influenced the final text • Whether the majority view on contentious points was followed 	<p>Closing Deliberation Report (AI-Generated): Produced immediately upon consultation close</p> <p>Quantitative Summary:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total participants (overall and per article) • Comments submitted (breakdown by type: support/oppose/amend/question) • Demographic reach (age, gender, region - anonymized aggregates) • Engagement timeline (when participation peaked) <p>Qualitative Analysis:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Main themes and arguments (per article) • Consensus positions (>70% agreement) • Major areas of disagreement • Citizen Amendment Proposals ranking • Expert vs. lay citizen perspectives • Potential implementation challenges raised <p>Visualizations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Position maps and argument networks showing relationships between ideas with Debategraph • Sentiment analysis per article
<p>Post - Deliberation</p>	<p>Output generation</p>	<p>Manual report generation by ministry staff after consultation closes. Typical output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brief summary (2-5 pages) attached to bill • Lists number of comments, sometimes grouped by article • May include general themes • Rarely quotes specific comments or provides detailed analysis • No visualizations, statistics, or structured synthesis • Process opaque and time-consuming (weeks of manual work). Quality varies dramatically by ministry capacity. Critical problem: Article 61.4 	<p>Comprehensive Consultation Report (Auto-Generated):</p> <p>Section A: Executive Summary (2 pages)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total participation metrics • Main conclusions and recommendations • Critical issues requiring attention • Changes recommended for final draft <p>Section B: Detailed Analysis (per article)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comment summary (themes, frequency, stakeholder breakdown) • Citizen Amendment Proposals • Consensus vs. contentious positions • Technical/legal issues raised

		<p>mandates comprehensive reporting and <u>email</u> to participants - but this is systematically not enforced</p> <p>Many consultations never produce a public report on opengov.gr . Participants never learn outcomes. This non-compliance is the #1 accountability gap.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suggested textual changes grouped by theme <p>Section C: Cross-Cutting Themes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Issues raised across multiple articles • Systemic concerns about the draft • Alternative policy approaches suggested • Implementation challenges identified <p>Section D: Demographic Analysis</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation breakdown (region, age, stakeholder type) • Underrepresented voices • Differences in perspective by group <p>Section E: Visualizations & Infographics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Position maps (Debategraph outputs) <p>2. Multi-Format Delivery</p> <p>Web version: Interactive HTML with expandable sections</p> <p>PDF: Printable comprehensive report for Parliament</p> <p>Plain language summary: 2-page citizen-friendly version</p> <p>Audio version: Text-to-speech recording (accessibility)</p> <p>Video summary: 5-minute AI-generated visual presentation</p> <p>Data export: CSV/JSON for researchers and journalists</p>
	<p>Review</p>	<p>No systematic review of consultation quality or impact. No metrics tracked. No evaluation of whether consultations improve legislation or democratic legitimacy. No learning loop to improve future consultations. Occasional ad-hoc reviews by civil society (e.g., GovWatch reports documenting non-compliance with Article 61.4), but no institutionalized evaluation. No assessment of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Representativeness of participation • Quality of deliberation 	<p>Impact Evaluation (Post-Legislative), conducted after final bill passage</p> <p>Influence Analysis:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of citizen recommendations adopted/modified/rejected • Which types of comments most influential (expert vs. lived experience) • Correlation between consensus level and adoption

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Influence on final legislation • Democratic value created (or not) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parliamentary references to consultation in debate
	<p>Wider Public</p>	<p>Limited public communication about consultations and outcomes. Announcements on opengov.gr homepage and ministry websites. Occasional press releases for high-profile legislation. No proactive outreach to non-participants. Final bills submitted to Parliament with consultation reports attached, but:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reports often buried in lengthy documentation • No public-facing summary of consultation results • No effort to inform broader public about what citizens said • No "closing the loop" communication to general public • Media coverage rare unless controversial • Results: Most Greeks unaware consultations happen, even less aware of outcomes. 	<p>Automated email to ALL participants with personalized summary highlighting articles you commented on</p> <p>Follow-Up (when final bill submitted):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Email update showing what changed from draft to final • Direct links to specific provisions where your input visible • Invitation to provide feedback on the consultation process itself • Notice of parliamentary debate schedule <p>Wider Public Dissemination - Multi-Platform Strategy:</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI-generated infographics for Twitter/Facebook/Instagram • Short video summaries (60-90 seconds) • Key quotes from citizen comments (anonymized) • "What We Heard" series highlighting main themes <p>Government Channels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Featured stories on gov.gr portal • Monthly newsletter highlighting active consultations and results • Integration with gov.gr notification system <p>Civil Society:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partnerships with CSOs for member mobilization • Training workshops on effective participation

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			<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Co-creation of outreach materials <p>Dedicated opengov.gr Results Portal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Searchable archive of all consultation reports• "Success Stories" highlighting influential citizen input• Comparative statistics across consultations• Interactive visualizations of participation trends• Downloadable datasets for researchers and journalists
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INTERNATIONAL PILOT

		AS IS	TO BE
Pre - Deliberation	Participant Acquisition	Self-selection (arising primarily from online outreach).	Self-selection (arising primarily from online outreach).
	Agenda Setting	Agenda framed in online materials and can evolve collaboratively.	Agenda framed in online materials and can evolve collaboratively.
	Establishing Rules	Modes of interaction framed in online materials and modelled in action by curators.	Modes of interaction framed in online materials and modelled in action by curators.
	Group Building	All direct participants interact online as part of a single, open group; asynchronous collaboration means that subgroups can form and start to interact at any time.	All direct participants interact online as part of a single, open group; asynchronous collaboration means that subgroups can form and start to interact at any time.
	Information & Learning	Information and learning are built into the framing and content of the graph.	Information and learning are built into the framing and content of the graph. AI offers further support to this process.
Deliberation	Problem Definition	Problem definition and redefinition are part of the graphing process as new information arises and learning occurs.	Problem definition and redefinition are part of the graphing process as new information arises and learning occurs. AI offers further support to this process.
	Open Discussion	Open discussion is a continuous aspect of the graphing process.	Open discussion is a continuous aspect of the graphing process. AI offers further support to this process.
	Self-Reflection	The asynchronous graphing process offers significant opportunities for, and encourages, self-reflection.	The asynchronous graphing process offers significant opportunities for, and encourages, self-reflection.

	Finding Solutions	The graphing process focuses more on capturing and explaining the range of options available rather than on finding solutions per se.	The graphing process focuses more on capturing and explaining the range of options available rather than on finding solutions per se. AI offers further support to this process.
	Final Decision Making	The graph is not intended to be a decision-making forum (but can act as scaffolding for decision-making in other forums).	The graph is not intended to be a decision-making forum (but can act as scaffolding for decision-making in other forums).
Post - Deliberation	Output generation	The graph is a living document and its own primary output.	The graph is a living document and its own primary output. AI offers different forms of output to help to ease the process of interpretation.
	Review	The open and collaborative nature of the graph development process means that the outputs are under continuous review.	The open and collaborative nature of the graph development process means that the outputs are under continuous review.
	Wider Public	The graph is continuously open to the wider public, and continuously open to further development. The policy graph can be embedded and shared on other websites.	The graph is continuously open to the wider public, and continuously open to further development. The policy graph can be embedded and shared on other websites. AI offers new forms of outreach.

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ITALIAN PILOT

		AS IS	TO BE
Pre - Deliberation	Participant Acquisition		<p>Invitation via social media channels and newsletters (mail).</p> <p>Selection based on sociodemographic criteria (age, gender, status, origin).</p> <p>An analysis will be carried out of those who have agreed to participate and corrective measures will be implemented if some categories are missing (e.g., a new round of invitations targeting specific people categories).</p> <p>Desirable AI features: Tools such as Panelot can be used to conduct a civic lottery. AI avatars or simulated participants can be generated to represent the views of people who are not part of the participating group.</p>
	Agenda Setting		<p>AA Italy provides basic information about the process, further contextualisation, and responds to accessibility needs proactively or when participants join.</p> <p>The Italian Climate Change Adaptation Plan (PNACC) is presented to participants, who choose the topic to focus on from a selection of proposed macro-themes.</p> <p>According to participants' proposals, needs and topic chosen, the agenda will be established collaboratively.</p> <p>Desirable AI features: AI helps to summarise the PNACC, make it understandable and select the macro-themes. Audio-videos are produced by AI.</p>
	Establishing Rules		<p>During the first online meeting, the rules will be explained and discussed in order to reach a shared “participation agreement”.</p>

		<p>Desirable AI features: Assistance chat bot to support participants in using the platform. AI clusters participation rules agreement based on discussion inputs. Collective dialogue tools such as <u>Pol.is</u> or ECHO, <u>DeliberAlde</u>, <u>Psi</u>, <u>Cortico</u> can be used to cluster inputs.</p>
	Group Building	<p>Participants are divided into discussion groups. Where possible, groups will be balanced to ensure they are heterogeneous.</p> <p>Can use Frankly’s demographic group builder for this</p>
	Information & Learning	<p>Participants will be provided with an information kit containing basic information about the process, background information on the topic and other relevant information.</p> <p>An online repository space will be created where information material will be available for participants to consult.</p> <p>Two online meetings with experts and stakeholders will be organised, called “learning journey”, which will include multiple rounds of informing-questioning-answering where participants will engage with pre-prepared materials, speakers, Q&A responses, and experiences to build group learning.</p> <p>The content of the “learning journey” will be summarised, added to the repository and made more understandable by AI.</p> <p>Desirable AI features: A generated audio- video summarises the main training content. AI helps to present the information in easy language with diagrams and visual explanations where possible. AI can be used to develop scenarios as a way of informing participants or helping them to understand the issue and to test draft proposals.</p>
Deliberation	Problem Definition	<p>This is done during the agenda setting phase (see above).</p>

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<p>Open Discussion</p>		<p>One round of online discussions will be implemented. In this phase participants, divided into working groups, discuss the topic (and sub-topics) of the PNACC.</p> <p>Desirable AI features: Collective dialogue tools such as <u>Pol.is</u>, ECHO, Remesh or the Habermas Machine can be used to summarise different points of view expressed in each working group. AI can be used to create a summary of the main contributions discussed in each working group, as well as a final report putting together the main content from all groups. At this stage, online tools will be used to facilitate conversation between people (e.g., Frankly). AI can simplify text into easy language and translate it.</p>
<p>Self-Reflection</p>		<p>Participants read and analyse the first report produced and may request further clarification and information (asynchronously).</p> <p>Desirable AI features: AI tools can suggest additional training materials on the topics discussed by working groups, as well as further points for discussion.</p>
<p>Finding Solutions</p>		<p>In a second round of online meetings, participants, divided into working groups, will make proposals on the topic (and/or sub-topic). Each group's proposals will be shared with the others, which will be able to comment on them. Instant feedback loop mechanism will be implemented in this phase.</p> <p>Desirable AI features: Online tools such as <u>ThinkScape</u>, Devil advocate or the Habermas Machine can be implemented to help discussion in small groups, with active live cross-pollination between groups throughout the process. In this phase, online tools will be used to facilitate conversations between people (e.g. Frankly).</p>
<p>Final Decision Making</p>		<p>A final document containing all proposals emerged in the previous phase is drawn up and left on the on platform to be consulted by participants. Any alternative proposals on which consensus was not reached during the deliberation phase will be highlighted and put to a vote. After choosing between alternatives, the final document will be voted on again in its entirety and approved by a qualified majority.</p> <p>Desirable AI features:</p>

			<p>AI can be used to make the final document to be voted on understandable with infographics and audio-videos presentation.</p> <p>Some features of AI-based tools can be used to accompany the voting phase and to identify connected statements among a large number of alternative inputs (e.g. the Habermas machine, e.g. <u>Polis</u>, <u>Remesh</u>, <u>YourPriorities</u>, ECHO).</p> <p>In this phase, online tools will be used to hold conversations between people (e.g. Frankly).</p> <p>AI can simplify text into easy language and translate it.</p>
Post - Deliberation	Output generation		<p>The final document will be produced using AI tools to create infographics and explanatory audio-videos.</p> <p>AI can simplify text into easy language and translate it.</p>
	Review		<p>AI tools will be used to perform a quality process check (metrics, analytics).</p>
	Wider Public		<p>Massive final report dissemination via email and through content creation for social media channels supported by AI.</p> <p>A strategy of outreach (e.g. stakeholder map) and advocacy can also be supported by AI.</p> <p>AI can simplify text into easy language and translate it.</p>

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German Pilot

		AS IS	TO BE
Pre - Deliberation	Participant Acquisition	Currently the participant acquisition is solely relying on self-selection	The number of participants can be scaled by using affiliate links. When friends sign up via a person's link, that person receives points on the platform, which can be used for cosmetic aspects (e.g., avatars).
	Agenda Setting	Top-Down Agenda-Setting by the leading level of the city administration	Offline meetings (possibly using Echo) in the run-up to the participation process should discuss which topic from a predetermined selection is currently the most relevant.
	Establishing Rules	Simple button to agree to the terms and conditions of platform use. No precise definition of discussion rules.	A gamified tutorial can ensure that all participants actually engage with the rules. A feedback button can also be added for the collaborative development of the discussion rules.
	Group Building	Currently there is no explicit mechanism to form sub-groups.	A collaborative game could be introduced in small groups to further develop arguments.
	Information & Learning	A descriptive text explains the thematic background of the deliberation topic.	A chatbot informs citizens about previous council decisions on specific topics before they participate. Another option is to introduce AI-generated videos to visualize the information in a simplified
Deliberation	Problem Definition	There is no dedicated phase to for problem definition right now.	
	Open Discussion	The open discussion takes place in a simple form of comments and replies.	A range of AI tools will support the process: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Simplification and translation of language; - Legally compliant, reliable fact checking; - A devil's advocate bot that revives dormant discussions with stimulating/challenging comments - Simplified entry into the discussion through an AI-generated summary of the current arguments - Periodic 'wrap-ups' of the past period as a gamification module; number of comments written; quality of comments written; thematic

			focus, etc. This can, but does not have to be shared publicly in the profile.
	Self-Reflection	There is no dedicated phase to for Self-Reflection right now.	The aforementioned Devils advocate bot can also be used to stimulate self-reflection.
	Finding Solutions	There is no dedicated phase to for Finding Solutions right now.	
	Final Decision Making	There is no dedicated phase to for Final Decision Making right now.	Meta-Consens-Orientation. An AI Bot which tries to connect different argumentative approaches to explain why the identified consensus would be the best solution (to foster acceptance even in opposing camps).
Post - Deliberation	Output generation	To date, there is no transparent process for generating output, as the summary report is created manually and then submitted to the city council as a decision template.	An automated content summary extracts various argument. This should be validated by feedback loops from the participants.
	Review	Also generated by hand by the municipal staff.	AI-supported analyses can review the content and quality of the deliberation process. For these metrics and the overview of arguments, an automated condensed visualization should be created here to enable feedback loops. For example, why are some aspects less developed than others?
	Wider Public	Results are distributed through the common public affairs channels of the municipality	Immediate feedback loops to participants after completion of the process

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Appendix C – WP2 evaluation questionnaire

Introduction:

Q1. Welcome text + Pilot/Organization name (open text)

“Welcome to the WP2 user evaluation survey! Thank you for taking the time to review the draft Deliberative Process Guidelines and the annexed Matrix. This survey focuses on usability, clarity, and practical applicability of the guideline from an organiser/pilot partner perspective. Please indicate your organization/Pilot name.”

Q2. Have you read the guidelines? (single choice)

Skip logic: If “No” → End survey.

Overall structure clarity:

Q3. In your view, is the overall structure of the guideline clear (principles → stages → scaling mechanisms → risks → example)? (single choice)

- Yes
- No

If Q3 = No:

Q4. If anything was unclear, which section felt most complex? (multiple choice)

- Deliberative principles
- Scaling mechanisms
- Stages
- Matrix
- Socio-technical challenges
- Other: _____

Q23. What suggestions do you have to improve that section? (open text)

Core principles:

Q6. To what extent do the principles feel actionable for practitioners? (Likert 1–5)

- Not actionable at all
- Not very actionable
- Neutral
- Somewhat actionable
- Very actionable

Q5. Core Principles (Inclusion, Equality, Plurality, Authenticity, Reflection) — The explanation of the five core normative principles is... (Likert 1–5)

- Very unclear
- Somewhat unclear
- Neutral
- Clear
- Very clear

Q7. Comments (open text)

Process stages:

Q8. Process Stages (Selection, Pre-Deliberation, Deliberation, Post-Deliberation) — How clear and usable is the guidance on recruitment, motivation, and inclusion strategies? (Likert 1–5)

- Not usable
- Not very usable
- Neutral
- Usable
- Very usable

Q10. Pre-Deliberation Stage — How clear and actionable is the guidance on orientation, group-building, information, and learning modules? (Likert 1–5)

- Extremely unclear
- Somewhat unclear
- Neither clear nor unclear
- Somewhat clear
- Extremely clear

Scaling mechanisms:

Q11. Scaling Mechanisms (Gamification, Multimodality, Distributed Groups, etc.) — How understandable are the six scaling strategies (motivation, diversity, division, comprehensibility, complexity reduction, community connection)? (Likert 1–5)

- Very hard to understand
- Hard to understand
- Neutral
- Understandable
- Very understandable

Q12. Which of the strategies feels most usable in real pilot contexts? (multiple choice)

- Motivation / Gamification
- Diversity & Hybrid Access
- Distributed Small-Group Deliberation
- Multimodal Communication
- Layered / Networked Architecture
- Complexity Reduction / Structured Learning
- None

Socio-technical challenges and risks:

Q13. Socio-Technical Challenges — How helpful is the section on risks (bias, digital divide, cognitive load, consequentiality, automation risks)? (Likert 1–5)

- Not helpful
- Not very helpful
- Neutral
- Helpful
- Very helpful

Q14. Can you list additional socio-technical challenges that were not included? (open text)

Design matrix and overall usability:

Q17. How useful did you find the design matrix when designing your scalable deliberative process? (Likert 1–5)

- Not at all useful
- Slightly useful
- Moderately useful
- Very useful
- Extremely useful

Q18. After reading the guideline, do you feel you could actually design a deliberative process with it? (Likert 1–5)

- Not at all
- Not really
- Partly (needs clarifications or templates)
- Yes, but with difficulty
- Yes, fully

Q19. Which parts would you need more support to implement? (open text)

Q20. Is anything missing that would improve the usability of the guideline? (open text)

Mitigation strategies (with conditional follow-up):

Q15. Does the guideline offer sufficiently clear mitigation strategies? (single choice)

- Yes
- No

If Q15 = No:

Q16. Could you outline the main issues? (open text)

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Appendix D – WP3 evaluation questionnaire and result

Meaningful deliberation			Evaluation criteria			
			Feasibility	Importance	Easiness of implementation	Contribution to meaningful deliberation
Foster democratic values	Conditions	Ensure accessibility of mass deliberation for all possible deliberators				
		Enlarge the capacities of deliberators to engage in mass deliberation				
		Guarantee influence on official decision-making				
		Ensure transparency about the use of AI in mass deliberation				
	Requirements	Develop AI and digital literacy among deliberators				
		Put deliberators in the lead of organising the mass deliberation				
		Respond to concerns regarding AI among potential deliberators				
		Guarantee meaningful human control over AI by involved and affected actors				
		Guarantee the traceability of deliberative output's influence on official decision-making				
Guarantee the effectiveness of mass deliberation	Conditions	Establish a structured deliberative process that allows for mass deliberation				
		Balance the added value of AI applications with its costs				
		Address safety problems caused by AI (such as manipulation, hallucination and bias) that undermine deliberative quality				
	Requirements	Measure deliberative quality by monitoring discussions				
		Allow for updating the deliberative output				

Sustainable integration			Evaluation criteria			
			Feasibility	Importance	Easiness of implementation	Contribution to sustainable integration
Practice adaptive governance of AI-enabled mass deliberation	Conditions	Design both the technological and governance parts of AI-enabled mass deliberation concurrently				
		Establish spaces for (mutual) learning about AI-enabled mass deliberation				
		React to changing interests and needs among involved and affected actors in AI-enabled mass deliberation				
		React to continuous developments and innovations in technology, especially AI				
	Requirements	Take time to organise AI-enabled mass deliberation				
		Formulate a vision on AI-enabled mass deliberation				
		Map the risks of using AI in mass deliberation				
		Enlarge capacity of public organisations to intervene in deliberative practice				
		Encourage monitoring changes in deliberative practices				
Cultivate long-term support among involved and affected actors	Conditions	Demonstrate commitment as public organisation to AI-enabled mass deliberation				
		Confer legitimacy to the AI-enabled mass deliberative practice				
		Adopt a deliberative stance/attitude within the public organisation				
		Establish political will to engage in AI-enabled mass deliberation				
		Guarantee the needed resources to enact AI-enabled mass deliberation				
		Dedicate organisational capacity for AI-enabled mass deliberation				
		Identify possible tensions between stakeholders				
Situate mass deliberation in existing organisational practices	Conditions	Situate mass deliberative practices in official decision-making processes				
		Issue a formal mandate for deliberative practices				
		Respect the Rule of Law within the deliberative practice				
		Establish data and AI governance				
	Requirements	Embed the AI applications in a broader technical infrastructure				
		Combine AI-enabled mass deliberation with classic (mini public) deliberation				
		Relate AI-enabled deliberative practice to representative democratic practices (if applicable)				
		Limit dependency on third parties				

Questions	Answers
1 Do the two subgoals (sustainable integration and meaningful deliberation) cover everything that is needed in your understanding of institutionalisation? Why?	
2 To what extent are the two subgoals complementary OR contradictory? What contradictions do you see in the full set of conditions and requirements? What can be done to these contradictions?	
3 To what extent does the full set of conditions and requirements reflect all necessary elements within the subgoals? Why?	
4 Do you have any remarks, comments, additions, or improvements regarding the conditions and requirements?	

Descriptive results of the assessment of individual conditions and requirements:

			Feasibility					
			Frequency					Median
			1	2	3	4	5	
Meaningful deliberation								
Foster democratic values	Conditions	Ensure accessibility of mass deliberation for all possible deliberators	1	3	9	2	0	3
		Enlarge the capacities of deliberators to engage in mass deliberation	0	3	11	1	0	3
		Guarantee influence on official decision-making	1	5	6	3	0	3
		Ensure transparency about the use of AI in mass deliberation	0	0	4	9	2	4
		Develop AI and digital literacy among deliberators	0	3	10	2	0	3
		Put deliberators in the lead of organising the mass deliberation	0	8	5	2	0	2
		Respond to concerns regarding AI among potential deliberators	0	0	1	9	5	4
		Guarantee meaningful human control over AI by involved and affected actors	1	1	7	5	1	3
		Guarantee the traceability of deliberative output's influence on official decision-making	0	2	4	5	4	4
Guarantee the effectiveness of mass deliberation	Requirements	Establish a structured deliberative process that allows for mass deliberation	0	0	5	10	0	4
		Balance the added value of AI applications with its costs	0	1	6	7	1	4
		Address safety problems caused by AI (such as manipulation, hallucination and bias) that undermine deliberative quality	0	2	6	4	3	3
		Measure deliberative quality by monitoring discussions	0	3	1	8	3	4
		Allow for updating the deliberative output	0	2	2	8	3	4
Sustainable integration								
Practice adaptive governance of AI-enabled mass deliberation	Conditions	Design both the technological and governance parts of AI-enabled mass deliberation concurrently	0	1	9	4	1	3
		Establish spaces for (mutual) learning about AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	0	1	11	3	4
		React to changing interests and needs among involved and affected actors in AI-enabled mass deliberation	1	2	7	3	2	3
		React to continuous developments and innovations in technology, especially AI	1	3	7	4	0	3
		Take time to organise AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	0	4	9	2	4
		Formulate a vision on AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	0	2	8	5	4
		Map the risks of using AI in mass deliberation	0	0	2	7	6	4
		Enlarge capacity of public organisations to intervene in deliberative practice	0	1	9	4	1	3
		Encourage monitoring changes in deliberative practices	0	1	4	6	4	4
Cultivate long-term support among involved and affected actors	Requirements	Demonstrate commitment as public organisation to AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	1	7	4	3	3
		Confer legitimacy to the AI-enabled mass deliberative practice	0	2	10	2	1	3
		Adopt a deliberative stance/attitude within the public organisation	0	6	6	2	1	3
		Establish political will to engage in AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	6	5	2	2	3
		Guarantee the needed resources to enact AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	5	7	2	1	3
		Dedicate organisational capacity for AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	3	7	4	1	3
		Identify possible tensions between stakeholders	0	2	2	8	3	4
Situate mass deliberation in existing organisational practices	Requirements	Situate mass deliberative practices in official decision-making processes	0	3	7	4	1	3
		Issue a formal mandate for deliberative practices	0	0	5	8	2	4
		Respect the Rule of Law within the deliberative practice	0	0	0	5	10	5
		Establish data and AI governance	0	0	4	6	5	4
		Embed the AI applications in a broader technical infrastructure	0	4	4	6	1	3
		Combine AI-enabled mass deliberation with classic (mini public) deliberation	0	0	6	6	3	4
		Relate AI-enabled deliberative practice to representative democratic practices (if applicable)	0	1	4	8	2	4
		Limit dependency on third parties	1	3	8	1	2	3
	Min	0	0	0	1	0	2,00	
	Max	1	8	11	11	10	5,00	

Meaningful deliberation			Importance					
			Frequency					Median
1	2	3	4	5				
Foster democratic values	Requirements	Ensure accessibility of mass deliberation for all possible deliberators	0	0	0	3	12	5
		Enlarge the capacities of deliberators to engage in mass deliberation	0	0	1	7	7	4
		Guarantee influence on official decision-making	0	0	0	5	10	5
		Ensure transparency about the use of AI in mass deliberation	0	0	2	3	10	5
		Develop AI and digital literacy among deliberators	0	0	4	3	8	5
		Put deliberators in the lead of organising the mass deliberation	1	0	8	3	3	3
		Respond to concerns regarding AI among potential deliberators	0	0	2	5	8	5
		Guarantee meaningful human control over AI by involved and affected actors	0	0	1	2	12	5
		Guarantee the traceability of deliberative output's influence on official decision-making	0	0	0	0	15	5
Guarantee the effectiveness of mass deliberation	Requirements	Establish a structured deliberative process that allows for mass deliberation	0	0	0	3	12	5
		Balance the added value of AI applications with its costs	0	0	7	5	3	4
		Address safety problems caused by AI (such as manipulation, hallucination and bias) that undermine deliberative quality	0	0	0	2	13	5
		Measure deliberative quality by monitoring discussions	0	0	2	5	8	5
		Allow for updating the deliberative output	0	1	0	7	7	4
Sustainable integration								
Practice adaptive governance of AI-enabled mass deliberation	Conditions	Design both the technological and governance parts of AI-enabled mass deliberation concurrently	0	0	1	4	10	5
		Establish spaces for (mutual) learning about AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	0	2	6	7	4
		React to changing interests and needs among involved and affected actors in AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	0	3	1	11	5
		React to continuous developments and innovations in technology, especially AI	0	0	2	5	8	5
	Requirements	Take time to organise AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	0	2	6	7	4
		Formulate a vision on AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	0	2	4	9	5
		Map the risks of using AI in mass deliberation	0	0	0	3	12	5
		Enlarge capacity of public organisations to intervene in deliberative practice	0	0	2	6	7	4
		Encourage monitoring changes in deliberative practices	0	0	6	4	5	4
Cultivate long-term support among involved and affected actors	Requirements	Demonstrate commitment as public organisation to AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	0	2	3	10	5
		Confer legitimacy to the AI-enabled mass deliberative practice	0	0	1	1	13	5
		Adopt a deliberative stance/attitude within the public organisation	0	0	3	2	10	5
		Establish political will to engage in AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	0	2	2	11	5
		Guarantee the needed resources to enact AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	0	1	2	12	5
		Dedicate organisational capacity for AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	0	1	4	10	5
		Identify possible tensions between stakeholders	0	0	1	8	6	4
Situate mass deliberation in existing organisational practices	Requirements	Situate mass deliberative practices in official decision-making processes	0	0	0	3	12	5
		Issue a formal mandate for deliberative practices	0	0	2	6	7	4
		Respect the Rule of Law within the deliberative practice	0	0	0	1	14	5
		Establish data and AI governance	0	0	0	2	13	5
		Embed the AI applications in a broader technical infrastructure	0	1	5	6	3	4
		Combine AI-enabled mass deliberation with classic (mini public) deliberation	0	0	1	8	6	4
		Relate AI-enabled deliberative practice to representative democratic practices (if applicable)	0	0	2	10	3	4
		Limit dependency on third parties	0	0	4	3	8	5
		Min	0	0	0	0	3	3,00
		Max	1	1	8	10	15	5,00

PENDING ITC APPROVAL

Meaningful deliberation			Easiness of implementation					
			Frequency					Median
			1	2	3	4	5	
Foster democratic values	Requirements	Ensure accessibility of mass deliberation for all possible deliberators	2	5	7	1	0	3
		Enlarge the capacities of deliberators to engage in mass deliberation	0	8	6	1	0	2
		Guarantee influence on official decision-making	4	6	0	4	1	2
		Ensure transparency about the use of AI in mass deliberation	0	0	7	7	1	4
		Develop AI and digital literacy among deliberators	0	6	7	2	0	3
		Put deliberators in the lead of organising the mass deliberation	2	10	1	2	0	2
		Respond to concerns regarding AI among potential deliberators	0	1	6	6	2	4
		Guarantee meaningful human control over AI by involved and affected actors	0	6	5	3	1	3
		Guarantee the traceability of deliberative output's influence on official decision-making	0	4	7	3	1	3
Guarantee the effectiveness of mass deliberation	Requirements	Establish a structured deliberative process that allows for mass deliberation	0	0	10	5	0	3
		Balance the added value of AI applications with its costs	0	4	6	4	1	3
		Address safety problems caused by AI (such as manipulation, hallucination and bias) that undermine deliberative quality	0	4	6	4	1	3
		Measure deliberative quality by monitoring discussions	0	2	5	8	0	4
		Allow for updating the deliberative output	0	2	3	8	2	4
Sustainable integration								
Practice adaptive governance of AI-enabled mass deliberation	Requirements	Design both the technological and governance parts of AI-enabled mass deliberation concurrently	1	4	8	2	0	3
		Establish spaces for (mutual) learning about AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	1	6	7	1	4
		React to changing interests and needs among involved and affected actors in AI-enabled mass deliberation	1	6	4	3	1	3
		React to continuous developments and innovations in technology, especially AI	0	10	4	1	0	2
		Take time to organise AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	0	11	4	0	3
		Formulate a vision on AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	0	8	4	3	3
		Map the risks of using AI in mass deliberation	0	1	2	8	4	4
		Enlarge capacity of public organisations to intervene in deliberative practice	0	6	5	3	1	3
		Encourage monitoring changes in deliberative practices	0	2	7	4	2	3
Cultivate long-term support among involved and affected actors	Requirements	Demonstrate commitment as public organisation to AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	4	4	4	3	3
		Confer legitimacy to the AI-enabled mass deliberative practice	0	7	4	3	1	3
		Adopt a deliberative stance/attitude within the public organisation	1	7	4	2	1	2
		Establish political will to engage in AI-enabled mass deliberation	2	7	3	2	1	2
		Guarantee the needed resources to enact AI-enabled mass deliberation	4	8	3	0	0	2
		Dedicate organisational capacity for AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	8	6	1	0	2
		Identify possible tensions between stakeholders	0	2	11	1	1	3
Situate mass deliberation in existing organisational practices	Requirements	Situate mass deliberative practices in official decision-making processes	1	3	10	1	0	3
		Issue a formal mandate for deliberative practices	0	2	8	5	0	3
		Respect the Rule of Law within the deliberative practice	0	0	0	8	7	4
		Establish data and AI governance	0	4	3	5	3	4
		Embed the AI applications in a broader technical infrastructure	0	6	7	1	1	3
		Combine AI-enabled mass deliberation with classic (mini public) deliberation	0	0	11	3	1	3
		Relate AI-enabled deliberative practice to representative democratic practices (if applicable)	0	1	11	1	2	3
		Limit dependency on third parties	2	5	7	0	1	3
				Min	0	0	0	0
		Max	4	10	11	8	7	4,00

PENDING ITC APPROVAL

Meaningful deliberation			Contribution to related subgoal					
			Frequency					Median
			1	2	3	4	5	
Foster democratic values	Requirements	Ensure accessibility of mass deliberation for all possible deliberators	0	0	0	3	12	5
		Enlarge the capacities of deliberators to engage in mass deliberation	0	0	2	2	11	5
		Guarantee influence on official decision-making	0	0	0	3	12	5
		Ensure transparency about the use of AI in mass deliberation	0	0	1	6	8	5
		Develop AI and digital literacy among deliberators	0	0	3	9	3	4
		Put deliberators in the lead of organising the mass deliberation	1	1	4	4	5	4
		Respond to concerns regarding AI among potential deliberators	0	0	4	6	5	4
		Guarantee meaningful human control over AI by involved and affected actors	0	0	2	1	12	5
		Guarantee the traceability of deliberative output's influence on official decision-making	0	0	0	1	14	5
Guarantee the effectiveness of mass deliberation	Requirements	Establish a structured deliberative process that allows for mass deliberation	0	0	1	1	13	5
		Balance the added value of AI applications with its costs	1	2	4	5	3	4
		Address safety problems caused by AI (such as manipulation, hallucination and bias) that undermine deliberative quality	0	0	0	2	13	5
		Measure deliberative quality by monitoring discussions	0	0	1	5	9	5
		Allow for updating the deliberative output	0	0	2	5	8	5
Sustainable integration								
Practice adaptive governance of AI-enabled mass deliberation	Conditions	Design both the technological and governance parts of AI-enabled mass deliberation concurrently	0	0	3	6	6	4
		Establish spaces for (mutual) learning about AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	0	3	3	9	5
		React to changing interests and needs among involved and affected actors in AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	1	2	7	5	4
		React to continuous developments and innovations in technology, especially AI	0	0	3	7	5	4
	Requirements	Take time to organise AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	0	2	7	6	4
		Formulate a vision on AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	0	2	7	6	4
		Map the risks of using AI in mass deliberation	0	0	2	6	7	4
		Enlarge capacity of public organisations to intervene in deliberative practice	0	0	2	6	7	4
		Encourage monitoring changes in deliberative practices	0	0	3	8	4	4
Cultivate long-term support among involved and affected actors	Requirements	Demonstrate commitment as public organisation to AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	0	0	7	8	5
		Confer legitimacy to the AI-enabled mass deliberative practice	0	0	1	3	11	5
		Adopt a deliberative stance/attitude within the public organisation	0	0	3	3	9	5
		Establish political will to engage in AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	0	1	2	12	5
		Guarantee the needed resources to enact AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	0	0	3	12	5
		Dedicate organisational capacity for AI-enabled mass deliberation	0	0	1	7	7	4
		Identify possible tensions between stakeholders	0	0	1	9	5	4
Situate mass deliberation in existing organisational practices	Requirements	Situate mass deliberative practices in official decision-making processes	0	0	0	3	12	5
		Issue a formal mandate for deliberative practices	0	0	2	6	7	4
		Respect the Rule of Law within the deliberative practice	0	0	0	2	13	5
		Establish data and AI governance	0	0	0	1	14	5
		Embed the AI applications in a broader technical infrastructure	0	1	7	5	2	3
		Combine AI-enabled mass deliberation with classic (mini public) deliberation	0	0	2	9	4	4
		Relate AI-enabled deliberative practice to representative democratic practices (if applicable)	0	0	2	12	1	4
		Limit dependency on third parties	0	1	3	7	4	4
				Min	0	0	0	1
		Max	1	2	7	12	14	5

PENDING TFC APPROVAL

Appendix E – WP2 non-aggregate analysis

The non-aggregate analysis is reported below (Figure A1)

Figure D1: Box-plot non-aggregated responses

Generally, non-aggregated responses follow the trend of organisation-mean responses.

By triangulating the non-aggregated responses with the aggregated mean responses (Figure A2), we observe a very high level of correlation between the individual-level aggregated means and the organisation-level aggregated means.

Figure D2: individual vs organisational mean responses correlation

Appendix F – WP5 literature review eDemocracy

Studies resulted from eDemocracy, eParticipation, deliberation, and acceptance literature review.

No	Title	Reference
1	Exploring Factors Affecting Citizens' Acceptance of Using E-Participation in Malaysian Local Governments Through an Extended UTAUT Model	[22]
2	Understanding the Intention to Use LAPOR Application as e-Democracy in Indonesia: An Integrating ECM and UTAUT Perspective	[23]
3	Public E-Participation Services as a Cure for Declining Voter Turnout: Acceptance Model Research Using PLS-SEM	[24]
4	Unearthing citizens' acceptance factors for e-participation initiatives through Facebook	[25]
5	Determinants of citizens' intention to engage in government-led electronic participation initiatives through Facebook	[26]
6	An eParticipation Acceptance Model	[27]
7	Factors explaining why some citizens engage in E-participation, while others do not	[28]
8	Introducing a new citizen-centric model of e-participation in Iraq	(Mustafa et al., 2019)
9	Continuous usage of e-participation: The role of the sense of virtual community	[30]
10	Citizens' intention to use and recommend e-participation: Drawing upon UTAUT and citizen empowerment	[31]
11	Acceptance of electronic democracy: An empirically validated approach	[32]
12	The framework for sustainable eDemocracy development	[33]
13	Factors influencing citizens' adoption of e-government: an empirical validation in a Developing Latin American Country	[34]
14	Empirical study of user acceptance of online political participation: Integrating Civic Voluntarism Model and Theory of Reasoned Action	[35]
15	Examining social capital and individual motivators to explain the adoption of online citizen participation	[36]
16	How E-Government Can Help Societies during a Crisis: Implications of the UTAUT Model in Lebanon	[37]
17	Examining the antecedents and outcomes of smart government usage: An integrated model	[38]
18	Voters' Intention to Use Electronic Voting Systems	[39]
19	Factors influencing the adoption of e-government websites in Afghanistan from the citizens' perspective	[40]
20	Citizens' Perception of Blockchain-Based E-Voting Systems: Focusing on TAM	[41]
21	E-government familiarity influence on Jordanians' perceptions	[42]
22	An empirical validation of a unified model of electronic government adoption (UMEGA)	[43]

Appendix G – WP5 literature review AI and acceptance

Studies resulted from AI and an acceptance literature review

No	Title	Reference
1	Trust in artificial intelligence, trust in engineers, and news media: Factors shaping public perceptions of autonomous drones through UTAUT2	[44]
2	Determinants of Public Sector Managers' Intentions to Adopt AI in the Workplace	[45]
3	Unpacking perceived risks and AI trust influences pre-service teachers' AI acceptance: A structural equation modelling-based multi-group analysis.	[46]
4	Artificial intelligence in psychology: How can we enable psychology students to accept and use artificial intelligence?	[47]
5	Innovation in tune: An empirical investigation of user acceptance of artificial intelligence-generated music	[48]
6	Analysing the impact of artificial intelligence on the online purchase decision-making process through the lens of the UTAUT 2 model	[49]
7	User acceptance of AI voice assistants in Jordan's telecom industry	[50]
8	Trust influence on AI HR tools perceived usefulness in Swiss HRM: the mediating roles of perceived fairness and privacy concerns	[51]
9	Attitudes Toward the Adoption of 2 Artificial Intelligence-Enabled Mental Health Tools Among Prospective Psychotherapists: Cross-sectional Study	[52]
10	More trust or more risk? User acceptance of an artificial intelligence virtual assistant	[53]
11	Predictors of Health Care Practitioners' Intention to Use AI-Enabled Clinical Decision Support Systems: Meta-Analysis Based on the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology	[54]
12	Linkage mechanism of antecedents for employees' continuous adoption of artificial intelligence virtual assistants	[55]
13	Understanding adoption of an artificial intelligence-enabled language e-learning system: an empirical study of UTAUT model	[56]
14	Why Do Retail Customers Adopt Artificial Intelligence (AI) Based Autonomous Decision-Making Systems?	[57]
15	Understanding teachers' willingness to use an artificial intelligence-based teaching analysis system: extending the TAM model with teaching efficacy, goal orientation, anxiety, and trust	[58]
16	Investigating the factors influencing users' adoption of artificial intelligence health assistants based on an extended UTAUT model	[59]
17	Unravelling the dynamics of digital equality and trust in AI-empowered metaverses and AI-VR-convergence	[60]
18	Comprehension, apprehension, and acceptance: Understanding the influence of literacy and anxiety on acceptance of artificial Intelligence	[61]
19	Adoption of AI-driven personalisation in digital news platforms: An integrative model of technology acceptance and perceived contingency	[62]
20	I Was Born to Love AI: The Influence of Social Status on AI Self-Efficacy and Intentions to Use AI	[63]

No	Title	Reference
21	What influences patients' continuance intention to use AI-powered service robots at hospitals? The role of individual characteristics*	[64]
22	AI Adoption for Collaboration: Factors Influencing Inclusive Learning Adoption in Higher Education	[65]
23	"Baby, you can drive my car": Psychological antecedents that drive consumers' adoption of AI-powered autonomous vehicles.	[66]
24	Assessing AI adoption in developing country academia: A trust and privacy-augmented UTAUT framework	[67]
25	Adoption of AI-enabled robo-advisors in fintech: simultaneous employment of UTAUT and the theory of reasoned action	[68]
26	Radiation Oncologists' Perceptions of Adopting an Artificial Intelligence-Assisted Contouring Technology: Model Development and Questionnaire Study	[69]
27	Adoption of AI-Enabled Tools in Social Development Organizations in India: An Extension of UTAUT Model	[70]
28	AI product knowledge as moderator of trust and attitude in usage intention: a study of Indonesian postgraduates	[71]
29	The Acceptance of AI Tools Among Design Professionals: Exploring the Moderating Role of Job Replacement	[72]
30	AI as my teacher: adoption of AI-driven virtual teaching assistants among students using the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology 2	[73]
31	Determinants of artificial intelligence use by accounting practitioners from the perspective of the technology readiness and acceptance model (TRAM)	[74]
32	Exploring the usage intention of AI-powered devices in smart homes among millennials and zillennials: the moderating role of trust	[75]
33	Exploring Designer Trust in Artificial Intelligence-Generated Content: TAM/TPB Model Study	[76]
34	The psychology of AI adoption in education: University students' intentions to use Large Language Models for learning from a TAM and TPB perspective	[77]
35	Factors Affecting the Attitude of Medical Doctors in Türkiye towards Using Artificial Intelligence Applications in Healthcare Services	[78]
36	Artificial intelligence, social influence, and AI anxiety: analysing the intentions of science doctoral students to use ChatGPT with PLS-SEM	[79]
37	Understanding managers' attitudes and behavioural intentions towards using artificial intelligence for organisational decision-making	[80]
38	Examining the factors influencing citizen adoption of e-government chatbot services in Jordan: A longitudinal survey study	[81]
39	The effect of trust on user adoption of AI-generated content	[82]
40	Unveiling the Impact of AI Technological Anxiety on the Marketers' Intention to Adopt Generative AI	[83]
41	Understanding continuance intention toward the use of AI chatbots in customer service among Generation Z in Vietnam	[84]
42	Cross-National Findings of Factors Affecting the Acceptance of AI-Based Sustainable Fintech	[85]

No	Title	Reference
43	Healthcare Sustainability: The Role of Artificial Intelligence Acceptance by Medical Staff	[86]
44	A UTAUT-Based Framework for Analysing Users' Intention to Adopt Artificial Intelligence in Human Resource Recruitment: A Case Study of Thailand	[87]
45	Artificial Intelligence (AI)-Based Technology Adoption in the Construction Industry: A Cross-National Perspective Using the Technology Acceptance Model	[88]
46	Adoption Intentions Toward AI-based Clinical Decision Support Tools: A Tam Study on Hospital Pharmacists	[89]
47	The Romanian Consumer's Perspective on the Integration of Artificial Intelligence in E-Commerce	[90]
48	Impact of perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness of humanoid robots on students' intention to use	[91]
49	Exploring factors influencing educators' adoption of ChatGPT: a mixed method approach	[92]
50	A model for the adoption of artificial intelligence in inclusive education: an exploratory study of key factors and expert insights	[93]
51	Exploring user acceptance of physical intelligent assistants: A study on AI-powered eyewear	[94]
52	Factors Affecting the Adoption of AI-Based Applications in Higher Education: An Analysis of Teachers' Perspectives Using Structural Equation Modelling	[95]
53	Acceptance of ChatGPT in the communication industry: the role of scepticism in the traditional TAM framework	[96]
54	Adoption of artificial intelligence in financial services: The case of robo-advisors in India	[97]
55	Exploring the intention of undergraduate students to embrace chatbots: from the vantage point of Lesotho	[98]
56	Perspectives of Patients With Chronic Diseases on Future Acceptance of AI-Based Home Care Systems: Cross-Sectional Web-Based Survey Study	[99]
57	Persuading Patients Using Rhetoric to Improve Artificial Intelligence Adoption: Experimental Study	[100]
58	Engineering students' perceptions and actual use of AI-based math tools for solving mathematical problems	[101]
59	Consumer Acceptance and Adoption of AI Robo-Advisors in the Fintech Industry	[102]
60	Students' adoption of AI-based teacher-bots (T-bots) for learning in higher education	[103]
61	Explanation of time perspectives in adopting AI service robots under different service settings	[104]
62	Digital humanism and artificial intelligence: the role of emotions beyond the human-machine interaction in Society 5.0	[105]
63	Adoption of AI-based chatbots for hospitality and tourism	[106]
64	Psychosocial Factors Affecting Artificial Intelligence Adoption in Health Care in China: Cross-Sectional Study	[107]

No	Title	Reference
65	The impact of personality traits and AI literacy on the adoption intentions of AI among design faculty in Chinese higher education	[108]
66	User acceptance of AI in transport: The case of SAE Level 3 Conditional Automated Driving	[109]
67	Bus drivers' intention to accept level 4 autonomous buses in ethical dilemmas: An extended technology acceptance model	[110]
68	Primary teachers' acceptance and sustained adoption of AI-powered learner corpora for writing instruction through TAM and ECM perspectives	[111]
69	Survey on Chinese users' acceptance of AI assistants: expanding the technology acceptance model	[112]
70	AI acceptance and Chinese EFL learners' behavioural engagement with mediating effects of motivation	[113]
71	Factors influencing intention to adopt an AI chatbot for learning in higher education: An integrated PLS-SEM, IPMA, and ANN approach	[114]
72	ThaiGAM: A dual-moderation framework for GenAI adoption in open learning innovation	[115]
73	Catenation between mHealth application advertisements and cardiovascular diseases: moderation of artificial intelligence (AI)-enabled internet of things, digital divide, and individual trust	[116]
74	Assessing ChatGPT acceptance and use in education: a comparative study among German-speaking students and teachers	[117]
75	AI in education: The mediating role of perceived trust in adoption decisions of school leaders	[118]
76	What motivates academics in Egypt toward generative AI tools? An integrated model of TAM, SCT, UTAUT2, perceived ethics, and academic integrity	[119]
77	The Use of Artificial Intelligence in Accounting Classes: Behavioural Insights from Students	[120]
78	An extended UTAUT model study on the adoption behaviour of artificial intelligence technology in the construction industry	[121]
79	Factors Influencing Generative AI Usage Intention in China: Extending the Acceptance-Avoidance Framework with Perceived AI Literacy	[122]
80	Determinants of Behavioral Intention to Use Generative AI: The Role of Trust, Personal Innovativeness, and UTAUT II Factors	[123]
81	Investigating users' acceptance of AI-based creativity support tools: an empirical study from China's creative industries	[124]
82	Understanding the intention to use artificial intelligence chatbots in education: The role of individual innovativeness and AI trust among university students	[125]
83	Artificial intelligence facilitators in higher education institutions: A student-centric exploration with comparative analysis in Asian countries	[126]
84	The factors affecting teachers' adoption of AI technologies: A unified model of external and internal determinants	[127]
85	Assessing Artificial Intelligence (AI) Literacy and Readiness in Thailand's Workforce: Challenges and Opportunities for Digital Transformation	[128]

No	Title	Reference
86	Artificial Intelligence Driven E-Services of New Generation Banks: Customer Perception, Attitude and Response Analysis	[129]
87	Determining Factors Influencing Indonesian Higher Education Students' Intention to Adopt Artificial Intelligence Tools for Self-Directed Learning Management	[130]
88	Understanding AI and Mobile Learning Adoption in Malaysian Universities: A UTAUT-Based Model	[131]
89	Extending the technology acceptance model: The role of subjective norms, ethics, and trust in AI tool adoption among students	[132]
90	Exploring Key Drivers for Embracing Artificial Intelligence in Public Relations Pedagogy	[133]
91	The Digital Transformation of Healthcare Through Intelligent Technologies: A Path Dependence-Augmented–Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology Model for Clinical Decision Support Systems	[134]
92	Evaluating the Impact of Artificial Intelligence Tools on Enhancing Student Academic Performance: Efficacy Amidst Security and Privacy Concerns	[135]
93	Behavioural Intention to use Artificial Intelligence (AI) among Accounting Students: Evaluating the Effect of Technology Readiness	[136]
94	A Society that Encourages AI: The Impact of Social Influence Factors on the Adoption of Generative AI Based on Cognitive Appraisal Theory	[137]
95	How do risks and ethical issues impact the adoption of artificial intelligence in auditing?	[138]
96	ChatGPT in higher education - A Student's perspective	[139]
97	The influence of subjective knowledge, technophobia and perceived enjoyment on design students' intention to use artificial intelligence design tools	[140]
98	AI in Banking: What Drives Generation Z to Adopt AI-Enabled Voice Assistants in Saudi Arabia?	[141]
99	Understanding User Acceptance of AI-Driven Chatbots in China's E-Commerce: The Roles of Perceived Authenticity, Usefulness, and Risk	[142]
100	Adoption of Artificial Intelligence Tools for English Language Learning Among Saudi EFL University Students: The Moderating Role of Faculty	[143]
101	Proposing a conceptual model for the adoption of artificial intelligence by teachers in STEM education	[144]
102	The Relevance of Trust in the Implementation of AI-Driven Clinical Decision Support Systems by Healthcare Professionals: An Extended UTAUT Model	[145]
103	What Emotions and Personalities Determine Acceptance of Generative AI?: Focusing on the CASA Paradigm	[146]
104	Assistive Tools or Insecurity: The Impact of Technological Readiness on Willingness to Use AI	[147]
105	AI adoption among adolescents in education: extending the UTAUT2 with psychological and contextual factors	[148]
106	Expanding the technology acceptance model: Trust as a mediator in the relationship between environmental factors and intent to use narrow AI	[149]

No	Title	Reference
107	Ethical dilemmas and the reconstruction of subjectivity in digital mourning in the age of AI: an empirical study on the acceptance intentions of bereaved family members of cancer patients	[150]
108	Exploring the determinants of AIGC usage intention based on the extended AIDUA model: a multi-group structural equation modeling analysis	[151]
109	Customer adoption of artificial intelligence in healthcare: An empirical investigation based on multiple samples	[152]
110	Integrating artificial intelligence (AI) in healthcare: advancing older adults' health management in Saudi Arabia through AI-powered chatbots	[153]
111	ChatGPT use in hospitality and tourism: a multi-analytic approach	[154]
112	Technology acceptance model for understanding consumer's behavioral intention to use artificial intelligence based online shopping platforms in Bangladesh	[155]
113	How sociodemographic factors relate to trust in artificial intelligence among students in Poland and the United Kingdom	[156]
114	Acceptance and use of ChatGPT in the academic community	[157]
115	Exploring the predictors of public acceptance of artificial intelligence-based resurrection technologies	[158]
116	An Evaluation of Artificial Intelligence Chatbots' Ethical Use, Attitudes Towards Technology, Behavioural Factors and Student Learning Outcomes in Collegiate Aviation Programs	[159]
117	Students' Intention toward Artificial Intelligence in the Context of Digital Transformation	[160]
118	Extended TAM based acceptance of AI-Powered ChatGPT for supporting metacognitive self-regulated learning in education: A mixed-methods study	[161]
119	Investigating consumers' adoption of AI chatbots for apparel shopping	[162]
120	Understanding the Adoption of Artificial Intelligence in Journalism: An Empirical Study in Vietnam	[163]
121	The Adoption of Artificial Intelligence in Serbian Hospitality: A Potential Path to Sustainable Practice	[164]
122	Medical professionals' adoption of AI-based medical devices: UTAUT model with trust mediation	[165]
123	Understanding Chinese University EFL Learners' Perceptions of AI in English Writing	[166]
124	Rethinking AI Acceptance in Corporate: A Human-Centric Extension of UTAUT	[167]
125	A Study on the Relationship between AI Anxiety and AI Behavioral Intention of Secondary School Students Learning English as a Foreign Language	[168]
126	Students' Flow Experience of Using AI-Powered Online English Learning Platforms	[169]
127	New Challenges of Learning Accounting With Artificial Intelligence: The Role of Innovation and Trust in Technology	[170]
128	The factors influencing teacher education students' willingness to adopt artificial intelligence technology for information-based teaching	[171]

No	Title	Reference
129	Acceptance of artificial intelligence among pre-service teachers: a multigroup analysis	[172]
130	Surveillance, security, and AI as technological acceptance	[173]
131	Examining the Adoption of AI-based Banking Chatbots: A Task Technology Fit and Network Externalities Perspective	[174]
132	Antecedents of understanding the investors' acceptance of artificial intelligence: Perceptions from the Jordanian context	[175]
133	Determinants of College Students' Actual Use of AI-Based Systems: An Extension of the Technology Acceptance Model	[176]
134	FACTORS INFLUENCING USERS' INTENTION TO ADOPT AI-BASED CYBERSECURITY SYSTEMS IN THE UAE	[177]
135	The Drivers of Acceptance of Artificial Intelligence–Powered Care Pathways among Medical Professionals: Web-Based Survey Study	[178]
136	The Effect of Using Artificial Intelligence on Learning Performance in Iraq: The Dual Factor Theory Perspective	[179]
137	Evaluating the Intention for the Adoption of Artificial Intelligence-Based Robots in the University to Educate the Students	[180]
138	A Multi-Industry Analysis of the Future Use of AI Chatbots	[181]
139	Intention to Adopt AI-Powered Online Service Among Tourism and Hospitality Companies	[182]
140	Home, sweet home: How well-being shapes the adoption of artificial intelligence-powered apartments in smart cities	[183]
141	Role of interaction quality and trust in the use of AI-based voice-assistant systems:	[184]
142	Factors Influencing the Adoption Intention of ai powered chatbot for Public Transport Services within a smart city	[185]

PENDING FOR APPROVAL

